

Internationalisation of Higher Education: A comparative study of educators' experiences

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Abstract

Across the global, Higher Education Institutions are prioritising Internationalisation. Gauging whether institutions fully achieve their priority of internationalisation is open to interpretation and academic debate itself. Indeed there are a range of definitions, understandings and applications of the term internationalisation' and these are often context based. According to Knight (2004), there are a "small number of academics or policy makers who are seriously studying the nuances and evolution of the term [internationalisation] itself given the changes and challenges that are before us" (p.9). When there is an inconsistent definition and understanding of internationalisation there are implications for educators within the HEI. In the face of internationalisation, the role of the educator is ever changing and impacted upon (Tran and Nguyen, 2015).

This thesis focused on a study of the practice of internationalisation within three HEIs: one in Australia, one in Japan, and one in Scotland. In this study, internationalisation was considered from the educator's perspective. The research explored the experiences of educators in terms of internationalisation. The investigation was positioned within an interpretivist paradigm. The epistemological underpinning of the study was interpretivism which offers a voice to the experiences of the educators who shared their lived experiences. The experiences of the educators were collected using a mixed method approach of questionnaires and semi-structured interviews. The data was analysed using basic descriptive analysis, Thematic Analysis and Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis.

The study found that, in order for internationalisation to be implemented and sustained within a HEI, the educator must be an integral part of the process. The research revealed ways in which internationalisation is understood within the micro and macro

contexts of Higher Education, and concludes that, for internationalisation to be successful, HEIs must acknowledge their educators as critical stakeholders in the process and provide them with appropriate support to fulfil their responsibilities in this area.

This research is significant in this field because it provides a practical and deeper understanding of how educators at three HEIs experience internationalisation and provides insights into how they can improve their understanding and contribution towards internationalisation in their HEI context.

Keywords: Internationalisation, educator experience, Higher Education Institutions

Author's Declaration

This thesis is the result of the author's original research. It has been composed by the author and has not been previously submitted for examination which has led to the award of a degree.

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Signature

Laura Wilson

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

CPD	Continuing Professional Development
FE	Further Education
HE	Higher Education
HEA	Higher Education Academy
HEI	Higher Education Institution
IaH	Internationalisation at Home
IAU	International Association of Universities
IHE	International Higher Education
IoC	Internationalisation of the Curriculum
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
UK	United Kingdom
UNESCO	The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation

CHAPTER ONE Introduction to the Study

Chapter Outline

This chapter introduces the necessity for this research in this area of educational research. The chapter explains reasons why the particular topic was chosen and how the study developed over time. It outlines the rationale for the study along with the research aim and questions. The chapter concludes with a thesis chapter outline and definitions of key terms used throughout the thesis.

Introduction

The research focuses on the perspective of the educator, examining the (perceived) impact of internationalisation on the educator through experiences in their own Higher Education Institution (HEI) context. Particular focus is placed upon how internationalisation affects the work and professional identities of educators in HEIs and how they respond to internationalisation in their own HEI context.

The study draws upon the experience of a group of educators who work in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), one in Australia, one in Japan and one in Scotland that have policy and goals based around the concept of internationalisation.

Statement of Problem

Internationalisation is currently a priority and goal for most Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) around the world; however, how it is successfully achieved and measured is subject to interpretation.

Internationalisation of HEIs is not a new concept or idea. Research focused on curriculum and student perspective is abundant (Sawir 2013; Vinther and Slethaug,

2013; Leask, 2009) whereas understanding of educator experience, influence and input of internationalisation is not. Indeed, there has been minimal focus on the staff perception of this issue (Dewey and Duff, 2009; Daniels, 2013; Schartner and Cho, 2017).

In the face of internationalisation, the role of the educator is ever changing and impacted upon (Tran and Nguyen, 2015). This study sought to understand current practice in regards to the implementation and process of internationalisation within a Higher Education Institutions and through the lens of the educator. In order to compare and contrast educators' experience in a variety of contexts, HEIs in Australia, Japan and Scotland have been chosen for the undertaking of data collection. This study will focus on what the educators' say about their experience, as well as try to understand the perceived impact and influence that the educator has on the effectiveness of internationalisation, which is currently an important issue common to most HEIs.

Development of the Study

This thesis seeks to understand the lived experiences of educators in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in regards to internationalisation. In order to do so the research is driven by several factors. One factor that influenced the development of this study is the researcher's own international experience as a student and educator in Australia, Japan and Scotland.

Returning to Scotland, from Australia, to complete this PhD has offered many opportunities for the researcher to gain a deeper understanding of the educators' experience in Scotland. This study has also allowed time for reflections on the researcher's experiences in Australia, Japan and Scotland from 2004-2019, including gaining confidence that the researcher's knowledge of the fieldwork sites would not

be a disadvantage and remaining impartial as a researcher was manageable and achievable (Coffey, 1999).

The HEI sector was chosen for this research as most of the literature pays specific attention to the sector of higher education rather than any other education sector. Also, an aim was to continue to contribute to research in the HE sector in the area of education and internationalisation.

Another factor that has driven this research is the limited interest in the opinion or experience of the people in charge of successfully implementing internationalisation, particularly the educator. The major focus and continued interest in internationalisation of HEIs from a student perspective or institutional perspective are vast and therefore researching the educator's perspective an area that requires further investigation.

Throughout the PhD journey the research aims and questions have had minimal alteration. Extensive review of relevant literature highlights that internationalisation is present in HE and it has significant impacts on several stakeholders. The literature review presents insights from key researchers and scholars in the field, identifying that despite common definitions of internationalisation focusing on international students and internationalisation of the curriculum there is limited discussion of the experience and implications internationalisation has on the educator in a HEI context.

This study attempts to address a gap in the literature by focussing on how the educator in HEI experiences and understands internationalisation, and what can be done to support the educator in having a more positive experience; as well as providing feedback to policy makers as to how they can support educators in their ambition and work load to effectively internationalise in their own HEI context.

Context of the Study

As previously noted, this study was conducted in three Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). Specifically, one HEI in Australia, one HEI in Japan and one HEI in Scotland.

The researcher had worked as an educator and studied at a post-graduate level the topic of education in Australia, Japan and Scotland. Through professional networks the researcher made contact with several HEIs in Japan and Australia and invited them to participate in this research. In the end the HEIs that agreed to take part in the research were not HEIs that the student had previously studied or worked in. In terms of the HEI in Scotland, the researcher had received a PhD studentship from this particular institution and it was necessary to include this institution in the research project. It is important to note that the researcher did not know any of the staff at the HEI who took part in the research via pilot study, questionnaire or semi-structured interview.

Within each of the three HEIs is a School or Faculty of Education. Each of these Schools of Education is responsible for informing and supporting future and current primary and secondary school teachers. The School of Education in each of the three HEIs were invited to take part in this current research. Certain members of the School of Education from each of the three HEIs became participants of this mixed methods research approach. A commonality amongst the semi-structured interview participants is that they are all members of School of Education within their HEI and have a role in Teacher Education.

In accordance with the participant information sheet and consent form, and in order to maintain some level of anonymity of the participants and HEIs, the following contextual information regarding HEI specifics is limited.

HEI Specific Context:

SCOTLAND: West of Scotland. School of Education is recognised as one of the leading education degrees in Scotland and the UK.

AUSTRALIA: New South Wales, Southern Region. Teacher Education at this HEI School of Education is renowned for quality educational experiences and student support.

JAPAN: Hyogo, Kyushu, South East Japan. School of Education at this HEI has a reputation for excellence in Initial Teacher Education in Japan.

The process of selecting the three HEIs and the participants was purposive as explained further in Chapter Three.

Objective of the Study

The objective of this study was to gain an understanding of the lived experience of educators in HEIs in regards to internationalisation. It is intended that this study offers a catalyst for discussion of the support required for educators in HEIs in order for internationalisation to be successfully achieved.

In order to meet the objective of the study, a sequential mixed method approach is utilised to collect and analyse data. Basic quantitative data analysis methods and ideas are utilised as well as thematic analysis, used in a traditional sense to understand the basic qualitative data from questionnaires. A more detailed and lengthy data collection method is in the form of semi-structured interviews. The data from the semi-structured interviews was analysed using Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA). IPA was predominantly applied to gather evidence to further understand the perceptions and experiences of a sample of educators in Australia, Japan and Scotland HEIs. Using

IPA as a tool for analysis was an attempt to ensure research participants responses, shared experiences, and reflections were represented effectively.

Significance of the Study

It has been claimed that there is a lack of analysis of how internationalisation processes affect HE, specifically educators, and that studies examining the impacts are conducted infrequently (Bedenlier and Zawacki-Richter, 2015). Furthermore, according to Stier (2002) and Teichler (2017) often discussions on internationalisation in higher education focus predominantly on student and faculty mobility whereas other aspects are largely left behind. Therefore, this present study is of significance and will contribute the limited research surrounding internationalisation and the educator in HE.

Purpose of the Study

The term ‘internationalisation’ is understood and applied differently depending on context (Knight, 2007). There are many and varied definitions of internationalisation. This research seeks to understand how internationalisation is defined and understood by educators in HE and the impacts of and for educators within the HEI when internationalisation takes place, particularly when internationalisation is a key priority for current HEIs.

Knight (2013) states that the importance of internationalisation within HEIs is recognised but questions if the benefits, risks and processes are fully understood. Knight (2013) notes that there is no question that internationalisation has transformed the work of higher education, but it is essential to remember that internationalisation has also undergone fundamental changes itself. In 2004, Knight determined that only a small number of academics or policy makers were seriously studying the nuances

and evolution of the term internationalisation given the changes and challenges it involved. Hence, this study is most contemporary and of significant importance, especially for the 21st Century HEI.

A HEI becoming or remaining internationalised, is a process that is deemed necessary for the success of the 21st Century HEI (OECD, 2014). In order for internationalisation to take place and thrive within an HEI, it could be suggested that the educator must be the key agent of change in this process, that they are directly linked to the success of internationalisation. This contention is supported by Jiang and Carpenter (2013) who suggest that HEI internationalisation is primarily an internal matter of integration rather than a process driven only by external environments. Furthermore, the educator must understand the strategy and have adequate connection to the vision (Alashoo et al., 2005, Jiang and Carpenter, 2013).

Agnew and Kahn (2014) have identified that although the focus of learning has broadened and shifted to the process of learning, institutions of higher education have been slow to respond to this new reality of internationalisation. In this regard they continue to state how important it is that higher education leadership creates institutional cultures that are responsive to global forces and provide diverse learning experiences needed for today's workforce and civic life. As Iuspa (2010) points out, in regards to the process of internationalisation, a HEI needs to be aware of how their institutional management (policy) sustain and manage their internationalisation process as it is a process that is complex and involves many stakeholders. It is also one that is inevitable and university wide. Consequently, the role of the educator is significant in this process.

Research Aims and Questions

The aim of the thesis is to understand the experiences of the educator in HE in regards to internationalisation in their HEI context. Furthermore, the research aims to explore how educators define, understand and experience internationalisation within their own HEI context as well as give voice to their recommendations suggested to improve the educator's experience and understanding of internationalisation in HE.

Based upon the gaps in the literature, the study addressed the following questions:

Research Question One: How do educators in Higher Education (HE) define and understand internationalisation?

Research Question Two: What are the educators' experiences of internationalisation in their Higher Education Institutions (HEIs)?

Research Question Three: What are the educators' views about the future of internationalisation in Higher Education (HE) and their recommendations for improvement?

Structure of Thesis

The thesis is organised into six chapters as follows.

Chapter One provides a comprehensive picture of the research. The chapter includes an introduction to the background of the research study. It introduces the purpose, focus and the relevance of the research and the present study. This chapter also briefly outlines the methodology adopted in this research, the researcher's position in this study and, finally, the thesis structure along with definitions of key terms used throughout the thesis.

Chapter Two reviews the literature considered pertinent to the research topic. This chapter presents the background and context of this research by referring to relevant literature. The chapter begins by reviewing the literature around internationalisation and how it is understood and defined in Higher Education. It provides a review of the rationales and perceived benefits associated with internationalisation in Higher Education Institutions before providing a review of the literature directly related to internationalisation in Australia, Japan and Scotland. The chapter provides a review of research relating to the experiences of stakeholders in terms of internationalisation. Each of these sections of the literature review support the development of the research questions which arise from the gap in the literature which is positioned at the end of the chapter.

Chapter Three describes the methodological framework of the research, including the philosophical assumptions underpinning the research. The chapter provides the reasons for the choice of research methods, a sequential mixed methods approach utilising questionnaires and semi-structured interviews, explains how the research was conducted, outlines the recruitment procedure and describes the data collection

procedures and explains the approaches to data analysis, including Thematic Analysis (TA) and Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA). This chapter details the process using TA and IPA including a step by step description of analysis. Participants of the study are also introduced in this chapter. The chapter concludes with an explanation of ethical considerations and how rigour and reliability was established throughout the research process of this study.

Chapter Four presents the findings of the research. The chapter begins with an introduction outlining the structure of the chapter followed by a section explaining the robustness of the questionnaire quantitative research data. The chapter then provides an introduction to the codes and themes derived from the data and explains how they relate to the research questions and relevant literature of the present study. The findings from both the questionnaire and semi-structured interviews are presented in direct relation to the three research questions. Themes are identified and explored. Some extracts from the data from the eleven participants are used throughout the chapter in order to preserve the educators' voices and to provide an interpretative account of their understandings of the meaning of their experiences. The data is presented to demonstrate convergence as well as divergence between the participants. Chapter Four also includes a section providing further detailed interview evidence. This particular section provides a greater insight into the interviewees, their responses and the benefits of using IPA in qualitative research.

Chapter Five discusses the findings from the previous chapter in relation to the objectives of this study and the relevant literature. The chapter identifies how such findings build upon the research of others and why this research has been necessary. The discussion chapter is presented in the format of each research question, Research Question One, Research Question Two and Research Question Three, supported with

associated themes identified previously in Chapter Four as well as extracts the eleven participants are used throughout the chapter in order to provide the educators' voices and to provide an interpretative account of their understandings of the meaning of their experiences. The chapter also provides some identification and discussion of the differences and similarities that exist amongst educators in Australia, Japan and Scotland supported with relevant literature.

Chapter Six provides a summary of the findings and includes a discussion of the potential limitations of the research and its practical implications. The chapter includes an autobiographical reflection by the researcher. It also considers how the findings can translate into recommendations for practice and future research into the area of internationalisation in Higher Education.

Conclusion

In summary, it is the intention of this research to understand the experience of educators' in regards to internationalisation in their HEI context. The present study will therefore build on the work concerned with educators in HE but from a different perspective. This study does not provide all the answers for HEIs in the face of internationalisation and is context specific.

By doing this, a sample of educators in Australia, Japan and Scotland can be represented and provide some insight to their current experience and future recommendations in terms of internationalisation in their HEI context.

Definitions of Terms

Definition of key terms are included to provide a clear and unambiguous understanding of their meaning when applied throughout the thesis.

The **educator** in regards to this specific study is a person who is employed to teach and research in a Higher Education Institution. The educator in this study is not directly involved in policy relating to internationalisation and is not in a position of authority or responsibility within the HEI relating to internationalisation for example a Dean or Director of Internationalisation.

A **policymaker** in this present study is a person responsible for or involved in formulating policies, particularly in terms of policy relating to internationalisation. Policymakers in this study may include but are not limited to members of the HEI Executive.

The definition of **student** used in this study is an adaptation of the one provided by the HEA (2014). A student is inclusive of undergraduates and postgraduates studying within their country of origin as well as those studying transnationally, who can contribute to as well as benefit from internationalising Higher Education.

Disconnect is a term used in this thesis that refers explicitly to the lack of connection. The lack of connection is in particular reference to the phenomenon of internationalisation in Higher Education and difference of opinion between stakeholders relating to policy and practice of internationalisation.

Professional development is referred to often in this study. The definition applied throughout this thesis is of Continuing Professional Development which has been defined by the Quality Assurance Agency for Higher Education as a wide range of

“training programmes, some leading to formal awards, to extend a person’s employment-related knowledge, skills and understanding” (QAA, 2018, p.7).

Rationale is a set of reasons for a course of action. Throughout this thesis, rationale is referred to as the reason for a course of action that a HEI implements. The rationale is directly related to why and how a HEI internationalises.

CHAPTER TWO Literature Review

Introduction

This chapter provides a review of the relevant literature on internationalisation. A key goal of the literature review is to identify and critically examine the ways in which the concept and process of internationalisation is understood within Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). The concept and process of internationalisation in Higher Education (HE) have changed to some extent and in some senses, but they remain unchanged in several other regards. The literature review aims to provide a contextual understanding of what internationalisation is and how it may be defined in the context of HE. It examines the rationales for, and perceived benefits, of internationalisation in HE, and considers previous research that has focused on the internationalisation experiences of HE educators. This chapter moreover seeks to identify important gaps in the existing academic literature.

What is internationalisation?

Internationalisation of HE is a world-wide phenomenon (Marmolejo, 2010; Egron-Polak and Hudson, 2014). According to Hellsten (2008), internationalisation is undoubtedly “part and parcel of the current contemporary HE environment” (p.83). Rider-Grant (2015) considers internationalisation to be an integral part of HE and argues that it cannot be avoided. Schartner and Cho (2017) deem internationalisation in HE as a ubiquitous term because it can be understood, applied and defined differently depending upon different contexts. Similarly, Knight (2007; 2014) points out that even though internationalisation is a term used by the large majority of HE institutions, it can mean very different things across these contexts. Komotar (2018) refers to internationalisation as an umbrella term, while Childress (2009) questions

whether there can ever be a consensus about what internationalisation of HE may mean due to its ever-evolving nature and context-specific influences. Taken to its logical conclusion, an inconceivable definitional consensus may justify the complete atomisation of discussions around a definition due to subjectivity, where all opinions are equally valued and no simplifications or generalities should be pursued, whether informed by practise or academic discussion. According to Knight (2013) while a universal definition may not be possible, a definition that can be used in a broad range of contexts across countries and regions of the world would be beneficial. However, Knight (2013) cautions that a

“definition needs to avoid being an instrument that standardises or homogenises the internationalisation process around the world by specifying the rationales, benefits, outcomes, actors, activities, and stakeholders of internationalisation. What is critical is that the international dimension relates to all aspects of HE and the role that it plays in society” (Knight, 2013, p.85).

Internationalisation of HE is by no means a recent phenomenon (Jiang, 2008). Stier (2002) points out that an interest in the world, other people, and other cultures is nothing new and has always been a motive for academic activity. Early examples of internationalisation of education were the University of Paris’ Papal Bull of 1231 and the degree to which scholars would communicate internationally or study scholars from other countries. Therefore, Teichler (2004) notes that “the claim that HE is internationalising or ought to internationalise is somewhat surprising because universities have long been considered one of society’s most international institutions” (p.8). Svensson and Wilhborg (2010) concur, arguing that “universities are [...] by nature of their commitment to advancing human knowledge, international institutions” (Svensson and Wilhborg, 2010, p. 597). Yet, although internationalisation in itself is

not ‘new’, there still continues to be uncertainty around how it should be defined especially with the recent expansion in higher education (Robson, Almeida and Schartner, 2017). Stier (2002) has pointed out that, although internationalisation in HE is a popular term and frequently used in varying contexts and for diverse purposes, it remains ambiguous and unclear. This point was recently reiterated by Yesufu (2018), who noted that “although internationalisation is widespread, the main motives, methods and measures of its effectiveness need further elaboration” (p.155).

Due to changing notions and perceptions over time and context (Green and Whitsed, 2013), Guruz (2011) suggests that definitions of internationalisation, as they relate to HE, have become more sophisticated, however, there is still considerable confusion about the nature of internationalisation of HE. One explanation for such confusion over definitions can be that in the context of HE, each HEI may seek to define internationalisation in accordance to their own goals and approaches. This is internationalisation defined due to a self-serving motive, rather than to illuminate the subject matter. And as a result of this motive, the way in which an HEI approaches internationalisation can vary in substance from the way another HEI does it. This can lead to lack of coherence and inconsistent approaches (Korhonen and Weil, 2015). According to Agnew and Kahn (2015), the process of internationalisation in HE would benefit from an approach that recognises the many meanings of and motivations for internationalisation, and builds bridges to work through the gaps between them. This is precisely the focus of this doctoral thesis in relation to the role educator.

Many definitions of internationalisation of HE refer to it as a *process*. The advantage of referring to it as a ‘process’ is to deliberately highlight the continuous and ongoing nature of internationalisation (Guruz, 2011). For example, the OECD’s definition frames internationalisation of HE as a complex of processes whose combined effect,

whether planned or not, is to enhance the international dimension of the experience of higher education in universities and similar educational institutions. (OECD, 1994). One of the most often quoted definitions of internationalisation is Knight's (2004) which refers to internationalisation as "the *process* of integrating an international, intercultural, or global dimension into the purpose, functions or delivery of post-secondary education" (p.11). An updated version of Knight's (2004) definition is De Wit et al.'s (2015) which refers to internationalisation of HE as "the intentional *process* of integrating an international, intercultural or global dimension into the purpose, functions and delivery of post-secondary education, in order to enhance the quality of education and research for all students and staff, and to make a meaningful contribution to society" (p.281). Yemini's (2015) definition is similar in its focus on internationalisation as "the *process* of encouraging integration of multicultural, multilingual, and global dimensions within the education system" (p.21), but more specific in terms of the key aim, which, according to Yemini (2015), is "to instil in learners a sense of global citizenship" (p.21). Coelen's (2016) definition is also centred on the learner:

"internationalisation of higher education constitutes the provision of an environment containing such elements that a learner is given the opportunity to attain achieved learning outcomes associated with international awareness and intercultural competence" (p.40).

In the late 1990s, Knight (1997; 1999) identified four important approaches to internationalisation in HE: the activity approach, the competency approach, the ethos approach and the process approach. While several alternative approaches could be taken, Knight's method is a useful means of summarising key narratives and now these four approaches will be explained. The *activity approach* refers to distinct

activities, often mobility related such as student and staff exchanges. These are specific to only one group of students or staff, that is say those involved in these activities, and these participants are not integrated fully in the academic and social life of the HEI. The *competency approach* refers to the development of intercultural sensitivity and competence in staff and students. The *ethos approach* refers to the development of a culture to support internationalisation. Finally, the *process approach* is the most comprehensive and refers to efforts to integrate an international dimension into all aspects of the HEI, including policy and practice.

Knight's (1997; 1999) process approach to internationalisation of HE, as elaborated by de Wit et al. (2015) to include a statement about intended outcomes, frames the conceptualisation of internationalisation of HE at this analysis is at the heart of this thesis. In other words, internationalisation of HE in this thesis is defined as a systematic approach to integrate an international dimension across all aspects of academic and social life in HE, with a view to preparing students to live and work effectively as global citizens in an internationalised world.

Although internationalisation is clearly not new to universities, in the recent context of globalisation several new and important issues are raised, see Carpentier and Unterhalter (2010). According to Svensson and Wilhborg (2010) globalisation includes politically and market regulated flows of people, money, goods and services (p.596). The British Council (2016) states that "international HE is increasingly becoming a global policy preoccupation" (p.17) and "there is hardly a country left unaffected by the global flows of students, teaching and research" (British Council, 2016, p.2). Others have also suggested that internationalisation of HE is linked to globalisation, in that it is part of an institutions and country response to globalisation

(Coelen, 2013; Friesen, 2012). Indeed, some consider that internationalisation of HE is the result of globalisation (Brandenburg and de Wit, 2011).

What drives internationalisation processes? Knight (1994) suggests that the internationalisation process in HE can be affected by a range of factors including awareness amongst all relevant stakeholders, staff commitment, planning, operationalisation, review, and reinforcement. According to Knight (1994), commitment and support from senior leaders is instrumental for internationalisation to become a central element of an institution's strategic plan. Staff involvement (Mestenhauser, 2002) and university wide collaboration (Iuspa, 2010) have also been identified as important factors in the development of internationalisation in HE. To develop a holistic international dimension, Iuspa (2010) recommends that HEIs should fit into place an organisational framework that will embed their international activities within the HE mission, ethos and goals.

At this point of the discussion it is also worthwhile considering how essential is internationalisation in education. Johnston and Edelstein (1993) state that "the expansion of the international dimension of HE is not so much an option as a responsibility" (p.3). More recently, Morris (2009) has argued that HEIs should take an active role in addressing international challenges and opportunities through their education, research and service missions. The development of intercultural competence is central to this (Deardoff, 2009). Intercultural competence has been defined as "the ability to think and act in interculturally appropriate ways" (Hammer, et al. 2003, p.422), or, in other words intercultural competence is the "appropriate and effective management of interaction between people who, to some degree or another, represent different or divergent affective, cognitive, and behavioural orientations to the world" (Spitzberg and Changnon, 2009, p.7). Related concepts include

intercultural understanding, which is the “ability to live and work productively and harmoniously with people having different value, backgrounds, and habits” (Bok, 2009, p.9), and intercultural sensitivity, which is “the ability to discriminate and experience relevant cultural differences” (Hammer et al. 2003, p.423).

Other authors having taken more of a values approach to assessing intercultural competence. Hett (1993) has suggested that an important starting point in the development of intercultural competence is global mindedness, an outlook which enables individuals to see beyond national boundaries, to connect to the world community and to feel a sense of responsibility for its members. Global mindedness can promote cultural pluralism and globalcentrism, which are essential for preparing younger generations for the cosmopolitan world in which they are bound to interact with foreign nationals, different ethnic and cultural groups (Bok, 2009). As early as 1981 it was noted that “international understanding has come to represent a very practical and urgent need, and clearly HE has the major responsibility in this area in the long term” (Harari, 1981, p.1). Internationalisation is one way through which HEIs can fulfil this responsibility.

To sum up, internationalisation in HE can be defined as an intentional process of integrating an international dimension into the life of a HEI. It should be stated that this definition could be criticised, however, since the drive towards internationalisation may not be entirely *intentional* nor achieved by a short-term or single *process*. A HEI may unintentionally develop a greater sense of and/or be characterised as progressing internationalisation, while endeavouring to fulfil other strategic objectives. For example, internationalisation may be an unintended consequence of pursuing excellence in research and teaching. Also there may be repeated attempts over several decades, which use different means to achieve

internationalisation. However, the advantages of this definition of internationalisation include clear reference to cross-country engagement and that by referring explicitly to the life of a HEI, this goal becomes of fundamental importance to that institution.

In many respects, HEI internationalisation is a response to globalisation and to the need to produce global graduates who have economic or cultural value. Global graduates can be considered as those highly educated individuals who are interculturally aware and well prepared to navigate the global economy. The next section will consider this aspect of internationalisation of HE further, through an examination of the reasons why HEIs are internationalising.

Rationale and Perceived Benefits of Internationalisation

Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) are internationalising for several reasons and according to Galloway and Rose (2015) “internationalisation of HE remains a priority for universities worldwide” (Galloway and Rose, 2015, p. 230).

Whilst internationalisation remains a priority for HEIs, “the goals of internationalisation are continuously evolving, ranging from educating global citizens, building capacity for research, to generating income from international student tuition fees and the quest to enhance institutional prestige” (IAU, 2012, p.2). A need for HEIs to better articulate their internationalisation strategies and processes has been highlighted frequently in the literature (Childress, 2009; Friesen, 2012). Indeed, De Wit (2002) suggests that a clear rationale as to why HEI should engage in internationalisation will support them in developing their strategies and processes.

Over time, several scholars have examined the rationales for internationalisation in HE (Altbach and Knight, 2007; de Wit, 1999; Knight, 1997; 1999; Seeber et al., 2016).

They have concluded that the rationales that drive the process of internationalisation can vary between HEIs, yet they are likely to fall into broad categories. Knight (1997, 1999, 2008) has proposed four such categories: academic, economic, political and cultural-social. These categories have been reiterated by others scholar including Qiang (2003) and de Wit (2002) consequently, they provide a useful framework to help us understand the reasons behind HEIs' efforts to internationalise.

A key rationale for internationalisation in HEIs proposed by Knight (1997; 1999, 2008) and others (Aigner et al., 1992; Johnston and Edelstein, 1993, Knight and De Wit, 1995; Scott, 1992) is the economic benefit derived from international activity, mainly in the form of the institutional benefits of increased income generated from the fees paid by international students. Although it is important to note that there can be negative consequences from increasingly framing internationalisation as a means of generating additional fee revenue. For example, increasing marketisation in education, which consequently overshadows the other important goals of higher education.

Another key rationale for internationalisation of HE is founded on concerns around a country's position in the world and the role education can play in improving this position. Internationalisation of HE can be seen as a form of investment which can enhance a country's prestige or 'soft' diplomatic power and give it a competitive advantage (IAU, 2012). As a recent report by the British Council (2016) highlighted, "the value and benefits of international collaboration, student and academic mobility and exchange are reaped by individuals and institutions, and support the development and building of nations" (British Council, 2016, p.2). Knight (1997; 1999, 2008) refers to this as a political rationale for internationalisation of HE.

The academic rationale for internationalisation of HE is equally important and focuses on the academic benefits a HEI can gain from international activity. These academic rationales include alignment with international academic standards through engagement in international research and scholarship networks. Also included are the benefits of an internationalised curriculum and the opportunities it avails for students to learn about international developments in their field of study. Marmolejo (2010) has usefully summarised the academic rationales for internationalisation of HE as follows: to enhance the international profile of the institution; to improve student preparedness for a globalised world; to strengthen research and knowledge production and exchange; and to diversify its faculty and staff.

The cultural and social rationale is also significant and refers to HEIs' efforts to internationalise in order to prepare graduates to be global citizens with intercultural understanding (Green, 2012). As Knight (1997) puts it "the acknowledgement of cultural and ethnic diversity within and between countries is considered as a strong rationale for the internationalisation of a nation's education system [and] one of the strongest rationales for internationalising the teaching and learning experience of students in HE" (Knight, 1997, p. 11).

Perceived Benefits of Internationalisation

It could be argued, the benefits of internationalisation for an HEI are multiple and varied. To the contrary is the view that there are potential risks and unintended consequences (Knight, 2013). Indeed, it has been suggested it is unclear what the main driving force is for internationalisation of HEIs (Bedenlier and Zawacki-Richter, 2015; Gao, 2015). Therefore, Knight (2013, p. 85) clearly states the need for more

fastidious analysis and sombre debate of internationalisation's "values and purposes" (p.85).

Motives around internationalisation in HEIs can be questioned (Knight, 2015; Tilak, 2015) and it is important to carefully delineate the positive and negative consequences (Bedenlier and Zawacki-Richter, 2015, p. 187). Knight (2013) raises the fundamental question of whether the benefits, risks and processes of internationalisation are fully understood. It is therefore necessary to consider the aims that are driving internationalisation (Hudzik and Stohl, 2009). Particularly, as Stier (2002) noted that internationalisation is said to enrich Higher Education (HE) which is still the case according to Rider-Grant (2015) who suggest that internationalisation is now an integral part of HE and it cannot be avoided.

Internationalisation is now part of a strategy at many education institutions to enhance prestige, global competitiveness and revenue (IAU, 2012, p.4). Internationalisation can be beneficial for a university's reputation (Delgado-Marquez et al., 2013). Furthermore, Ng (2012, p.440) posits that in order for HE systems to be more globally competitive, the nature of competitiveness itself is being acutely stressed.

For some HEIs, establishing an international profile or global standing is becoming more important than reaching international standards of excellence (IAU, 2012). Marmolejo (2010) considers the top five reasons for internationalising an institution to be: to enhance the international profile of the institution; improve student preparedness; internationalise the curriculum; strengthen research and knowledge production; and diversify its faculty and staff.

The Research Report UK HE International Unit (Universities UK, 2008) states that universities are international organisations with a diverse staff and student body which

is perceived as a net benefit. The report highlighted that an international dimension is essential in order for the university to remain competitive and for it to prosper.

Internationalisation includes partnerships between HEIs and there are a range of benefits associated with this process including financial revenue, internationalisation of the curriculum and mobility. Also, internationalisation is often associated with student and staff mobility, increased market share of international staff and students, to improve in global rankings (Lumby and Foskett, 2016) and increase of internationalisation at home (Robson et al., 2018).

In a valuable study, Komotar (2018) pointed out that internationalisation is of key importance for improving the quality of HE. And it is this quality improvement that provides the payoffs. Over time, there have been several initiatives for measuring and assessing the quality of internationalisation (Aerden, 2015; Knight, 2005; van der Wende, 1999). Yesufu (2018) identified how to measure the quality and progress of internationalisation in a HE institution in regards to international curriculum, policy and research and mobility. De Wit et al.'s (2015) definition of internationalisation highlights the importance of international curriculum, policy and research in order to improve teaching and learning in HEIs around the world as it suggests that internationalisation is a process that enhances the quality of education for all.

Another perceived benefit of internationalisation in HEIs is that they prepare students as global citizens. One popular aim of internationalisation is to prepare students to be globally aware (Green, 2012). The 4th IAU Global Survey (2013) identified that student knowledge improvement and appreciation of international issues remain the most significant expected benefit of internationalisation. The social and economic dimensions of globalisation increasingly impact people's lives and this is the central

context for HEI internationalisation. Educators are challenged to bring forward a theoretical basis for and understanding of this internationalisation (Svensson and Wilhborg, 2010, p.609).

One obvious suggestion is that internationalisation of a HE has greatly benefitted some areas more than others. Rose and McKinley (2018) argue that English-speaking nations have been key beneficiaries of internationalisation, irrespective of the broader incentives to internationalise.

According to Knight (2013) there is no question internationalisation has transformed the work of HE, but it is essential to remember that internationalisation has undergone fundamental changes and may continue to do so in the future. Green (2012) states that the importance of measurement and assessment of outcomes will only increase as internationalisation in increasingly pivotal to education quality and engagement.

To summarise, IAU (2012) inform us that “the benefits of internationalisation are clear” (p.4). The many benefits include improved quality of teaching and learning as well as research, and a deeper engagement with national, regional global issues and stakeholders. However, some of these clear benefits are contested and when an HEI intends to internationalise, the IAU suggest that they “make every effort to avoid or at least mitigate its potential adverse consequences” (IAU, 2012, p.4). Nonetheless, and irrespective of the perceived benefits of HEI internationalisation, the impact of the global environment on HEIs has been considered to be “inescapable” (Marginson and van der Wende, 2007, p.188).

The following section provides further detail in terms of international context with specific examples of internationalisation policy and processes from HEIs in Australia,

Japan and Scotland. This group of countries is also important in the analysis later in the thesis.

Internationalisation in Australia, Japan and Scotland

Internationalisation in Australian Higher Education

Explicit efforts to internationalise Australian HE go back to the Colombo Plan, an Australian government scheme that was developed in the 1950s to provide humanitarian aid to developing Asian countries, particularly in the Asia Pacific region. A key element of the scheme was to offer young people from these regions financial support to study in Australian HEIs (Kell and Vogl, 2007; Oakman, 2010; Worthington, 2014). After the Colombo Plan had run for many years, changes in the Australian HE landscape, including decrease in state funding and regulation (Marginson and Considine, 2000), resulted in a shift of the internationalisation focus of Australian HEIs from primarily a humanitarian project to a more economically driven exercise with emphasis on attracting full-fee paying international students alongside providing scholarship funded places (Burke, 2012). As a result, internationalisation in Australian HE evolved from aid to trade (Adams, Banks and Olsen, 2011), that is from an activity whose main aim was to promote inter-cultural relationships to a commercial enterprise with fees becoming a major source of income for HEIs (Harman, 2005). This model of internationalisation has attracted criticism for what has been perceived by some as a commercial orientation (Forbes-Mewett and Nyland, 2012).

Although inward student mobility has been the main component of the history of internationalisation in Australian HE (Leask, 2003; Adams et al., 2011), the 1990s saw Australia expanding its internationalisation activities to also include outward student

mobility, internationalisation of the curriculum and the development of international research links (Back et al., 1996). Ongoing developments on all fronts resulted in what Hudzik (2015) refers to as ‘comprehensive internationalisation’ with economic benefits arising from international student fees complemented by social and cultural benefits associated with inward and outward mobility, as well as academic benefits derived from international scholarship and research networks and collaborations (Ng, 2012).

Australia’s commitment to internationalisation was reiterated through the New Colombo Plan, which was launched in 2014 and aimed to provide opportunities for Australian undergraduates to study and undertake internships, placements and research in the Indo-Pacific region (Australian Government, 2019). When the New Colombo Plan started as a pilot in 2014, over 1300 Australian students took part across four pilot locations – Indonesia, Singapore, Japan and Hong Kong. By the end of 2020, 40,000 Australian students will have had the opportunity to experience living, studying and working across 40 locations in the Indo-Pacific. The Australian Government is hoping that the relationships and networks that have been developed over the years in the context of the New Colombo Plan will contribute to Australia's future prosperity (Australian Government, 2019).

The New Colombo Plan was complemented by the National Strategy for International Education 2025 which was launched in 2016 (Australian Government, 2016). This strategy aims to promote Australian HEIs as desirable destinations for international students with world-leading education and research activities and services (Australian Government, 2016). It should be noted these are government initiatives, therefore focused to some extent on the interest of government ministers such as economic goals

including employability, however, there are clear individual benefits including internship and placements for students.

To sum up, Australian HE's internationalisation has developed over the years from a mainly humanitarian endeavour offering scholarships to international students from developing countries, to a more commercial enterprise aiming to promote Australia's position as a key player in the educational internationalisation field.

Internationalisation in Japanese Higher Education

Vosse (2019) traces attempts to internationalise Japanese HE back to the Meiji period (1886-1912) with its aspiration to give Japan a competitive edge and bring it on level with the West. HEIs were expected to contribute to this through an internationalised curriculum informed by Western ideas and technologies, and through inward and outward mobility. However, according to Vosse (2019), this opening up to western influences was tightly controlled to ensure that only influences considered beneficial for Japan's development were allowed through.

At the beginning of the 21st Century, Japan's concern with its global position and competitiveness were as significant as they were at the beginning of the 20th century (Vosse, 2019). With only a few Japanese HEIs making it into the global top 100, a number of strategies were put in place to boost internationalisation and, by extension, the position of Japanese HE in global rankings (Newby et al., 2009). In 2001 an education reform plan was introduced by the Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology (MEXT). One of the goals of this plan was to establish universities of 'world class' status (Eades, 2005; Newby et al., 2009). Support for the achievement of this goal was provided through the 2005 "Strategic Fund for

Establishing International Headquarters in Universities”. This fund aimed to support HEIs in their efforts to establish an internationally competitive academic environment. However, a 2009 OECD review of higher education in Japan commented that despite the recognition of the need for change, such change was difficult due to a number of obstacles, including conservatism and excessive attention to means rather than ends. Despite the obstacles, Japan’s efforts to internationalise its HE continued. In 2009, a project entitled “Establishing University Network for Internationalization” and known as Global 30 Project was launched (Yonezawa, 2011). This aimed to promote internationalisation of the academic environment of Japanese HEIs by enrolling international students, providing international students with access to Japanese language and culture, and establishing overseas offices to promote international cooperation (Yonezawa, 2011). In 2014, this project was replaced by the new “Top Global University Project”. One of the aims of this project was to increase the number of foreign educators or educators with qualifications from foreign countries working in Japanese HEIs. Furthermore, the project aimed to increase the level of inward and outward student mobility through exchange programmes, and the number of foreign language instruction programmes offered by Japanese HEIs. These aims reflected Japan’s desire to increase its competitiveness by boosting the position of Japanese HEIs in global rankings and by ensuring that Japanese nationals graduating from Japanese HEIs have the necessary knowledge and skills to function optimally in global society (Yonezawa, 2011).

The “Top Global University Project” (2014) appeared to be more comprehensive and placed particular emphasis on reforming institutional governance, administration and strategic planning in an attempt to transform Japanese HE (Yonezawa and Shimmi 2016). Yet, progress was slow and transformation was hindered by continued

government control (Yonezawa and Shimmi, 2016). It has been suggested that a tension between Japan's desire to develop an international profile on the one hand and to preserve its national identity on the other has also affected the success of this project (Burgess, 2015; Yonezawa and Shimmi, 2016).

Worthy of note here is Japan's emphasis on using English as means to increase internationalisation in its HE sector. While developing English language proficiency has been included as a target in the various internationalisation projects for Japanese HE, on the ground there has been resistance to use a language that some perceive as a threat to their national identity (Morita, 2015). Yet, English proficiency is considered as central to the development of 'global human resources', a term used in Japan to refer to Japanese citizens who can function internationally while pursuing goals whose purpose is to benefit Japan's economic and social standing (Yamada and Yamada, 2014). According to the Japanese Council on Promotion of Human Resource for Globalization Development, which was established in May 2011, global human resources must have "linguistic and communication skills, self-direction, a spirit of challenge, cooperativeness and flexibility, a sense of responsibility and mission, and an understanding of other cultures coupled with a sense of Japanese identity" (Yamada and Yamada, 2014, p.42). While it is clear there are several goals, the challenge is whether they are always complimentary or indeed whether they conflict with one another. The latter would imply trade-offs in implementing an internationalisation strategy.

It has been observed by the literature that key amongst the skills needed by global human resources is proficiency in English (Yamada and Yamada, 2014; Wang, 2018), which explains the inclusion of English language specific aims in internationalisation efforts in Japanese HE, including efforts to recruit international educators. Yet, despite

these intentions, significant barriers still affect the use and development of English within Japanese HE. Some of these barriers are structural such as the low numbers of international educators, despite efforts to increase their numbers. While others are attitudinal, such as reluctance by Japanese students and staff to embrace English (Yamada and Yamada, 2014).

As this overview indicates, Japanese HE's internationalisation efforts aimed to develop Japan's competitiveness and positioning in the world. Japan has launched a series of internationalisation projects over the years, focusing on internationalising the curriculum, recruiting international educators, and increasing inward and outward mobility. The progress of these efforts has been affected by structural barriers and an ongoing tension between Japan's desire to internationalise and its concern to maintain its national identity. Moving forward, a more systematic and coordinated approach may help bring about the desired benefits without compromising Japan's distinct cultural identity (Vosse, 2019).

Internationalisation in Scottish Higher Education

Although the UK has elements of a single HE system and issues such as quality assurance and immigration are coordinated at UK level, each of the four nations, Scotland, Northern Ireland, England and Wales, has devolved powers over the operation of its HEIs. These devolved power include control of their national fee system (Mellors-Bourne, Jones and Woodfield, 2015). Traditionally, UK HEIs have received government funding, however, such funding has been gradually reduced and UK HEIs have had to rely on alternative funding streams to finance their activities. The recruitment of international students has offered British HEIs an additional income. How reliable the income is, is questionable. One widespread perception is

that the additional income is no longer an opportunity but it is increasingly considered to be a constraint. With increasing running costs, the number of full-fee paying international students required to provide necessary income has increased and competition amongst HEIs to secure this income has become intense (Weedon and Kong, 2015).

In a recent report on international students in Scotland (Scottish Government, 2018), the Scottish Government stated that of the 241,935 undergraduate and postgraduate students enrolled in Scottish HEIs in 2016/17, 189,630 (78%) were UK domiciled. In contrast 31,045 (13%) were non- EU domiciled and 21,245 (9%) were EU (non- UK) domiciled. The Scottish Government report stated that international students account for 22% of students at Scottish HEIs compared to 19% of students studying in HEIs across the UK as a whole. The report noted that the proportion of non-UK students enrolled in Scottish HEIs has remained relatively constant over the past five years, with non-UK students consistently making up 2-3% more of student enrolments in Scottish HEIs than across the UK as a whole.

The report further highlighted the economic benefits of international student recruitment but also noted the academic and social benefits that come with a multicultural and multinational HEI environment, including enriched learning experiences and the development of an international outlook among home students which can make “an important contribution to ensuring the connectivity of Scotland's economy and society to the global exchange of people, ideas and trade” (Scottish Government, 2018, non-paginated). Against a background of globalisation, Scotland, like Japan and Australia, is keen to produce ‘global graduates’ who will be able to thrive in a globalised world.

However, increasingly stricter immigration controls coupled with the implications of the UK withdrawal from the European Union (Brexit) have affected international student recruitment for Scottish HEIs. This may threaten to deprive institutions not only of valuable income but also of the academic and social benefits of inward student mobility (Scottish Government, 2018). To counter this view, the Scottish Government has been keen to maintain freedom of movement post-Brexit, and is in favour of a differentiated migration system that recognises the different needs across the UK (Scottish Government, 2018).

The uncertainty caused by Brexit and the rigid immigration policies currently in place have put international student recruitment in Scottish HE into sharp focus. However, it is important to note that international student recruitment is only one aspect of the internationalisation efforts in Scottish HE. International research collaborations are common with many of them well established for many years, while efforts to internationalise the curriculum are ongoing (Weedon and Kong, 2015). Therefore, it could be argued that the approach to internationalisation in Scottish HE has and continues to be comprehensive.

Educators' Experiences of Internationalisation

Although the previous section focused on broader issues related to the definitions, the perceived benefits of internationalisation in theory and government policies directed towards internationalisation a more granular or bottom up approach can also be taken. This section considers educators' experiences of internationalisation in HE, including barriers and challenges faced by educators as a result of internationalisation in their HEI context.

Drawing on a range of literature on internationalisation in HE, Bedenlier and Zawacki-Richter (2015) note that “it is widely agreed that academic faculty members are crucial contributors to a higher education institution’s successful internationalisation process” (Bedenlier and Zawacki-Richter, 2015, p.186). Similarly, Tange (2010) has pointed out that educators

“are at the interface between institutional demands and students’ expectations. More often than not, they have not been involved in the decision-making process leading the university managers to adopt a policy of internationalisation, and yet they are expected to transform the management strategy into a sustainable teaching practice [...]. Arguably, [educators] represent the group of university employees most deeply affected by internationalisation” (Tange, 2010, p. 141).

Therefore, despite the important role of educators in the implementation of their HEI’s internationalisation policy (Teekens, 2006; Childress, 2009; Tange, 2010; Yonezawa, 2017), the educator perspective on internationalisation is underrepresented in the literature on internationalisation (Friesen, 2012; Sanderson, 2008; Criswell and Zhu, 2015). Previous research on this topic is limited although what exists provides important insights into the experiences of these key players in the internationalisation process.

Arguably, internationalisation has had an immense impact on the working lives of educators and has led to the formation of new pedagogies and academic identities (Ninnes and Hellsten, 2005). Hellsten (2008) has stated that

“It is no longer feasible to refute an acknowledgement of [internationalisation’s] impact on the lives of students, lecturers and their intercultural practices in many host institutions around the Western world” (Hellsten, 2008, p.83).

Internationalisation is associated with educational changes and challenges. According to Hellsten (2008), “it is fair to say that [as a result of internationalisation] our teaching rooms no longer resemble sites from 10 years ago” (Hellsten, 2008, p.95). Writing from an Australian perspective, Hellsten (2008) spoke of “a sense of apprehension “on the floor” of teaching rooms, which are filled, in many Australian cases, with at least 50% international students” (Hellsten, 2008, p.85). This point was reiterated in Tange’s (2010) account of internationalisation in Danish higher education which notes that educators are likely to experience internationalisation as a challenge if “they are confronted with unfamiliar cultural beliefs and expectations when entering an auditorium filled by learners from across the world” (Tange, 2010, p.139).

The sense of overwhelming change, and challenges therein for educators, could be ameliorated by policy makers’ and/or university managers’ providing guidance, appropriate decisions on allocation of resources and inclusivity. Dewey and Duff’s (2009) case study of internationalisation in one department of an HEI in USA provides illuminating details about the factors that affect educators’ experiences of internationalisation. Dewey and Duff (2009) identified a number of barriers that hinder educators’ meaningful participation in the internationalisation project, including poor communication regarding international opportunities, logistical constraints associated with limited funding, and low levels of practical support. Dewey and Duff’s (2009) study concluded that the internationalisation policy of a

HEI cannot be implemented without the participation of the educators however educators alone do not “have the capacity and responsibility to take on full implementation of an institution wide priority area [such as internationalisation]” (Dewey and Duff, 2009, p.503).

Issues of academic agency and lines of communication are pertinent to the implementation of internationalisation. By agency we mean “the capacity of actors to critically shape their responses to problematic situation” (Biesta and Tedder, 2006, p.11). Friesen’s (2012) phenomenological study of educator engagement in a Canadian University also found that educators are key agents in the institutional process of internationalisation yet they can find it difficult to engage with the internationalisation process when there is ambiguity within their institution around what internationalisation means and how it can be developed. Friesen’s (2012) main aim was to explore the participating educators’ motivations, perceptions and experiences in relation to internationalisation within their HEI. The educators in Friesen’s study (2012) understood internationalisation to be linked to “institutional reputation and economic return” (Friesen, 2012, p.217) rather than to teaching and research. Friesen’s study (2012) highlighted that the role of the educator has changed in our globalized world and that such a change can generate uncertainty for the educators. Despite this, the participants in Friesen’s (2012) study strived to align their work with the strategies of their institution even when they received little guidance or clarity from those leading the internationalisation process within their HEI. Friesen (2012) concluded that HEIs would benefit from looking at how individual educators’ needs and values are affected by internationalisation. She also emphasised the need to engage educators in the development of shared vision and policy about internationalisation. This echoes Alashoo et al. (2005) who highlighted the

importance of ensuring that staff understand the internationalisation strategy they are expected to implement and that they have adequate connection to the internationalisation vision of their HEI.

Drawing on data from participants across Finland, Switzerland and Germany, Korhonen and Weil's (2015) study also focused on educators' experiences of their roles and practices in relation to internationalisation of HE. The study highlighted some of the challenges experienced by educators involved in the internationalisation process and some of the benefits associated with it. The participants in Korhonen and Weil's (2015) study spoke of how their roles and approaches have evolved in response to the changes in the teaching-learning environments brought about by internationalisation of HE such as a more diverse, multicultural student body. They highlighted the importance of incorporating international perspectives in their teaching, and the benefits of the increased knowledge flow and new insights that international students bring into classroom. The participants also shared concerns and uncertainty about the changes associated with internationalisation, specifically in relation to the adequacy of resources available to support their evolving practice.

Other researchers who have explored the role of educators in the internationalisation of HE include Stohl (2007), who found that the engagement of educators is instrumental to the development and sustainability of internationalisation in HE. Stohl (2007) concluded that

“to capture the [educators'] interest in, and commitment to, internationalization, we need to move beyond the conceptualization of the internationalization or globalization of HE in terms of how the different aspects of teaching, research, and service functions of the university are

becoming more “internationalized” and examine how these activities encourage greater learning and discovery” (Stohl, 2007, p.358).

Adeoye, Anyikwa and Avant (2012) explored educators’ perceptions and experiences of internationalisation in HE as part of a broader study also involving students. The research, based in Nigeria, used descriptive statistics to describe the perceptions of 446 participants 150 of whom were staff. Adeoye, Anyikwa and Avant (2012) found that participants’ understanding of the concept of internationalisation was low, however, the majority of participants acknowledged that internationalisation does promote collaboration within the HEI. The study urges policy makers to seek and acknowledge educators’ and students’ perceptions of internationalisation and highlighted the important part HEI leadership can play in the effective implementation of internationalisation policy.

Similar to the findings of Adeoye, Anyikwa and Avant (2012), Warwick and Moogan’s (2013) study of internationalisation across British HEIs found that educators’ idea of internationalisation is shaped by their own experiences. The study examined the reality of internationalisation as perceived by key stakeholders, including educators, and identified gaps between intended internationalisation as reflected in HEIs’ policies and enacted internationalisation as reflected in practice. Warwick and Moogan (2013) found that educators held different understandings of internationalisation, even within the same HEI, with some adopting a narrow conceptualisation linked to the recruitment of international students and others having a much broader view which included international links and internationalisation of the curriculum. Warwick and Moogan’s (2013) study also revealed that the support of senior HEI staff is key to effective internationalisation while poor communication of

the HEI's internationalisation vision will inevitably act as a barrier to the implementation of this vision. Warwick and Moogan (2013) found that internationalisation requires commitment from all staff and concluded that over-reliance on the enthusiasm of a few can be problematic.

Warwick and Moogan's (2013) finding that the commitment of only a few staff is not sufficient for effective internationalisation echoes earlier research noting that educator engagement in internationalisation is a challenge for many HE institutions (Green and Shoenberg, 2006; Childress, 2010). Leask (2001; 2009) has argued that there is a reluctance among some educators to embrace internationalisation, based on the belief that internationalisation is something that belongs to someone other than the educator. Warwick and Moogan's (2013) finding suggests that this continues to be an issue and indicates a need for more active involvement of educators in the development of their HEI's internationalisation vision and strategy.

A qualitative study of internationalisation in Danish HE from the perspective of the educator (Tange, 2010) found the increasing multiculturalism of classrooms through the presence of non-native students to be a challenge for the participating educators. According to Tange (2010) this is because the educators 'often become the main agents responsible for the socialisation of international students into a Danish learning tradition' (Tange, 2010, p.147).

Arguably, many of the challenges experienced by the educators in Tange's (2010) study are the result of limited institutional support. This is also highlighted by Hanson and McNeil's study (2012) which revealed that although the participating educators "demonstrated a personal commitment to the practice of internationalizing their respective curricula" (Hanson and McNeil 2012, p.34), they had concerns about the

lack of support in dealing with the complexities involved in trying to effectively internationalise whilst managing increasingly heavy academic workloads.

Such concerns about lack of institutional support highlight a disconnect between policy makers who develop internationalisation strategies and the educators who are tasked with implementing them (Turner and Robson, 2007; Lunn, 2008; Sanderson, 2008; Friesen, 2012). One reason for this is already suggested by Mestenhauser (1998), who stated that senior administrators who traditionally make operational decisions, often do not have the required interdisciplinary, intercultural, and pedagogical competencies required to understand what is involved at the implementation stage. This is reiterated by De Haan (2014) who noted that “once the [internationalisation] policy formulated by senior management is implemented at the faculty level, the strategy designed on paper often does not produce the intended results in practice” (De Haan, 2014, p. 136). De Haan (2014) concluded that a “deeper understanding from both perspectives [educators’ and administrators’] is necessary in order to identify the disconnection between institutional and faculty levels” (De Haan, 2014, p. 136).

Despite the recommendations to improve the educator experience of internationalisation with increased support, access to resources and involvement in vision creation, progress seems slow and there is room for improvement. According to Bedenlier and Zawacki-Richter (2015), one way to address this is through more systematic analysis of how internationalisation processes affect HE, specifically educators. Their research specifically focused on the impacts on academic faculty members in relation to the internationalisation of HE and concluded that

“Academic faculty members are affected by the internationalisation of HE at different levels, covering a range from immediate personal involvement in the institutional context to global developments with indirect impacts” (Bedenlier and Zawacki-Richter, 2015, p.197).

Stakeholders from within and out with the HEI have their own priorities and directions in terms of internationalisation, yet, even as a key stakeholder, there is limited knowledge about faculty member priorities (Criswell and Zhu, 2015). How educators experience and are affected by internationalisation is an area of research that is lacking. Faculty engagement in internationalisation remains a challenge for many higher education institutions (Green and Shoenberg, 2006; Childress, 2010). It has been suggested that in order to understand the perceived impacts on faculty members in the internationalisation of HE, more refined definitions and concepts are needed” (Bedenlier and Zawacki-Richter, 2015, p.197).

According to Bedenlier and Zawacki-Richter (2015), more research can provide useful insights that can help us better understand the needs of educators against the background of internationalisation. With its focus on educators’ experiences and perceptions, the present study is hoping to make a valuable contribution towards better understanding of this important dimension of the internationalisation process.

Gaps in the Literature- Research Questions

There seems little doubt that the global landscape for higher education internationalisation is changing dramatically (Altbach and de Wit, 2018). But these changes are not impacting all countries in a similar fashion. Teichler (2017) argues that internationalisation policies continue to differ substantially between countries.

Increased commitment to internationalisation among HEIs is to be somewhat expected considering the fact that internationalisation is a key element for HEIs around the world (Maringe, 2009). As part of the commitment to, and success of internationalisation in HEIs it has been stated that further “exploration into understanding how institutions and faculty members engage and influence each other through the international process” is essential (Friesen, 2012, p.224).

Further research is important because despite a large amount of information on business strategies and international competition, there is limited research and scholarly discussion around the issues and challenges that arise from HEI internationalisation (Jiang and Carpenter, 2013) and “there are few discussions in relation to risks and challenges of HEI internationalisation” (p.7), particularly from the perspective of educators within the HEI. Therefore, we should now investigate the practice of internationalisation and how it contributes to the betterment of higher education (Yonezawa, 2017).

Some of the risks and challenges arise because of the “complex reality of the internationalisation of HE” (Bedenlier and Zawacki-Richter, 2015, p.197). They include implementation gap, limited resources, lack of understanding and faculty (member) engagement (Green, 2012; Stohl, 2007). Specifically, De Haan’s (2014) research determined that an ‘implementation gap’ exists between internationalisation

strategic plans and the actual outcomes of such. De Haan (2014) posits that managing the internationalisation process and activities requires an increased amount of strategic planning and management.

Svensson and Wihlborg (2010) advise that there is a lack of understanding of internationalisation from a pedagogical perspective, as well as from a perspective of the participants involved (Svensson & Wihlborg, 2010). Meanwhile, (Marioni and de Wit, 2019) highlight the perception that internationalisation is limited by resources and that institutions are not sufficiently inclusive in their internationalisation strategy. This is despite the fact that, more recently, the 5th IAU Global Survey (2018) inclusive of responses from 907 higher education institutions (HEIs) in 126 countries found the majority of HEIs who participated reported internationalisation to be of a high level of importance. It could perhaps be a sign that in the future there may be a growing differentiation in the level of commitment to internationalisation among HEIs (Marioni and de Wit, 2019).

The gaps in the literature for this particular area of study has led to the creation of the following research questions based on the title:

Internationalisation of Higher Education: A comparative study of educators' experiences.

Research Question One: How do educators in Higher Education (HE) define and understand internationalisation?

Research Question Two: What are the educators' experiences of internationalisation in their Higher Education Institutions (HEIs)?

Research Question Three: What are the educators' views about the future of internationalisation in Higher Education (HE) and their recommendations for improvement?

CHAPTER THREE Research Design and Methods

Introduction

The purpose of this research is to understand internationalisation of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) from the educator's perspective. To develop this understanding, data from educators in HEIs in Australia, Japan and Scotland were collected.

This chapter aims to explain the methodology utilised in this research in order to answer the research questions. It begins with addressing philosophical considerations (ontology and epistemology), which is followed by a discussion of the research design (mixed method approach). The chapter then provides a description and justification of the methods used for data collection and outlines ethical considerations. Furthermore, the chapter explains how the data were analysed and concludes by outlining the measures that were taken to ensure reliability, validity and transferability.

Philosophical considerations

Paradigm

Research in education necessitates a structured way of doing and seeing. In other words, it requires a paradigm. A paradigm is a loose collection of logically related assumptions, concepts, or propositions that orient thinking and research (Bogdan and Knopp Biklen, 2007). A paradigm is linked to a theoretical orientation that comprises particular ways of looking at the world and assumptions about what is important. All research is guided by some theoretical orientation; this may be explicit or implicit (Bogdan and Knopp Biklen, 2007). As a researcher one must be aware of their theoretical orientation and use it to help collect and analyse data effectively. Similarly, one must utilise a paradigm that is appropriate to the research questions and ensure

that the research is systematic and informed by the principles of the chosen paradigm. The choice of paradigm guides the choice of methodology, which refers to the overall approach to research (Mackenzie and Knipe, 2006).

An overview of the research framework underpinning this study is displayed in Table 3.1. The framework will be discussed in greater detail throughout this chapter.

Table 3. 1 Research Framework of the Study

Ontology	Constructivism
Epistemology	Interpretivism
Theoretical Perspective	Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis
Methodology	Mixed Method
Method	Questionnaire and Semi-Structured Interviews

Ontological and Epistemological Assumptions

Researchers differ in their approach towards research based fundamentally upon their particular ontological and epistemological perspectives (Guba and Lincoln, 1994). The choice of different research approaches and methods is dependent upon the researcher’s ontological and epistemological assumptions. An outline of the ontological and epistemological assumptions that underpin this research is provided in this section to demonstrate how the methods selected are linked to the research objectives.

According to Guba and Lincoln (1994), ontology is concerned with the nature of reality and what is knowable. Epistemology on the other hand refers to how we can

come to understand what is knowable, especially with regard to methods, validity, scope, and the distinction between justified belief and opinion (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018).

Constructivism assumes that reality is constructed through interaction within social environments (Mertens, 1998) and is based on the theory that people are likely to have a different understanding and interpretation of reality (Benton and Craib, 2001). Furthermore, a constructivist approach assumes that there is no single or objective reality and that knowledge is created through experience and interactions in the social environment (Creswell and Poth, 2018). By adopting a constructivist ontology, the researcher can be free from making any claims about 'truth' and "focus on the specific contexts in which people live and work" (Creswell and Poth, 2018, p. 24).

Constructivism, defined by Crotty (1998) as the view 'that all knowledge and all meaningful reality is contingent upon human beings and their worlds, and developed and transmitted within their social context' (Crotty, 1998, p.42) is the ontological foundation for this current research as it foregrounds the belief that reality is socially constructed and meaning is created by actors through their interactions within social environment and systems (Maxwell, 2013). A constructivist perspective seeks to develop understandings about the research phenomenon through the perspective of those who have direct experience of it (Creswell, 2013). Findings are co-constructed between the researcher and the participants through interaction that seeks to articulate the meaning that the participants give to their experiences of the phenomenon being studied (Creswell, 2013). The perspective in this study has been co-constructed by the researcher and the participants, hence a constructivist ontological approach is suitable.

Interpretivist Perspective

An interpretivist theoretical perspective has been adopted in this study. The strength of this philosophical approach is that it allows the exploration of the thoughts and feelings of the research participants (Sekaran, 1984). Interpretivist research is underpinned by the assumption that reality is a subjective experience and that the only way to understand the meaning participants give to their experiences is by providing them with opportunities to share these experiences (Cohen et al., 2018).

This philosophical position is appropriate for this research which seeks to understand what meaning the participants give to their experiences and how they construct their reality. As Gruber et al. (2010) suggest, different stakeholders within HEIs perceive quality and satisfaction according to their own perspectives and personal needs. In the context of this research study, views about internationalisation varied between individuals, based upon their experience. An elaboration of interpretivist philosophy can help explain the link to this study.

Interpretivism, according to Shank (2002) is a “systematic empirical inquiry into meaning” (Shank, 2002, p.11), “an epistemological position that requires the social scientist to grasp the subjective meaning of social action” (Bryman, 2016, p.692) In addition, Cousin (2009) suggests that an interpretivist would argue that the human sciences must strive to understand people’s intentions within given contexts, not simply observe their outward behaviour. This is because interpretivism aims to obtain an understanding of a social phenomenon from the perspective of the participants through interaction that provides the participants with opportunities to explain their reality (Taylor, Bogdan and De Vault, 2015). This study sought to generate understandings and insights related to internationalisation in HE based on the

participants' accounts of their experiences and the meaning they assign to them, rather than to explain or predict their attitudes and actions with reference to an external, objective reality, which would be more aligned with a positivist approach (Creswell, 2013).

An interpretivist epistemological stance was decided upon because the researcher was part of the setting, rather than outside of it. By becoming part of the setting the researcher was fully aware of the subjectivity that was present. The aim of the researcher was to create some degree of closeness with participants as rapport building and respondent disclosure are seen to be interdependent (Shank, 2002).

Phenomenology

One approach which is central to this interpretative research framework is phenomenology (Taylor, Bogdan and DeVault, 2015). Phenomenology is “a philosophy that is concerned with the question of how individuals make sense of the world around them and how in particular the philosopher should bracket out preconceptions in his or her grasp of that world” (Bryman, 2016, p.26). A phenomenological approach was decided upon as it is reflective of qualitative approaches that depend upon a phenomenological point of view. Using the phenomenological framework this research sought to understand what internationalisation means to educators in HEIs. In particular, it sought to understand the meaning of the phenomenon being studied (internationalisation) to people in particular situations (educators in HEIs). Moreover, this approach is relevant to this research study because phenomenologists do not assume they know what things mean to the people they are studying (Douglas, 1976). Indeed, phenomenologists attempt to see things from that person's point of view (Bogdan and Taylor, 1975). As Smith et

al. (2009) has noted, “phenomenology is the study of structures of consciousness as experienced from the first-person point of view” (p.46), hence the voices of the participants is found through the use of Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) which is consistent with the epistemological position of this current research. It is discussed in detail in the IPA Section later in this chapter.

Having set out key philosophical matters related to methodology, this chapter will now outline the research design.

Research Strategy

Mixed Method Research

Research paradigms are widely acknowledged by the research community. Paradigms according to Morgan (2007) have become “a central concept in social science research methodology, but often with a meaning that is rather different from the way that term is used in the field of science studies” (Morgan, 2007, p.49). Morgan (2007) provides a summary of the four most common versions of the term ‘paradigm’ as illustrated below in Figure 3.1. Paradigm as worldviews, paradigm as shared beliefs amongst members of a speciality area, paradigm as model examples of research and paradigm as epistemological stances. For this research the ‘paradigm as epistemological stances’ will be used as it has defining characteristics including ontology, epistemology and methodology from the philosophy of knowledge. Paradigm as epistemological stances is also relevant to this research as it has a “major impact” (Morgan, 2007, p.51) in combining methods. Methods including and how they may be relevant to combining qualitative and quantitative research methods.

Figure 3. 1 Versions of Paradigms (adapted from Morgan, 2007)

	Epistemological Stances	Model Examples	Shared beliefs in a Research Field	Worldviews
Characteristics	Ontology, epistemology, and methodology from philosophy of knowledge	Requires specific exemplars	Shared beliefs regarding Question and answers in a research field	All-encompassing perspectives of the world.
Place in combining methods	Major impact	Little explicit use	Minor impact	Little explicit use

Questions of ontology and epistemology are connected to method and methodology. Usher et al. (1997) assert that every research method is “embedded in commitments to particular versions of the world (ontology) and ways of knowing that world (epistemology)” (p.4). Cousin (2009) suggests that methods are best understood as the tools and procedures we use for our inquiries, whereas, methodology is about the framework within which they sit. Procedural methods for this research included the selection of participants, setting, timing and location, and the systematic recording and analysis of the data.

The method refers to systematic modes, procedures or tools used for collection and analysis of data (Mackenzie and Knipe, 2006). In order to understand how educators experience and understand internationalisation within their own context, a mixed method research approach was applied. A combination, convergent design, of both qualitative and quantitative research methodologies (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011;

Greene, 2008; Webb et al., 1966) were employed for the purpose of acquiring an overview of the perceptions and understandings from educators in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in three countries.

For this research, the definition of mixed method from Johnson and Onwuegbuzie (2004) was applied as “the class of research where the researcher mixes or combines quantitative and qualitative research techniques, methods, approaches, concocts or language in to a single study” (Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004, p.17). A procedural diagram below (Figure 3.2) demonstrates the combination of both qualitative and quantitative data. For the purposes of this research “quan-QUAL” has been used.

Figure 3. 2 Qualitative and Quantitative Integration (Tashakkori, 2006)

The qualitative and quantitative data will be presented as two strands. A two strand presentation has been utilised due to the fact that in sequential mixed method designs, the research may occur in chronological order, with one strand emerging from another (Teddlie and Tashakkori, 2009). In order to address the research questions, it was deemed important that both strands were used, however, as explained in the next section, they were not given equal importance. The two sets of data were compiled and analysed individually. Yet the two sets of data were also used to complement one another, to reinforce findings (Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004) and to demonstrate the interrelationship that may occur.

Strands of Research Methods

This section sets out elements of the mixed method approach. These are both quantitative and qualitative methods.

Quantitative Strand

The quantitative design aspect of this research allowed for descriptions of educators' experiences and perceptions of internationalisation to be presented and shared, supporting the idea that an attempt is being made to show how and why this phenomenon operates. Quantitative design is not used here to predict or to forecast a phenomenon rather than to prove it is present. Previously, quantitative research has been used to study attitudes and explore meaning (Bryman 2016; Stewart et al., 1980), therefore the questionnaires utilised provide data that are precise and allow the participant to share their views with the researcher (Feilzer, 2010). Although other forms of research have been considered, the questionnaires were chosen as they allowed for the collection of data from a large sample and from three different countries. The quantitative data obtained in this research study provided an opportunity to specifically identify the participants ranked preferences and their strength of opinions and views.

Qualitative Strand

In regards to the qualitative design aspect of this research, it could be suggested that the research purpose is to explore and describe. Explore, in what may be perceived as an attempt to generate ideas about this phenomenon and describe the characteristics of the phenomenon from the perspective of the participants.

In qualitative research, Silverman (2013) states that there is a need to recognise theoretical underpinnings of methodologies which may be contested and the often contingent nature of the data chosen. In this respect, the following information aims to outline such underpinnings.

An interpretivist epistemological approach to research is the use of semi-structured, one to one interviews. This is because the method of semi-structured interview relies on the response from participants to help direct the research, therefore, making the study more focused over time (Saunders et al., 2015). Although other forms of research were considered, individual face to face interviews were chosen as a primary method of gathering raw data for further analysis. This method allowed for the collection of authentic statements from educators to understand their perceptions and experiences of internationalisation at their HEI.

The method of semi-structured interview was used because it provides qualitative researchers with the opportunity to engage in focused discussion with the participants about their experiences and perceptions of the phenomenon being studied. Such discussion can provide valuable insights into how people interpret their experiences and what meaning they attribute to them. Semi-structured interviews are particularly useful in uncovering the meaning of a phenomenon for the people involved (Merriam, 2009). The questions used throughout the semi-structured interview were intended to understanding the experiences of participants and called for a qualitative design.

Significantly more focus and time on qualitative research methods supported the research intention to investigate individual experiences and perceptions of educators within the Higher Education context. Furthermore, semi-structured interviews were thought to be the method most suitable for understanding the questionnaire data in

more detail. In this way, the quantitative data were used largely to supplement the qualitative data. This is in alignment with the interpretivist approach to this research.

Due to the sequential design of the research, questions asked throughout the semi-structured interview could be adapted to explore the findings from the questionnaire. A uniform interview schedule was utilised which reflected the research questions and the data collected from questionnaires, yet questions could also be personalised to each individual participant through use of prompts (see Appendix 6).

To summarise, the semi-structured interviews attempted to understand the experience of educators in greater detail. Therefore, semi-structured interviews were designed to follow on from the questionnaire research to explore the findings more fully.

Alignment of Research Questions and Research Design

The research presented here represents a mixed method application of both questionnaires and semi-structured interviews. The integration of these methods allows for a holistic picture as the use of complementary methods may lead to more valid results (Jick, 1979). Appendix 1 displays in detail the alignment of research questions, semi-structured interview schedule questions and questionnaire questions.

Abductive Approach: Background and Context

Deductive reasoning is associated with quantitative research compared to inductive reasoning which is associated with qualitative research. Several weaknesses of a deductive only approach include that it seeks to test certain propositions from an existing theory without understanding how individuals interpret their experience (Saunders et al., 2015). Furthermore, a deductive approach may not allow for alternative reasoning based on the context of an event (Dudovskiy, 2018). On the other hand, an inductive approach develops theory based on understanding the context and

meaning of social events (Saunders et al., 2015). However, a considered weakness of an inductive only approach is its limitation in terms of contribution to theory development (Dudovskiy, 2018; Smith et al., 2009; Thomas, 2006).

An alternative approach, is a combination of inductive and deductive approaches. An abductive approach can be understood as a process that values both deductive and inductive approaches as demonstrated in Figure 3.3.

Figure 3.3 A View of Abductive Reasoning (Adapted from Wheeldon and Ahlberg, 2012)

An abductive approach is used to explore a phenomenon or a surprising fact to develop or modify an existing theory through data collection and tested through additional data collection (Saunders et al., 2015). Abduction allows the researcher to describe and

understand the world from the participant's perspective (Bryman, 2016). As the abductive approach is the combination of inductive and deductive approaches, it can be used to support conclusions and help to explore a phenomenon (Saunders et al., 2015). Therefore, an abductive approach is appropriate for this research because there was no requirement for a hypothesis. In fact, an abductive approach supports the connection between data and theory based upon the voices of those who provided the data (Morgan 2007; Teddlie and Tashakkori 2009).

Abductive Approach: Justification and Application

For this research, an abductive approach was appropriate due to the mixed method approach used in order to understand the lived experience of educators in regards to internationalisation in their HEI context. The sequential mixed method design of this research required an abductive approach because mixed method research can be understood as an abductive process that values the expertise, experience, and intuition of researchers themselves (Wheeldon and Ahlberg, 2012).

Using mixed method allows a researcher to use both inductive and deductive reasoning. By combining a quantitative and qualitative approach, answers to the research questions in this study could be determined. In this mixed method study, the researcher used the findings from the quantitative component to inform a subsequent qualitative component. The initial analysis of data followed the same sequence of data collection therefore, quantitative data, questionnaire qualitative data and semi-structured qualitative data were analysed sequentially. However, after initial data analysis it was necessary for the researcher to go back and forth between data sets. This is part of the abductive reasoning process in which one moves back and forth between an inductive and a deductive reasoning process (Morgan, 2007).

Research Design Rationale

Advantages of the Research Design

By using both qualitative and quantitative data, a fuller understanding of educators' experiences and perceptions can be achieved and presented. Both methods are viewed as complementing one another rather than as "rival camps" (Jick, 1979, p.602). The phenomenon researched can be better understood with the triangulation of data which can be achieved in a mixed method approach. Triangulation of data has many aspects that are advantageous including that convergence is created when triangulation occurs (Denzin and Lincoln, 2018; Jick, 1979; Webb et al., 1966). Triangulation also provides opportunity to build on initial findings, supporting the aim of understanding the bigger picture (Denscombe, 2017).

Disadvantages of Research Design

It should be acknowledged that mixed method research has potential drawbacks. Firstly, it has been suggested that the researcher may find it difficult to integrate the two sets of data (Feilzer, 2010) and hence lack a full understanding of the phenomenon they are examining (Jick, 1979). Secondly, qualitative and quantitative findings are analysed separately (Feilzer, 2010; Bryman, 2016). Thirdly, mixed method may give heterogeneous results (Feilzer, 2010, p.13). Fourthly, judgment is required to apply the appropriate qualitative or quantitative method and in turn, analysis, to determine if results have converged or not and to assess if mixed method results are homogenous (Jick, 1979). Finally, in his contribution to the literature on research design, Howe (1988) suggests that qualitative and quantitative research paradigms should not be mixed.

Solutions and Rationale for Mixed Method Design

Despite the disadvantages of a mixed method approach to research, the research methods utilised were expected to complement one another and to provide a better understanding of the general viewpoint of educators via questionnaire and specifically, individual accounts via semi-structured interviews. Jick (1979) asserts that a range of perceptions can be reflected in a mixed method approach, some qualitatively described whilst others are quantitatively measured (Jick, 1979, p.606). A sequential mixed method research was used to try and capture the many different dimensions and to understand more fully the phenomenon being researched.

Mixed method research allows the researcher to use “quantitative methods to measure some aspects of the phenomenon in question and qualitative methods for others” (Feilzer, 2010, p.8). The use of a mixed method approach is a “third research paradigm in educational research” (Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004, p.14) allowing “the use of multiple approaches in answering research questions, rather than restricting or constraining researchers’ choices” (Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004, p.17). The strengths of an additional method can be used to overcome the weaknesses of another. Using a sequential mixed methods approach has been used successfully by others (Ivankova, Creswell and Stick, 2006; Neal, Hammer and Morgan, 2006).

A mixed method research approach was adopted acknowledging the idea that qualitative and quantitative designs both have some weaknesses that limit the research purposes and their appropriateness. Therefore, using this mixed method allows the researcher to take advantage of the strengths of both qualitative and quantitative approaches (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011; Greene, 2008) when attempting to understand an educator’s lived experience of internationalisation.

Research Methods Strengths and Weaknesses

To summarise, the design of this research was intended to be both quantitative and qualitative within an interpretative phenomenological framework. A mixed method approach provided an opportunity for triangulation of data collection. The use of a mixed methods approach strengthened the research findings and helped to reduce risks that can occur when limiting research to one method (Maxwell, 2013). Furthermore, both approaches have inherent strengths and weaknesses, however, according to Sieber (1973), the researcher can utilise the strengths of both techniques in order to understand better the social phenomenon being studied as referred to in the previous section. Indeed, as in typical educational research and this study, the research questions should drive the methods used (Miles and Huberman, 1994). This research utilised two qualitative methods in order to successfully answer the key research question and subsequent questions. As suggested by Hesse-Biber (2016) qualitative research is typically inductive therefore, guiding research questions are generally open-ended, allowing for a multiplicity of findings to emerge.

A variety of methodological approaches were used to understand the experience of the educator in regards to internationalisation of HEI in their own context. Each of the specific methods used has its advantages and drawbacks which will now be presented.

Questionnaire Strengths and Weaknesses

A variety of open and closed questions were necessary for this particular research method. Open ended questions were necessary in order to collect in depth, detailed responses and allow the participant to comment further on their responses if they deemed this necessary (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). Sections of the questionnaire presented as closed questions. Closed questions appeared as a ranking

scale (explained further in Questionnaire Design section later in this chapter) and established basic, yet crucial data that informed the interview (please see Appendix 2 for an example). Overall, this methodology was time and cost efficient, was found to be reliable, and data could be easily collated and measured (Bryman, 2016). Delivery of questionnaire was secure and confidential. The design and delivery of the questionnaire varied between respondents. The design of the questionnaire was based on using an online questionnaire for respondents in Australia and Scotland, compared to respondents in Japan who received them in the mail as a hard copy (please see Appendix 2 and 3 for an example). Both approaches had a number of attractive features including timely correspondence and the ability to translate correctly when needed. For example, questionnaires from Japan were hand written and were easier for the researcher to translate from Japanese into English. The data could also be extrapolated in a successful manner.

Semi-Structured Interviews Strengths and Weaknesses

The value of semi-structured interviews is founded on the belief that participants are individuals who actively construct their social worlds and can communicate insight, hence, data can be generated that gives insight into participants' views (Lewis and McNaughton Nicholls, 2013). Semi-structured interviews are relevant for this research as they allow for specific questions to be asked and flexibility can occur. With the opportunity to engage in guided conversation, validity is increased as the researcher focuses their attention on the participant's words, parking their own pre-existing ideas (Smith et al., 2009). This method of data collection is timely, and reliable (Given, 2008). Interviewing as an approach to qualitative research was chosen because there can be an emphasis on seeking rich, detailed answers. Also, interviewees can be interviewed on more than one occasion and the use of prompting may be used

(Bryman, 2016). Furthermore, there is an emphasis on flexibility which can enable the researcher to adjust the emphasis in the research as a result of issues emerging in interviews (Bryman, 2016).

Semi-structured interviews allow the researcher and participant to engage in dialogue where the questions can be modified throughout, depending on the participant's responses and issues raised. In order for the semi-structured interview to be successful, a set of questions may be determined and attached to the interview schedule.

Given (2008) suggests that by using semi-structured interviews the researcher has more control over the topics of the interview than in unstructured interviews because there is no fixed range of responses to each question. The semi-structured approach was chosen because the interviewee has a great deal of leeway in how to reply. When questions may not follow on exactly in the way outlined on the schedule, additional questions may be asked and this is most beneficial (Bryman, 2016).

Semi-structured interviews allow the participants to elaborate when and where necessary, and to feel comfortable in a safe, familiar environment (Given, 2008). In this research, a safe, familiar environment was created for educators in Australia and Scotland by conducting semi-structured interviews in the participant's office. In regards to Japan, semi-structured interviews via Skype occurred at a time which was convenient for the participants.

Finally, phenomenological studies primarily rely on interviews to collect data (Smith et al., 2009). Therefore, a semi-structured interview schedule was designed as a means of tapping into the participants' experiences of internationalisation in HE.

Pilot study

A pilot study was conducted to test the effectiveness and quality of the sequential mixed method design, including the data collection process and data analysis.

Pilot Questionnaires

Questionnaire design was evaluated by new first year PhD students (n=25) as part of the compulsory Higher Education Teaching and Learning course (October, 2016), and a group of current educators (n=10) participating in the Post Graduate Certificate in Higher Education Teaching and Learning course (October, 2016) both groups worked at the researcher's HEI. The questionnaire was delivered by hand to the groups of participants. Although response rates were high, it was recommended that an electronic version would be more efficient, as it would provide further anonymity for the participant and less pressure to be involved, as well as being more environmentally friendly. Feedback from this part of the pilot study was duly noted and addressed. An analysis of collected responses was undertaken and changes were applied. Specifically, feedback included updating the questionnaire design and delivery. A new version of the online questionnaire via Google Doc, with abridged questions was tested with supervisory team before final distribution.

Pilot Semi-Structured Interviews

From the ten educators who responded to the pilot questionnaire, three educators agreed to partake in a semi-structure interview. Due to extenuating circumstances only two educators were finally able to commit to taking part. The two semi-structured interviews took place in each educator's own office and were audio recorded. Afterwards the semi-structured interviews were transcribed and analysed.

These pilot interviews influenced the format of semi-structured interviews that were conducted as part of the main study. Firstly, some questions were reworded and clarified. Secondly, several prompts were updated. Finally, it was deemed it may be helpful to ensure a copy of the questionnaire results were available at hand in the interview as a helpful reminder to the educator of their questionnaire responses.

Participant Recruitment

The aim of this research was to try and capture the lived experiences of educators regarding internationalisation in their HEI context.

Inclusion Criteria of Participants

Study participants comprised of educators who were currently working within a HEI, directly involved in teaching and learning. For the purpose of this research, the term ‘educator’ was used to signify academic staff who teach at a higher educational institution.

Permission was sought and granted by Heads of Schools or Assistant Deans of Internationalisation within each HEI. Afterwards an email explaining the research and providing the link to the online questionnaire was sent to the educators from the researcher via the Head of School or Assistant Dean of Internationalisation (see Figure 3.4). Participants who had completed the online questionnaire were later approached via e-mail invitation which is explained further in the next section (See also Appendix 5).

Figure 3. 4 Participant Information- Questionnaire

Internationalisation of Higher Education from the perspective of the educator

Research Aim: To understand what educators say about Internationalisation of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs)?

Using the following 1-5 scale, please indicate, by filling the most correct response, the degree to which you agree with the statements listed below. Place additional comments in spaces provided.

Completion of this questionnaire will provide consent for your responses to be used as data. All responses will remain confidential. If you would prefer not to use your own email address, please enter anonymous@ac.uk/au/jp in the field below. You may be invited to participate in further research.

1. **Email address ***

2. **Which School do you belong to?**

Mark only one oval.

- Education
- Business and Enterprise
- Media, Culture and Society
- Science and Sport
- Engineering and Computing
- Health, Nursing and Midwifery
- Other: _____

3. **What is your role in your HEI?**

Mark only one oval.

- Educator
- Other: _____

It was the intention to recruit participants with a range of experience of internationalisation from each HEI. Recruiting of questionnaire participants occurred concurrently in each HEI. In each HEI, educators from the School of Education were invited first.

Participants: Questionnaire

Table 3. 2 Questionnaire Participant Recruitment

	Invited to participate in questionnaire	Actual number of questionnaire respondents	Questionnaire respondents: School/Faculty
Australia	Approximately 40	22	Education=22
Japan	Approximately 40	25	Education= 25
Scotland	Approximately 80	47	Education=14 Science and Sport=17 Health, Nursing and Midwifery=11 Business=3 Media, Culture and Society=1 Learning innovation=1

In Australia and Japan, the number of respondents was 22 and 25 respectively.

In Scotland, after several attempts to recruit participants from the School of Education, only 14 completed the questionnaire. In order to increase participant numbers, the questionnaire was distributed to other Schools within the HEI. Finally, 47 educators responded (For further explanation see Robustness Analysis of Quantitative Questionnaire in Chapter Four).

Figure 3. 5 Distribution of Questionnaire Respondents in the Scottish HEI

The questionnaire served two purposes in regards to preparing for the semi-structured interviews. The initial purpose was to act as a sieve for selecting a smaller group of respondents to act as participants in semi-structured interviews. Quantitative data from the questionnaire were used as a criterion for sampling of individuals to be interviewed. The questionnaires therefore provided data for generic purposive sampling of interviewees (Bryman, 2016) (discussed further below). The second purpose was to help support the content of the interview schedule, ensuring it was consistent and allowed for elaboration of comments provided in questionnaires.

Participants: Semi-Structured Interviews

Understanding the lived experience of an educator was the main aim of this research. A key aspect of Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) is to focus on convergence and divergence within a participant group's experience of a phenomenon which naturally requires comparisons at an individual level (Smith et al., 2009), in this case, the lived experience of internationalisation within an educator's current HEI context. An objective of this qualitative strand of research was to gain an insight into how and why educators may have varied understandings and experiences of internationalisation.

In order to achieve the aim of the research, interviewees comprised of educators who were currently working within Schools of Education in a HEI, directly involved in teaching and learning and who had been purposively selected. Purposive sampling was used to gather the research participants (Creswell, 2013). The following section discusses why purposive sampling was utilised.

Purposive sampling method was used for this research due to several reasons. Firstly, the sample size was small and participants were selected based on their knowledge,

ability and experience on a specific topic to obtain rich information on research questions and objectives (Saunders et al., 2015). Secondly, it was important to select participants who had varied knowledge, understanding and experience of being an educator in HEI.

In order to gain an insight into the views and experiences of educators in HEIs, a non-probability, purposive sampling approach was utilised to recruit participants for the qualitative strand of semi-structured interviews who met specific criteria and shared specific characteristics such as profession, faculty and experience in an HEI which aimed to be international (Leedy and Ormord, 2010). The educators recruited were experts in the phenomenon which was explored (Reid et al., 2005) in this case, educators within the School of Education. Generic purposive sampling (Bryman, 2016) allowed the interviewees to be selected purposively in term of criteria that were central to the main topic of the research – a comparative study of educators’ experiences of internationalisation.

The following selection criteria applied to those who were invited to take part in the semi-structured interviews.

An educator who:

- worked in a HEI and had no direct input to policy making or procedure relating to internationalisation. It was deemed important that in order to compare the experience of the educator, those who had roles involving direct decision making in terms of internationalisation i.e. policy makers were not appropriate.
- worked in The School of Education. The commonality of participants working in the School of Education was deemed appropriate as by working in the same School they may have had similar access to directives, curriculum, policy in

terms of internationalisation. Comparing the lived experiences of educators within the same working environment was deemed interesting and worthy of further investigation in order to arrive at commonalities or difference relating to the lived experience. Furthermore, the researcher was also a student within the School of Education.

- had completed the questionnaire and whose results from the questionnaire, compared to peers from the same HEI demonstrated a range of experience and understanding in terms of internationalisation. The intention was to try and gather a range of educator responses from each of the HEIs. By inviting participants from the same School (School of Education), who had very different opinions and experiences about internationalisation, it would hopefully provide an interesting cross section of lived experiences.

The aim was to identify cases from a standardised questionnaire that meet some predetermined criteria of importance and is used to inform in-depth follow – up (Patton, 2002). Responses to Question 1 were the criterion:

Question 1: Do you have a clear understanding of internationalisation within your HEI context?

The final 11 educators' responses to the questionnaires are demonstrated below. The results highlight a variety of responses to the questionnaire.

Table 3. 3 Interviewee Responses to Questionnaires

PAR.	Qu1	Qu2	Qu3	Qu4	Qu5	Qu6	Qu7	Qu8	Qu9	Qu10	Qu11
A1	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	4	4	4
A2	1	4	1	5	2	1	4	4	4	1	5
A3	5	4	4	4	4	2	3	1	3	4	5
A4	5	5	4	4	4	2	2	1	3	4	4
J1	3	2	4	5	3	4	2	1	5	3	5
J2	3	4	2	5	3	2	2	4	5	3	5
J3	4	5	4	4	3	3	1	2	3	4	5
S1	3	4	1	2	2	2	1	1	3	1	4
S2	5	3	4	1	3	4	1	1	1	3	1
S3	2	5	1	3	2	1	1	2	5	2	5
S4	5	2	1	5	3	3	2	1	3	3	5

An analysis of questionnaire data (Question 1 responses) resulted in categories of participants: those who thought they had a clear understanding of internationalisation in their HEI context, those who thought they had an unclear understanding, and those who remained neutral.

In each HEI few participants answered 5=Strongly Agree to Question 1. The eight participants included (Australia=2, Japan=2, Scotland=4). All eight were invited to participate in a semi-structured interview via email. Furthermore, in each HEI those who answered 1= Strongly Disagree (A=1, J=0, S=0) or 2= disagree (A=6, J=5, S=5) to Question 1 were limited, however they were invited to interview. In Scotland, 6 educators were invited via email before the final four agreed to participate. In

Australia, the first four invited agreed to participate. In Japan, the response rate was very low. 18 educators (2=SA, 8=A, 5=D) were invited to take part before the final 3 (3=N) agreed to participate.

Table 3. 4 Participants in the Selected HEIs

Position of participants	Number who responded to questionnaire with email address OR anonymously	Number who responded that they are aware that 'may be invited to participate' in further research	Number invited to interview	How many actually finally agreed to take part in final stages of the interview	Number of participants per HEI
Australian educator	Q:22 Anon: 5	Agreed to SSI:17/17	4	4	4
Japanese educator	Q:25 Anon: 0	Agreed to SSI: 25//25	18	3	3
Scottish educator	Q: 47 Anon: 12 School of Education: Q: 14 Anon: 1	Agreed to SSI: 35/35 Agreed to SSI: 13/13	6	4	4

The responses were not as expected or desired from the Japanese sample. However, the participants who participated were keen and eager to share their lived experiences of internationalisation in their HEI context. Although this experience was disappointing for the researcher, the experiences shared by the participants were valued and appreciated. Unfortunately, one of the Japanese participants had to withdraw which led to the final number of 11 participants.

The participants for semi-structured interviews were:

Table 3. 5 Country of Origin for Semi-Structured Interviews

Country	Interviewees
AUSTRALIA	4 WOMEN (A1, A2, A3, A4)
JAPAN	2 MEN, 1 WOMAN (J1, J2, J3)
SCOTLAND	2 MEN, 2 WOMEN (S1, S2, S3, S4)

Limitations of Purposive Sampling and Solutions

A disadvantage of purpose sampling is potential bias that may occur, particularly as participants are selected based upon certain characteristics (Mason, 2002). However, non-probability sampling can be useful when the researcher has limited resources, time and workforce. It can also be used when the research does not aim to generate results that will be used to create generalisations pertaining to the entire population (Bryman, 2016).

In order to overcome the limitations of potential bias the names and email addresses of the potential participants were not visible whilst selection criteria of response to Question 1 of the questionnaire was applied. In addition, the responses to the questionnaire had been populated into an excel spreadsheet based on the order of when the participant had completed the questionnaire.

Potential bias based on the fact that prospective participants are selected upon a selection criteria was addressed by the participant information being anonymised.

Data Collection

Data were collected over a period of ten months (Questionnaires: Feb-April 2017, Semi-Structured Interviews: Sept-Dec 2017). Initially data was collected from online and hard copy questionnaires, completed by a total of 94 educators (n=94). The participants were educators in Australia, Japan and Scotland who were currently working as educators in a HEI. After questionnaire analysis, participants were selected and invited to partake in a semi-structured interview which led to 3 or 4 educators taking part in semi-structured interviews in each country, overall 11 semi-structured interviews occurred (n=11).

Table 3. 6 Questionnaire Respondents

Country	Questionnaire Respondents (<i>n</i>)
Australia	22
Japan	25
Scotland	47
TOTAL	94

Questionnaire Procedure

Questionnaire Respondents

Despite 97 questionnaires being completed by respondents in HEIs, three respondents (n= 3) identified as policy makers or staff members who were involved in other roles as well as educators. Therefore, data from the three respondents could not be included

in the analysis. In order to ensure data was consistent with the research objectives, such educators were eliminated from the data before any analysis took place.

Questionnaire Design

Educators were asked to identify which School or Faculty they belonged to within their HEI, how long they had worked at their current HEI and to add an email address in order for them be contacted to perhaps take part in further research. Introductory questions at the start of the questionnaire included *'What is your current role? How long have you worked at your current HEI? What School do you belong to?'* (see Appendix 2). Such questions allowed for the collection of specific data that could be later used to support the identification of future interviewee participants.

The questionnaire collected responses to 11 closed questions and 3 open-ended questions (see Appendix 2). All questions directly linked to the research questions (see Appendix 1). Closed questions responses were designed using a Likert scale. The respondents answered question 1 to 11 on a scale of 1-5 (see Figure 3.6). The figures on the scale corresponded to levels of agreement with the statement, with one representing strongly disagree, two representing disagree, three representing neither agree nor disagree, four representing agree and five representing strongly agree (see Figure 3.6).

A Likert scale was used as the goal of a Likert scale is to “measure intensity of feelings about the area in question” (Bryman, 2016, p.154) as well as use phrasing that imply positive and negative views of the phenomenon of interest (Bryman, 2016). The respondents were asked to rate each of the questions using the scale, wherein, the lowest number, 1 equalled the most negative response, Strongly Disagree and 5, the

most positive response, Strongly Agree (Menter et al., 2011) as demonstrated below in Figure 3.6.

Questions 5 and 9 of the questionnaire allowed an opportunity for the participants to provide comments. The response rate to such questions was noticeably high. Comments were included regarding internationalisation in their HEI as well as substantive information, qualifying their answer to the Likert scale-type questions.

Figure 3. 6 Likert Scale and Key

Scale	1	2	3	4	5
Response	Strongly disagree (SD)	Disagree (D)	Neither agree or disagree (N)	Agree (A)	Strongly agree (SA)

Semi-Structured Interview Procedure

Interviewees

After questionnaire data analysis, several participants were invited from each HEI. One commonality amongst invited participants was their position within the School of Education within their HEI. Inviting educators in the same School/Faculty with a range of views towards internationalisation in their own HEI context was intentional and eleven educators were successfully interviewed.

Design of Semi-Structured Interview Questions and Schedule

Once the participant agreed, a copy of the questions was sent via email, before the semi-structured interview. Such a process enabled the interviewee to feel comfortable and in some sense prepared for the interview after months between initial questionnaire and the semi-structured interview.

Interviews were confirmed with educators via e-mail. Interviews were conducted over a period of 3 months. Before the participants agreed to participate in the interview, they were given a participant information sheet explaining the purpose of the interviews and how they would be conducted. This included a summary of the study as well as information detailing that the interview may last between 20-40 minutes and will be audio recorded. Participants were asked to decide where was most convenient for the interview to take place, either their office or a venue organised by the researcher.

One goal of this study was to explore how educators in Australia, Japan and Scotland perceive internationalisation in their own context. Perception, in this case was understood as the subjective process of acquiring, interpreting, and organizing sensory information (Lavrakas, 2008). In order to understand perceptions of the research participants, the questions asked via the questionnaire and semi-structured interview were designed to allow for responses to show how an educator makes sense of the phenomenon being studied, internationalization, in the environment in which they work.

In particular, perception questions allow the participant to provide information on how they perceive matters (Lavrakas, 2008). This was applied in the semi-structured interview questions which included '*how does their HEI compare to other HEIs?*' or

'in your opinion and experience, how effective is the internationalisation policy in your institution?' Utilising the chosen method of semi-structured interviews allowed the participant to share their perceptions and refer to relevant experiences to illustrate and explain them.

The interview schedule contained 10 open ended questions which were closely linked to the research questions and were informed by the questionnaire responses and literature. The questions helped to guide the educator through their experience in a logical progression in some sense.

The questions asked included:

'I would like to begin our conversation by asking you about your experiences of internationalisation in your HEI context'

After using this opening statement to ask the participants about their experience as an educator in regards to internationalisation, along with probes, they were then asked

'What would improve your experience of internationalisation in your HEI context?'

However, despite an interview schedule in place, the interview process was iterative and involved going back and forth between topics to discern the implications they had for one another (Crotty, 1998).

During each semi-structured interview, it was important to use the schedule in a flexible manner, allowing for the main questions to be asked in such a way to support the flow of conversation and allow the participant to speak freely, whilst the interviewer kept track of questioning (Smith et al., 2009). Eight of the eleven semi-structured interviews took place in the office of the educator or in a meeting room on campus. The three participants in Japan were interviewed online via teleconference

using Skype (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018; Denscombe, 2017). Throughout each interview notes were taken and the interview was recorded on two different devices. By taking notes the researcher could make comments regarding non-verbal clues such as change in intonation from emphasis of speech or a break in the response whilst an interviewee pondered on their responses. Furthermore, the researcher could refer to a list of prompts for the next question or seek clarification and also note when educators used their fingers to express something as “”.

As mentioned previously, an interview schedule with questions acts as a guide throughout the interview and supports the creation of a positive rapport between the interviewer and interviewee. Additionally, it is paramount that the interviewee feels comfortable and safe in sharing their responses. The interview schedule was available before the semi-structured interview took place and allowed the participant an opportunity to have a clear idea of what to expect in some sense (Smith, 2011). Semi-structured interviews allow for sensitivity to be demonstrated, yet, the interview can be controlled and remain in track.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics were used to analyse the data that were collected via the questionnaire. Thematic analysis was applied to the qualitative data from the open ended questions in the questionnaires. Elements of Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) were applied to the qualitative data from the semi-structured interviews. IPA, explained in a following section of this chapter, was applied to support the phenomenological approach used to collect, analyse and interpret these data.

Analysis of Questionnaire Quantitative Data

A questionnaire was chosen for this approach to data collection because the interpretivist epistemology which underpins this quantitative research suggests that through analysis of numerical data provided by participant responses, meaningful conclusions can be drawn and knowledge gained. Furthermore, “inclusion of questions about attitudes in social surveys suggests that quantitative researchers are interested in matters of meaning” (Bryman, 2016, p. 624).

The qualitative data was recorded and managed using an Excel spreadsheet and Google Drive application. A numerical data base was created to enter and display the questionnaire quantitative data. Answers to the open-ended questions were also entered into a database. The data from the open-ended questions were analysed separately using thematic analysis as explained in the next section.

Quantitative data analysis of the ordinal data was performed. The analysis of the quantitative data was straightforward and did not go beyond the creation of frequencies and percentages (Denscombe, 1998; Menter et al., 2011). Responses to each question were recorded, collated and compared. In this relatively small scale

research of 97 participants, steps included data preparation and descriptive statistics, commonly used when undertaking small scale research studies (Menter et al., 2011). However, in order to demonstrate consistency amongst each HEI and its questionnaire respondents, further analysis was undertaken to test reliability of responses (as noted in Chapter Four: *Robustness Analysis of Quantitative Questionnaire Results*).

Presentation of Data

In order to make sense of the quantitative data, tables and graphs were created (Denscombe, 1998). To illustrate the numerical data from each of the closed questions from the questionnaire a pie chart was created. Each pie chart displays the overall responses from all educators at each HEI. Three pie charts are provided for each question to provide convenient comparison. Each pie chart is divided into 5 sections (*Strongly Agree, Agree, Neither, Disagree, Strongly Disagree*) as demonstrated in Figure 3. 7 below. A summary of quantitative data was created and presented as percentages, on a pie chart, of each closed question. All respondents answered all closed questions therefore the percentages reported correspond to the total number of educators.

The intention is to provide insight into the respondents' experiences and perceptions by presenting the findings in a structured manner.

Figure 3. 7 Examples of Quantitative Data Representation

(Key: TITLE: *A= Australia, J=Japan, S= Scotland*

Data: *SA=Strongly agree, A=Agree, N=Neither, D= Disagree, SD=Strongly Disagree*)

Question 1 I have a clear understanding of internationalisation within my current HEI context	Question 2 I encounter internationalisation often in my current role	Question 3 I am satisfied with the investment my organization makes in training and education specifically for internationalisation

Analysis of Questionnaire Qualitative Data

There are significant challenges that can occur when conducting qualitative research. One of the main difficulties is that it can generate a large amount of data (Bryman, 2016). Miles (1979) has described qualitative data as an “attractive nuisance” (Miles, 1979, p.590), because of the attractiveness of the rich data it generates but the difficulty of finding analytic paths through that richness.

Thematic analysis

Thematic analysis was applied to the qualitative data from the open ended questions of the questionnaire (see Appendix 4). Thematic analysis, a method used to identify and interpret patterns of explicit and potential meanings in qualitative data (Clarke and Braun, 2006; 2017) was used to identify themes relating to the perceptions and experiences of internationalisation in the responses. Clarke and Braun (2006; 2017) advise that the researcher should start by identifying initial codes and reflecting on them to gain a sense of the continuities and lineage between them. Once coding has been completed, codes should be sorted into categories, and then categories should be merged into themes (Clarke and Braun, 2006; 2017). Codes were identified in the data by searching for repetition of key words and points first within and then across open ended responses (Ryan and Bernard, 2006). Consideration of the codes led to the identification of commonalities. Codes that shared commonalities were grouped to create categories. Next, relationships between categories were identified leading to the creation of themes (Clarke and Braun, 2006; 2017).

Coding process

Different levels and types of coding can be applied in qualitative data analysis (Bryman 2016). The use of coding was applied when reviewing the responses to the open-ended questions as it allowed for the data to be broken down into component parts. As Clarke and Braun (2017) suggests, this process allows for codes to emerge, codes which can be used to label, separate, compile and organise the qualitative data. Positive aspects of this approach include that it made the sifting through the data efficient and it ensured that the most common codes or those that revealed the most about the data were identified. The process of coding used was well suited to this study

as this process was a sufficient way in which to conceptualise this phenomenon (internationalisation), a starting point from which to measure and compare perspectives and attitudes of educators.

The categories and themes are presented below:

Table 3. 7 Thematic Analysis of Questionnaire Qualitative Data

Categories	Explanation of Category Codes	Theme (Internationalisation is a process aiming to:)
GLO CUL PEA	GLO: Global citizenship CUL: Culture/Cultural awareness PEA: Peaceful transitions and exchange	(promote) Intercultural Awareness and Global Citizenship
MOB EX IS	MOB: The movement of staff and students EX: Exchange students and programs IS: International students	(facilitate) Staff and Student Mobility
\$\$\$ PRO	\$\$\$: Money centred PRO: Profit making	(generate) Financial Gain
IOC ITL	IOC: Internationalisation of the curriculum ITL: International teaching and learning	(infuse the) Curriculum with International perspectives

Link between Thematic Analysis and IPA

Similar aspects of both Thematic Analysis (TA) and Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) were utilised for the analysis of the qualitative data collected in this study because they were underpinned by similar epistemologies.

Thematic analysis was used as it can be applied in different theoretical frameworks, including phenomenological studies to explore the experiences of participants (Creswell, 2013). An advantage of thematic analysis is that it is flexible and broad, therefore useful for analysing data from open ended questionnaire data (Braun and Clarke, 2017). Utilising thematic analysis for the questionnaire opened ended questions was also necessary in the final formulation of questions used for the semi-structured interviews.

In contrast to the broad approach of TA, IPA has a more idiographic focus which aims to explore and understand an individual's experience. Smith (2011) posits that deeper findings are a result of utilising a smaller sample in IPA, providing a more focused insight into a person's meaning of a phenomenon.

Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA)

Introduction

The aim of this study was to understand educators' experiences of internationalisation within their HEI context. The researcher utilised Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) as a way to interpret meaning from participants' experiences. IPA is concerned with exploring how individuals make sense of life experiences and how individuals derive meaning from their experiences (Larkin, Eatough, & Osborn, 2011; Smith et al., 2009). Therefore, IPA was well suited to provide detailed examinations of personal lived experiences of educators in this present study (Smith & Osborn, 2015).

According to Smith et al. (2009), participants in IPA studies should have experienced the phenomenon under study (Smith et al., 2009). Therefore, educators who worked in an HEI context, in School of Education, were invited to participate in this current research. Eleven educators participated in semi-structured interviews which is viewed as an ideal sample size because of IPA's concern with obtaining detailed accounts of each individual's experience (Smith et al., 2009).

IPA in Education

IPA was introduced in the 1990s (Smith, 1996; Eatough and Smith, 2017). At this time, Smith et al. (2009) sought an improved way to analyse psychological studies from the perspective of the subject (Tindall, 2009). Since then, IPA has grown rapidly beyond its association with psychology (Wagstaff et al., 2014) and more recently IPA has been used to interpret experiences of stakeholders within the field of education (Denovan and Macaskill, 2013; Thurston, 2014). Its use within educational settings

has been considered emergent (Holland, 2014).

With this in mind, IPA continues to develop and is being used to address a wide range of research questions in an expanding array of disciplines yet its “core commitment to the importance of sustained engagement with the individual’s attempts to make sense of their personal lived experience remains” (Eatough and Smith, 2017, p.206).

IPA researchers are interested in understanding human experience from the perspective of the individual (Eatough and Smith, 2017). More recently understanding human experience in an educational research setting using IPA has grown. Recent examples of how IPA has been successfully utilised in the field of education include research by Rakhshandehroo and Ivanova (2019), Guihen (2019), Forbes-Grant (2019), Edwards (2019), Thurston (2014), Holland (2014) and Denovan and Macaskill (2013).

IPA has been successfully utilised in research relating to Higher Education Institution (HEI) contexts. One specific example similar to this present study is the mixed method (Quan-QUAL) study of two leading Japanese HEIs in relation to student experience. A mixed method sequential explanatory design was chosen to examine the phenomenon at a deep level. An online questionnaire followed by semi-structured in-depth interviews provided data later analysed using IPA to interpret student satisfaction at English-medium graduate programs in Japan, specifically at graduate level and from a bottom up perspective (Rakhshandehroo and Ivanova, 2019).

IPA has been used in the field of education in a Secondary Education context. An example is the exploration of career experiences of women deputy headteachers, to make sense of their lived experience (Guihen, 2019). The study entailed a personal reflection as well as a case study of twelve current deputy headteachers who were

deciding to enter Head Teachership. This study was deemed original because although IPA has been used widely in many areas of social science, IPA had not commonly been used in this research area of educational leadership and management. A similar study utilised IPA to capture and analyse the experiences and perceptions of six middle school teachers of English Language Arts (ELA) (Forbes-Grant, 2019). The findings of this paper concluded that ELA teachers working in a district with strong departmental leadership, collaboration, and pedagogical values could persist in the difficult work of balanced literacy instruction. The findings also provided implications for teacher leadership.

A further area of research that adopted an IPA approach in education is that of Edwards (2019) who focused on employability within one HEI by examining the lived experiences of the key participants including senior leaders, middle managers and academics. Understanding the lived experience has also been previously explored by Thurston (2014) who used IPA to examine and understand the way in which two vision-impaired students with albinism experienced inclusion and support in high school in the UK. IPA was chosen as a method of analysis for this particular study as “it has a commitment to understand and to give an authentic representation to the lived experience of its participants” (p.111). A similar example of how IPA has been utilised in a HEI is the case study by Holland (2014) who explored the lived experience of the thirteen academics who taught in one English post-1992 university. The data collected from semi-structured interviews focused on work perceptions and relationships. The themes that arose from the data have been used to inform positive changes in staff development including academic support systems and mentoring practices. A final example of how IPA is suitable in educational research is a study by Denovan and

Macaskill (2013). Their study provides an example of how IPA was used to identify stress and coping strategies of first year undergraduates in a HEI. The study was based on semi-structured interviews and was analysed utilising IPA and five main themes were identified relating to the varied lived experiences of the participants. (p. 1002).

To sum up, IPA focuses on individual reactions to a phenomenon as reference points of analysis, rather than looking for meaning in large groups (Tindall, 2009). IPA is appealing to researchers in diverse fields, including education, due to its “explicit commitment to understanding phenomena of interest from a first person perspective” (Eatough and Smith, 2017, p.193). In particular, IPA is relevant, appealing and appropriate to the research field of education because “experience is subjective because what we experience is a phenomenal rather than a direct reality” (Eatough and Smith, 2017, p.196) also, IPA attends to all aspects of a person’s lived experience including their individual wishes, desires, motivations and how they manifest themselves or not in behaviour and action (Eatough and Smith, 2017).

Rationale for choosing Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA)

A rationale for utilising IPA in this study is that it encourages researchers to be flexible in the design and execution of a research study within the parameters of some clearly accessible guidelines (Eatough and Smith, 2017). A further advantage of applying IPA is that it produces in depth, thoughtful accounts of subjective experiences, incorporating verbatim participant quotes and relevant literature (Wagstaff et al., 2014).

IPA was applied to this research as its aim is to explore how participants are making sense of a phenomenon (internationalisation) within their social world (Smith and Osborn, 2007). IPA is concerned with “the quality and texture of individual

experience” (Willig, 2001, p.69) as well as being “interested in what happens when the everyday flow of lived experience takes on a particular significance for people” (Smith et al., 2009, p.1).

IPA is an in depth qualitative analysis and was applied to the semi-structured data collected in this study. This chosen analysis attempted to explore personal experiences as it aims to understand an individual’s personal perception of a phenomenon rather than trying to produce an objective statement of the phenomenon itself.

In this case, the event (phenomenon) is the internationalisation of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) and how the educator perceives it within their context. Indeed, Conrad (1987) and Smith and Osborn (2007) explain this method as a way in which to get a close look into an ‘insider’s perspective’. IPA is an apt approach and highly applicable to this research area as it tries to find out how individuals are perceiving situations that they are facing. By comparing individual experiences, IPA has a focus on convergence and divergence within a participant group’s experience of a phenomenon (Hefferon and Gil-Rodriguez, 2011).

Smith and Osborn (2007) argue that there is no single or definitive way to do IPA. This is because an advantage of IPA is that it encourages exploration and allows flexibility.

An important part of IPA is ensuring that connection and communication is continuous between the participant and researcher throughout the data collection process. By having sufficient communication, the researcher can more fully comprehend and understand whether their interpretation of the data gathered was appropriate and truly reflects the participants’ input (Smith et al., 2009). Such effective communication occurred after the completion of the questionnaire, when educators were selected for

interview and via email correspondence after the interviews were completed to ask further questions seeking clarification. IPA allows participant reflections on researcher interpretations, and time for critique, feedback and elaboration of the research findings (Smith et al., 2009).

Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis and Semi-Structured Data

Semi-structured interviews are highly recommended as the collection instrument for data when using IPA (Smith and Osborn, 2007). In order to gather good quality data for IPA, an open ended, semi-structured interview is suggested by Hefferon and Gil-Rodriguez (2011). This entails maintaining a careful balance between guiding and being led. Hence, the interview schedule for this study was short, with broad questions aiming to allow the participant to set the parameters of the topic and minimise the influence of the researcher (Smith et al., 2009).

Reflexivity and Researcher's Role

A researcher in social sciences should be reflective about the impact their values or experiences may have on the research process and the findings (Bryman, 2016). The IPA researcher is required to try and make sense of the participant trying to make sense of what is happening to them. This process is informed by hermeneutics, the theory of interpretation (Smith et al., 2009).

The main goal of the hermeneutic approach in this study was to explore and analyse the life world of individuals (Husserl, 1913; 1982). Therefore, data was analysed through an iterative hermeneutic process. Such a process included reading transcripts and listening to interviews many times to gain a sense of the overall viewpoint and perspective of each educator (Saldana, 2016; Smith et.al., 2009).

Furthermore, an interpretivist approach to this research allows the researcher to interpret elements of the study, therefore the use of interpretivism integrates human interest into a study. This is relevant to this particular research. Accordingly, “interpretive researchers assume that access to reality (given or socially constructed) is only through social constructions such as language, consciousness, shared meanings, and instruments” (Myers, 2008, p.38).

An advantage of phenomenological inquiry is that the researcher attempts to understand what they are studying by ‘bracketing’ (Husserl, 1913; 1982) themselves to understand their participants. Bracketing, is a method in which the researcher puts to one side “the taken-for-granted world in order to concentrate on our perception of that world” (Smith et al., 2009, p. 13). With this in mind, it is necessary to remember, the subjective aspects of people’s perceptions and behaviour. Hence, it is the responsibility of the researcher to attempt to gain entry into the conceptual world of their informants in order to understand how and what meaning they construct around their daily lives (Geertz, 1973). It should be noted that qualitative research, phenomenological in approach, tends to emphasise the subjective nature of any study and subjective thinking (Schutz, 1967). The researcher in this present study maintained a level of reflexivity throughout by acknowledging how their background, assumptions, positioning and behaviour impacted on the research process in a reflective journal (Finlay and Gough, 2003).

Limitations of IPA Research Method

Sample

This research did not set out to understand the viewpoints of *all educators*, however, an attempt was made to understand the viewpoint and perspectives of internationalisation of a small number of educators within their current HEI context. In order to do this, sample sizes were identified to give a balance between sufficient coverage and focus. Sample sizes were also determined by how many of the invited educators decided to participate in the study. It is recommended that five to six participants may be sufficient for IPA (Smith, 2011). For the purpose of this research, a sample was necessary from each HEI. The sample was determined at a later stage as referred to earlier in the chapter. It was important to consider and demonstrate an awareness of an appropriate amount of generated data and how it will be successfully analysed.

Furthermore, Reid et al. (2005) and Hefferon and Gil-Rodriguez (2011) suggest that less is more in IPA. Hence, fewer participants involved at a greater depth, according to Smith et al. (2009) is always preferable to a descriptive analysis of many individuals which is normally seen in thematic analysis or grounded theory. With this in mind, sample size is contextual and must be considered on a study-by-study basis (Smith et al., 2009). Case by case individual transcripts can be analysed leading towards a detailed understanding of educators within the Higher Education Institution (HEI).

Bias and misunderstanding

The focus for an IPA researcher is hermeneutic, idiographic and contextual, as they interpret the meaning for a particular person in a particular context. However, there are limits to the method of IPA as it can be very challenging for the researcher to

understand the participants' experiences completely. However, the researcher can try to make sense of the participants' world, and understand what it is like from their perspective.

The researcher must remain cautious of the underlying factors and perspectives that the participants themselves may not be aware of and in this regard, symbolic interactionism is acknowledged (Denzin and Lincoln, 2018). This refers to the way in which individuals construct meanings within both a social and personal world. With this in mind, the researcher had to interpret the participant's state from what they say. The participant's state can be either emotional and/or mental. In this context the educator may feel uncomfortable sharing or disclosing opinion about their workplace and this needed to be considered. Additionally, it was necessary to acknowledge that interpretation of data may be influenced by the researcher's viewpoint or experience and therefore it is important for the researcher to acknowledge and be aware of the potential for bias at all stages of research.

According Hefferon and Gil-Rodriguez (2011) there is a risk that analysis is not developed to a sufficient interpretative level, therefore, in order to ensure this did not occur, a smaller number of themes are represented, ensuring a more thorough and synthesised analysis can take place. Identification of common themes is necessary and afterwards, connecting the themes was attempted. Deciding to have a reasonable size of participants allowed for greater focus, more succinct questions in the interview schedule and a smaller number of superordinate and subordinate themes in the analysis, this in turn helped to achieve a successful IPA (Hefferon and Gil-Rodriguez, 2011) as explained in Figure 3.8 (Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis Process of Qualitative Data from Semi-Structured Interview).

Analysis of Semi-Structured Interview Data

Qualitative data from interviews are not straightforward to analyse (Bryman, 2016). Furthermore, there are no clear cut rules about how qualitative data should be analysed. According to Creswell (2012) “qualitative research is interpretative research” (p. 257). With these points in mind, in order to make sense of the findings, IPA was applied, as it provides the ability to explore in detail, the individual participant’s view of the world and hence capturing an “insider’s perspective” (Reid, Flowers and Larkin, 2005). Using this process helps to address the core of what the participants were thinking and experiencing (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009). IPA was utilised to interpret the lived experience of each educator.

IPA requires a “detailed, rigorous and systematic engagement with each participant’s interview transcript, employing inductive and iterative processes of reading, exploring, coding, reflecting, interrogating, integrating and eventually, thematising” (Flowers et al., 2006, p. 1380). As each transcript was analysed using the outlined steps, emergent and subordinate themes were identified and in turn superordinate themes were created by combining subordinate themes that were related. The analysis moved to a collective understanding rather than focusing on each individual educator, a more interpretative level (Smith et al., 2009). Themes identified were recurrent amongst most of the participants speaking about their experiences in a similar way. This ‘group level analysis’ (Smith et al., 2009) helps to summarise what the main themes are considered to be and provide evidence of such.

Using IPA revealed several superordinate themes. The superordinate themes were created based upon several subordinate themes which are presented in Figure 3.8, 3.9 and 3.10.

Figure 3. 8 Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis Process of Qualitative Data from Semi-Structured Interviews (Adapted from Smith et al., 2009)

<p>Step A: Transcription and listening</p>	<p>Verbatim transcription of each interview based on audio recording.</p> <p>Reading and re-reading of transcripts in an effort to immerse oneself in the data and for the researcher to imagine the participant's voice.</p>
<p>Step B: Initial noting</p>	<p>Noting points of interest, frequent statements and noting exploratory themes. Comment could include descriptive (content), linguistic (language) or conceptual (interpretation) (Example provided in Figure 3.9).</p> <p>A line-by-line analysis</p>
<p>Step C: Development of emergent themes</p>	<p>Use initial notes from previous step to identify themes including patterns (Example provided in Figure 3.9)</p> <p>Bracketing utilised between each transcript.</p>
<p>Step D: Combining of patterns and creation of subordinate and superordinate themes across cases AND countries</p>	<p>Searching for connections across emergent themes.</p> <p>Compare themes (within each data set Australia, Japan and Scotland) to create subordinate themes.</p> <p>Subsume themes to create superordinate themes applicable to every HEI context.</p> <p>Identify patterns between educators</p> <p>(See: Figure 3.10)</p>

Figure 3.9 Example of IPA Process

<p>that is still (unclear 36:02-08) the age he too has to be well. Extra work for the educator to ensure IS success.</p>																			
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<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th data-bbox="314 575 400 607">EMERGENT THEMES</th> <th data-bbox="400 575 724 607">ORIGINAL TRANSCRIPT CANDIDATE #</th> <th data-bbox="724 575 901 607">EXPLORATORY COMMENTS</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td data-bbox="314 607 400 902"></td> <td data-bbox="400 607 724 902"> <p>Interviewer: First of all thank you for accepting the invitation to participate in [unclear 00:34] interview as I try to explain my topic is about internationalization and the idea that perhaps it's a phenomenon or concept that might be ambiguous or unclear but I'm here today to try and understand Europe. I lived experience as an educator at the [unclear 00:54] university whatever you've worked for about... you understand this to be enjoyed experience so I'm just let you know that is completely confidential and I will provide you with the transcript complete and please feel free to use I/We statements. I just speak of your own experience. 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Figure 3.10 Overview of Themes: Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis

Ethical Considerations

So far this chapter has presented the philosophical underpinnings and mixed method framework for this research. The following section turns to ethical matters pertaining to the research.

Ethical research is paramount and therefore great care was taken to ensure that trust was developed and maintained between participant and researcher at all stages of research. Permission to conduct the research was sought from UWS Ethics Committee, School of Education and ethical approval was granted by the University of the West of Scotland. Afterwards, each participant was informed about the requirements via a participant information form and agreed to participate via a consent form. It was explained to participants that the researcher is independent of the HEI in which they were based. Furthermore, it was explained that the data collected be would remain confidential and would not affect the participant's current role within the HEI. All participants were adults and of no direct relationship with the researcher.

Procedures were put in place to ensure each participant felt comfortable when giving an account of their experience as an educator within their HEI. Throughout the process it was important for the researcher to ensure confidentiality and demonstrate ethical behaviour towards each participant. To ensure anonymity, participants of questionnaires are referred to as *Australian/Japanese/Scottish Questionnaire Respondent A1, J1 or S1* etc., whereas semi-structured interview participants are referred to as *Interviewee A1, J1, S1* and so on.

All interviewees were given an identifier according to their order of participation in the research, for example: A1 as first interviewee from Australia and A4 as final interviewee from Australia.

Positionality

Throughout this research, the researcher was in close contact with many HEI educators. Conveying positionality relative to the research was critical to ensure the transparency of the researcher's stance. In some sense, the researcher's beliefs and value systems are inseparable and impossible to avoid from the research process when conducting a research. Therefore, it is essential to remain ethical by stating one's positionality.

The researcher has lived and studied in all countries in which this research took place and had an understanding of cultural and societal norms and expectations. The researcher endeavoured to take steps to ensure sensitivity and an appealing environment for educators to participate in the research by travelling to the HEIs and communicating a time most convenient for the participants.

Furthermore, the researcher maintained a professional relationship with several of the HEI gatekeepers who approved the research to take place in their HEI or School/Faculty. They helped to ensure that the research was conducted in a culturally sensitive manner by approving the Consent Form and Participant Sheet (see Appendix 5) and altering/translating it where necessary. Consequently, it was not deemed necessary to seek ethical approval from other institutions.

Ensuring Rigour

Reliability and Validity

All research must be valid and reliable (Merriam and Tisdell, 2016). Using a sequential mixed method design is one way of ensuring trustworthiness of data (Creswell, 2015). Trustworthy findings occur when rigour is demonstrated (Merriam and Tisdell, 2016). In this research, trustworthiness is demonstrated in the way the data was collected, analysed and the way the findings are presented. In particular, steps were taken to ensure trustworthiness included aspects of credibility, dependability, confirmability and transferability (Lincoln and Guba, 1985; Bryman, 2016).

The credibility of research is measured by how believable the data is perceived to be. One way to ensure credibility in this study was to purposively include only educators from a Higher Education context.

Dependability is demonstrated by identifying how likely it is that the findings of this study may apply at other times. In the same sense, reliability is determined by the extent to which the results of a study are repeatable (Bryman, 2016). For a qualitative study, reliability is concerned with the degree to which the features of the study's design are congruent with the research inquiries (Bryman and Bell, 2003, p.33). Furthermore, reliability refers to the “consistency of a measure of a concept” (Bryman, 2016, p.157), suggesting that certain factors are in need of consideration when determining if a measure is reliable including stability and internal reliability. In terms of this research, reliability was illustrated by the use of a consistent mixed method in three different contexts (HEIs).

Validity is an important requirement for both quantitative and qualitative research (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). Validity in the quantitative research of this

study occurred in the careful and ethical way data was collected, analysed and presented. Validity in qualitative of this research was demonstrated throughout the process of data collection and data analysis and was accomplished in an ethical way. In both ‘strands’ of data collection and analysis, all procedures were followed according to those stated in the Ethical Application Form completed for University of the West of Scotland. The processes were followed directly and correctly, all data were collected and interpreted ethically in accordance with UWS Ethics Committee.

Consideration of internal validity (Merriam and Tisdell, 2016) questions how well the research findings capture reality. The use of IPA in this study is acknowledgement of the fact that it is an interpretation of data, an interpretation of reality, which is subjective in itself. Validity of qualitative data was ensured by criteria including, the commitment and rigour, sensitivity to context and transparency that the researcher applies to the research, which can all have a degree of flexibility (Smith et al., 2009; Yardley 2017). Measures taken to ensure commitment and rigour in this research include in-depth engagement during the data collection and data analysis. To ensure sensitivity to context and confirmability, the researcher carefully considered meanings generated by the participants and followed tools for bracketing. Transparency was demonstrated in the way that the data was interpreted throughout this research process. One example of validity in this research process was the transcription process.

Transcription

Each interview was audio-recorded and permission for this was given by all participants. Recording on two devices allowed for the interview to run smoothly. Recorded data is an important way to ensure a true reflection of what is said at the

time of interview. Transcription of each semi-structured interview was 5-8 hours per hour of interview (Smith et al., 2009).

Chapter Summary

This chapter provided the reasoning behind the philosophical and methodological approaches undertaken in this current study. The research framework undertaken included an ontological stance which was constructivist. An interpretivist epistemology and interpretivist theoretical framework was utilised and focused on a phenomenological perspective as it was the intention to present the lived experience of the participants through a particular lens. Interpretivism was identified as an epistemological stance for this research as the research objective was to understand the 'lived experience' of an educator in their HEI context in regards to internationalisation. Interpretivism was also closely aligned with the main method of data analysis, IPA.

This chapter also presented the sequential mixed method research design and methods relating to the conduct of this research from an interpretivist paradigm. The study utilised a sequential mixed method approach. Mixed methods were used, since quantitative and qualitative approaches were perceived to be complimentary. Methods included questionnaires and semi-structured interviews. An explanation of how rich data was collected using methods including questionnaires and semi-structured interviews was presented as well as the approach undertaken to analyse data. IPA and thematic analysis was explained as a way to interpret the data, and triangulation of data was highlighted as a way in which to provide rigour in this study. An outline of how ethical research was practised and undertaken in conjunction with ethical standards and limitations was presented including an explanation of the process of

recruitment of participants. Positionality and reflexivity of the researcher was clarified and finally, limitations were addressed.

The following chapter presents the findings from data and analysis. The findings are presented in a way that is complementary to the data analysis described in this chapter.

CHAPTER FOUR Research Findings

Introduction

This chapter aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of the participating educators' perceptions and experiences of internationalisation as a group and as individuals. For the purposes of the study, data was collected from aligned questionnaires and semi-structured interviews from educators in Australia, Japan and Scotland. By analysing the data this study aims to identify the commonalities and differences in perceptions and lived experiences between educators in the same institution and across three institutions in three countries.

The chapter begins with an explanation of the questionnaire data presented as a section entitled the Robustness Analysis of Quantitative Questionnaire Results and is followed by a section explaining the identification of codes and themes.

Whilst important questions have been addressed around internationalisation through the questionnaires, further research in the form of semi-structured interviews was necessary to develop a deeper understanding of an educator's perspective and lived experience of internationalisation in their current Higher Education Institution (HEI) context. The second stage of research was to establish the lived experience of internationalisation as an educator in an HEI, in more detail and from a smaller sample, specifically educators within the HEI's School of Education. The use of verbatim responses from the eleven educators are evident throughout this Chapter.

As explained in Chapter Three (Research Method and Design), the qualitative data from the semi-structured interviews were analysed using Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA). This particular framework provided a guide that is flexible and can be adapted to the researcher's data and research question (Smith, 2004). Throughout the chapter, findings will be presented including direct links to the

research questions, identifying commonalities and differences along the way between educators in each of the HEIs. By using this approach, comparison between HEIs and educators can be clearly identified and answer the following research questions:

Research Question One: How do educators in Higher Education (HE) define and understand internationalisation?

Research Question Two: What are the experiences of educators' in their Higher Education Institutions (HEIs)?

Research Question Three: What are the educators' views about the future of internationalisation in Higher Education (HE) and their recommendations for improvement?

Robustness Analysis of Quantitative Questionnaire Results

As noted earlier, invitations to participate in a questionnaire were sent to participants in HEIs in Scotland, Australia and Japan. Some key principles were adhered to when conducting the questionnaire. The researcher wanted a reasonable sample of data for each country, of at least around 20 participants. This presented a difficulty compared to a one country questionnaire, the researcher automatically required 60 participants in total across three countries. It was also intended to focus on the response of Education Department/Faculty members. Finally, the researcher assumed that more information is better, with the caveat that it is increasingly resource expensive to conduct a very large questionnaire, and have three countries, with different levels of questionnaire fatigue and different languages, with sometimes only marginal improvements in reflecting the true population.

Despite adhering to these principles some questions arose around the consistency of the samples and challenges were experienced in ensuring sufficient participation. The first problem was ensuring enough participants from each country. Responses from the Scottish HEI was not as expected at first, with only 14 participants in the Faculty of Education in total. It was decided that 14 responses may not provide sufficient variability in the data. Hence, the decision was made to broaden the sample to include other potential faculty members. Subsequently 47 responses were received. The question arose, was the responses approximately similar between the larger Scottish sample and the smaller School of Education sample? Also, if the researcher were to restrict the sample of responses to 25, using a randomly selected subsample, would the Scottish responses be different? To do this, the researcher used the Excel function “randbetween” to identify 25 random sample participants from the larger sample.

The responses are approximately the same across the three sizes samples. Full with 47 participants, Random 25 with 25 participants and School of Education with 14

participants. For example, for Q1 the average responses were between 3.67 and 3.93. This compares to Q3 where the average responses were between 2.07 and 2.60. Overall differences in average responses compared to the full sample are always less than 1.0, and indeed never more than 0.52. There is also similar levels of variability in the data.

For this study, particularly in order to present the findings in an efficient and effective way, it was decided upon to focus on the larger sample for the core analysis, since more information was perceived to be more useful. There is a clear and consistent signal from each of the three samples, and any differences can be accounted for by normal random statistical sampling.

Table 4. 1 Robustness Exercise: Scottish Higher Education Institution Data

Statistic	Sample	Questionnaire Questions				
		Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5
	<i>Full Sample</i>	3.74	3.51	2.60	3.74	2.62
Average	<i>Education</i>	3.93	3.93	2.07	4.07	2.36
	<i>Random 25</i>	3.67	3.42	2.29	3.88	2.67
	<i>Full</i>	1.05	1.21	1.15	1.22	1.01
St Dev	<i>Education</i>	1.00	1.07	1.07	1.00	1.01
	<i>Random 25</i>	1.17	1.28	1.08	1.03	1.05
	<i>Full</i>	4	4	3	5	3
Mode	<i>Education</i>	4	4	1	5	2
	<i>Random 25</i>	4	3	2	4	2
Difference to Full						
Average	<i>Education</i>	-0.18	-0.42	0.52	-0.33	0.26
	<i>Random 25</i>	0.08	0.09	0.30	-0.13	-0.05
	<i>Full</i>					
St Dev	<i>Education</i>	0.06	0.14	0.08	0.23	0.00
	<i>Random 25</i>	-0.11	-0.07	0.07	0.19	-0.04
	<i>Full</i>					
Mode	<i>Education</i>	0	0	2	0	1
	<i>Random 25</i>	0	1	1	1	1

Notes: Questions are 1 to 5. *Full Sample* is Scotland HEI with 47 participants. *Education* is 14 participants from School of Education. *Random 25* is 25 Scottish HEI questionnaire respondents who were identified randomly, using Excel Function “Randbetween”. The responses are approximately the same across the three samples. Differences in average responses are less than 1.0 on average and indeed never more than 0.52. There is also similar levels of variability in the data.

Identification of Codes and Themes

Interpretative Phenomenology Analysis (IPA) was used to understand the qualitative data collected from the semi-structured interviews in this study. IPA was applied to the data to understand the perceptions, and experiences of eleven Higher Education (HE) educators in Australia, Japan and Scotland. The themes presented in this chapter have been determined by utilising (IPA). An aim of this section is to provide a phenomenological and interpretive presentation of the research findings as well as determine superordinate and subordinate themes from the semi-structured interviews conducted. In order to do so, a sample of verbatim quotes are presented proportionally across participants so that individual voices can be heard and individual experiences can be illuminated. Extracts from at least half the participants who related to each subordinate theme will be included to support the claims made (Smith, 2011). Throughout the presentation of findings, the aim is to explore them both in depth and breadth, whilst also highlighting both shared and distinct experiences. The latter should therefore capture convergence and divergence between experiences.

Following the process of analysis explained in Chapter Three initial emergent, condensed emergent, subordinate and superordinate themes were identified. The themes are demonstrated in Figure 4.1 and Table 4.2. Figure 4.1 provides a visual representation of themes derived from the data of each HEI and also how the themes from each HEI were condensed together to create overarching subordinate themes. Table 4.2 presents the links between the subordinate themes, superordinate themes and research questions.

Figure 4.1 IPA: HEI Unique and Common Themes

Table 4. 2 Subordinate into Superordinate Themes

Final Subordinate themes	Superordinate theme	Link to Research Question
<i>Internationalisation as a process:</i> Financial Gain Students and Staff Mobility Intercultural awareness Global citizenship Infuse the Curriculum with International Perspectives	Definition (evolving and indefinite)	Research Question One: How do educators in Higher Education (HE) define and understand internationalisation?
Personal Encounters Professional Development Challenges and Barriers Disconnect Contribution to policy	Challenges and Barriers (of experiences)	Research Question Two: What are the experiences of educators' in their Higher Education Institutions (HEIs)?
Student Experience Values and Vision Systems and Resources	Future Prospects	Research Question Three: What are the educators' views about the future of internationalisation in Higher Education (HE) and their recommendations for improvement?

Further Detailed Interview Evidence

This section aims to provide further evidence of the utilisation of IPA in this present study and identify its benefits.

A key aspect of IPA is its focus on the subjective lived experience of the participants included in the study. Specific question design and interview schedule aligned with IPA allows the interviewer to ask a few general questions, in turn allowing the participant to share their experiences in an open way, with room to express themselves in whatever format they feel most comfortable. By doing so, the researcher does not impose their understanding of the phenomenon on the participant's narrative (Smith et al., 2009).

IPA is an interpretative method and is double hermeneutic which involves a dual interpretation process. This suggested that the researcher attempts to make sense of the other's personal world through the process of interpretative activity. The researcher did this by acknowledging that, "the participants are trying to make sense of their world; the researcher is trying to make sense of the participants trying to make sense of their world" (Smith and Osborn, 2007, p.53).

In terms of this present study, the participants shared their understanding and experiences of internationalisation to different extents. Some participants shared more than others which is to be expected when adopting an interpretative stance in semi-structured interviews. The following section provides a summary of the insights of each participant's interview. In this section the researcher strives to see the world as they see it (Larkin et al., 2006) and aims to capture what is important to the educator in this context and the topic at hand. Furthermore, offering an account of what it means for the participant to have such concerns within their current context is unique to IPA.

Insights into interviewee participants lived experience of internationalisation

A1: Canadian Female. Senior Lecturer.

A1 has worked in this HEI for 8 years. Originally from Canada, she considers herself to be an international educator. She was invited to participate due to questionnaire responses stating she had an unclear understanding of internationalisation in HEI in her own context, limited encounters of internationalisation in her current role, was dissatisfied with the HEI's investment in her professional development in this area and did not believe it was essential for her to follow policy and procedure in regards to internationalisation in her HEI context. Such points were elaborated upon throughout the semi-structured interview. Participant A1 expressed a preference that she would appreciate the opportunity to have future involvement in internationalisation process at her HEI and agrees that her HEI is successfully internationalised compared to other HEIs.

Examples of contribution and experiences of internationalisation mentioned in semi-structured interview include: Research collaboration with colleagues internationally and supporting exchange students.

A2: Australian Female. Professor.

A2 has worked at this HEI for 7 years. She has worked in a couple of HEIs around the world including UK and Europe and prides herself as being an international educator. Although she strongly disagreed to having a clear understanding of internationalisation within her current HEI context, she acknowledged that she encounters it in her current role and is expected to follow policy and procedure. She experiences dissatisfaction with the HEI's investment for training and does not feel supported in this area. The interview responses from participant A2 indicated that

compared to other HEIs she has working in the past, she strongly disagreed that her HEI is successfully internationalised.

Examples of contribution and experiences of internationalisation mentioned in semi-structured interview include: Previously member of internationalisation committee within this HEI and previous workplace.

A3: Australian Female. Senior Lecturer.

A3 has worked at this HEI for 10 years. Her questionnaire responses identified her to have a clear understanding of internationalisation at her present HEI. Participant A3 was very positive in her experiences of internationalisation in this HEI and experienced full support in her professional development regarding internationalisation. She expressed this through her examples of successful programs and curriculum she has led and implemented. Her experiences of internationalisation included facilitating and supporting learning exchange programs for her students to work and study abroad.

Examples of contribution and experiences of internationalisation mentioned in semi-structured interview include: Coordinator of Immersion Program for HEI. Previous member of internationalisation committee within this HEI.

A4: Australian Female. Senior Lecturer.

A4 has worked in this HEI for 35 years and now teaches in the School of Business but spent most of her career in School of Education. A4 was invited to participate as she was identified through the questionnaire as having a very clear understanding of internationalisation in HEI in her own context. She stated in the semi-structured interview that she encounters internationalisation in her current role regularly and that she is satisfied with the HEI's investment in professional development and resources

in regards to internationalisation. However, she also noted that she was not involved in the creation and review of relevant policy and procedure. Despite this she agreed that her current HEI, compared to other HEIs (from her experience) is successfully internationalised.

Examples of contribution and experiences of internationalisation mentioned in semi structured interview include: Internationalisation Committee member, Supervising International post graduate students.

J1: Canadian Female. Associate Professor.

J1 has worked in this Japanese HEI for 1-3 years. A reason why J1 was invited to participate was because her response to the open-ended question defined internationalisation as “a peaceful mixing of people from different cultures ... to improve society”. This was particularly interesting because her interview responses alluded to the fact that her lived experience of internationalisation in her HEI context was rather different to the other Japanese participants. J1 shared that as she is referred to ‘gaijin’ a somewhat derogatory term used for foreigners in Japan. However, despite this matter she was keen and eager to contribute to internationalisation within her HEI context.

“I am foreign staff but I am also new, so maybe in a few years I can help”.

Examples of contribution and experiences of internationalisation mentioned in semi-structured interview include: Language lunches including supporting English language skills. Attending and presenting at National and International Conferences.

J2: Japanese Male. Professor.

J2 has worked in this HEI for 1-3 years. Participant J2 is a passionate educator who has been an educator for over 30 years in HE. During the interview J2 was reserved and at times hesitant to share in great detail his experiences of internationalisation. However, when asked to elaborate on his definition of internationalisation which was “to get closer to a global standard” he compared how Japanese HEIs are in competition with others on a world wide scale and this is an important issue to be aware of for himself and fellow educator peers.

Examples of contribution and experiences of internationalisation mentioned in semi-structured interview include: Exchange students and programmes.

J3: Japanese Male. Professor.

J3 has worked in this HEI for 1-3 years. J3 was invited to participate was invited to participate as he was identified through the questionnaire as having a clear understanding of internationalisation in HEI in his own context. J3 was quite limited in his eagerness to share information regarding his role or experience relating to internationalisation. He did however state that he has “taught in many universities but this is the worst” (in terms of internationalisation).

Examples of contribution and experiences of internationalisation mentioned in semi-structured interview include: Exchange students and programmes.

S1: Scottish Male. Senior Lecturer.

S1 has worked in this HEI for 3-5 years. A reason why S1 was invited to participate was due to his extensive response to the open ended question defining internationalisation including the “need to account for differences in communication between different people from different cultural contexts and help to support them” (see Appendix 7 for complete quote).

S1 presents various challenges that they face in their role, particularly because of internationalisation. S1 is open about his experience in Scottish education, suggesting that policy relating to internationalisation is “still colloquial” which is a problem. He recommends government change and a review of the philosophy of internationalisation with in the HEI itself, most importantly, improving cultural differences.

S1 has very strong opinions regarding internationalisation in his HEI context. All examples provided by S1 include work experience in Scotland. This participant is a reflective practitioner who mentioned he likes to advocate and speak on behalf of others. He suggests that internationalisation is ‘purely conceptual’ and can be viewed on three different levels; international students, international curriculum and research. He believes there is an unambiguous steer towards internationalisation and frustrations faced by him in his role occur when supporting international students. A challenge that is evident is the lack of support received by the educator in their endeavours to ensure the international student receives the best experience. S1 states that in his experience there is a disconnect between the policy and the implementation of internationalisation. Such disconnect is linked to bureaucracy and lack of ‘identifiable benefits’.

Examples of contribution and experiences of internationalisation mentioned in semi-structured interview include: Attending and facilitating international conferences. Working with and supporting international students and staff.

S2: Scottish Male. Lecturer.

S2 was invited to participate as he shared via the questionnaire that he has a very clear understanding of internationalisation in his HEI. S2 has worked in this HEI for two years. From interview, it became apparent that S2 had attended professional development due to self-interest and eagerness to learn, not as part of mandatory training. Despite having attempted to internationalise the curriculum, this has proved difficult in his particular field of teaching and research. S2 voluntarily attended the internationalisation course at his HEI and highlighted that the course should be mandatory for everyone.

According to S2, teaching Mathematics does not really lend itself to internationalisation of the curriculum. The current HEI student population is described by him as homogenous. More could be done to improve Internationalisation at Home student experience and also to improve staff awareness of internationalisation, particularly from current leaders in the area of internationalisation within the HEI. He has worked in other Scottish HEIs and suggested that the other HEIs were somewhat more internationalised. All examples provided by S2 included work experience in HEIs in Scotland.

Examples of contribution and experiences of internationalisation mentioned in semi-structured interview include: Internationalisation Course. Collaboration with colleagues.

S3: Scottish Female. Senior Lecturer.

S3 has worked in this HEI 3-5 years. She was invited to participate as she disagreed that she had a clear understanding of internationalisation in Higher Education in the questionnaire, a point she elaborated on throughout the semi-structured interview.

She has worked in several Secondary Education, Further Education and Higher Education Institutions in Scotland and believes “based on my experience of other institutions and in other context” she “perhaps has a different view of internationalisation and perhaps a different view of what I think internationalisation should be or could be”. S3 shares that she has worked on EU projects as an example of internationalisation.

Overall, S3 has a very positive attitude towards internationalisation at their HEI, however most of the semi-structured interview focuses on their knowledge and current experience of international students. Interestingly, throughout the interview she demonstrates a concern for the well-being of the international students and hopes that students do not feel the pressure due to being a commodity per se. Global and international citizenship is highlighted and explored as important in the role of this educator, including the benefits that internationalisation (international students in particular) can have for home students.

S3 uses language in the semi-structured interview that demonstrates a sense of pastoral care for international and home students by repeating words such as ‘humane’, ‘ethical’, ‘to have integrity’, ‘relationships’ and ‘encouragement’. S3 believes more needs to be done to improve global citizenship of international students and home students well as internationalisation of the curriculum.

It is agreed that internationalisation is hard to measure and monitor, apart from a monetary perspective. There is some mention of curriculum but uncertainty how internationalisation is measured and monitored in her role or that of her peers.

Examples of contribution and experiences of internationalisation mentioned in semi-structured interview include: Travelling to Asia to test and recruit international

students. Organising and facilitating student abroad initiatives. International examples within curriculum.

S4: Scottish Female. Senior Lecturer.

S4 has worked in this HEI for over 10 years. All examples provided by S4 include work experience in Scotland. S4 was invited to participate as she strongly agreed that she had a clear understanding of internationalisation in Higher Education in the questionnaire.

During the semi-structured interview S4 provides some insight that internationalisation can be positive. Participant S4 also provides situations in which the educator is faced with challenges due to internationalisation for example supporting international students and questioning “what actually is internationalisation of the curriculum?” and uses words repeatedly including: ‘cynical’, ‘raised expectations’, ‘can’t do everything’, ‘I’m not involved’ ‘something else you have to do’ which demonstrate a level of dissatisfaction towards internationalisation.

Overall this interviewee provided various points of suggestion for improvement of internationalisation within her current HEI context. S4 clearly shares that there are many levels of internationalisation, from international students to research collaboration, professional development to target setting. S4 places a strong emphasis on how policy relating to internationalisation continues to change but is necessary as the concept of internationalisation and how it is applied in this current context has also changed over time.

Examples of contribution and experiences of internationalisation mentioned in semi-structured interview include: Supervisor of international students. Experience with

exchange programmes for students. An initial member of the HEI Internationalisation committee.

Research Questions and Answers using IPA

IPA is concerned with understanding the person in context and how they relate to or are involved in the world (Larkin et al., 2006). Additionally, IPA seeks to identify, through interpretation, convergence and divergence within a particular group's experience (Smith, 2010). The convergent and divergent experiences amongst the 11 interviewees are briefly summarised below according to each Research Question.

Research Question One: Defining and Understanding Internationalisation in HE

IPA attempts to make sense of the experiences of the participants, to try and comprehend how they came to define or understand internationalisation in the way that they do.

The opening question "In your opinion, what is internationalisation at ___ University?" allowed each of the educator's to tell their version of how they understand and define 'internationalisation' in their HEI context.

Convergence amongst responses from interviewees included commonalities amongst some of the definitions and understandings of internationalisation with the HEI context. In particular, internationalisation as a process linked to intercultural awareness and global citizenship, financial gain, student and staff mobility and internationalisation of the curriculum.

IPA also aims to identify divergence amongst responses relating to a phenomenon. In terms of defining internationalisation, the responses from the 11 interviewees included a varied of definitions relating to internationalisation. Specifically, a variety of

definitions came from educators within the same HEI despite being a staff member within the School of Education.

For several of the interviews the researcher reminded the interviewee of their previous questionnaire response to a similar question. By doing so it acted as a prompt and reminder of what they had previously shared in terms of internationalisation in the HE context.

Research Question Two: Experiences of Internationalisation in HEIs

The idiographic level of IPA allows the researcher to concentrate on specific individuals as they deal with specific situations or events in their lives (Larkin et al., 2006; Smith, 2008). Furthermore, IPA is about making sense of experience. Therefore, each of the interviewees were asked “How do you experience internationalisation at ___University?” Naturally, each of the educators, some more than others, went on to explain in great depths, their current and also their past experiences of internationalisation.

A point of convergence between interviewees that arose was that several of the interviewees took time to share how they had experienced internationalisation in other HEIs. Specific examples include:

J2 had worked in several other Japanese HEIs during his 30+ years career as an educator. He laughed at how his current HEI struggled to be anywhere near as internationalised as his previous HE workplaces. One reason he provided for this was the disparities in the allocation of government funding related to internationalisation. J2 shared that the implementation of government policy and government spending relating to internationalisation impacts upon how internationalisation is viewed or implemented in HEIs.

J3 was quick to share that Japan is far behind in terms of internationalisation in HE, and his current HEI was “the worst” in terms of internationalisation in his experience. To get a deeper understanding, he was asked to provide examples to further explain what he meant by this. In his response he alluded to the idea that it is always good to improve. This sentiment is a common trait of Japanese culture, to be humble, eager to continually improve. The researcher, keen to demonstrate authenticity through appreciation for the perspectives of others shared that they had had first-hand experience of this desire to continually seek improvement whilst studying and working in a Japanese HEI (Patton, 2002; Smith et al., 2009).

J1 shared her experience as a lecturer in Japan compared to her experience in U.S.A. She shared that she was still coming to terms with her new working environment compared to her brief experience as an educator in U.S.A. J1 was open, positive and eager to experience and be involved in internationalisation within her role in the Japanese HEI.

A4 compared her past experiences of internationalisation in HEIs in relation to working in the School of Business and now, the School of Education. She shared that there were differences in the way internationalisation was applied in each school and how each seemed to have different goals associated with internationalisation. An example she provided was that more international students from China were present in the School of Business compared to the School of Education. A4 emphasised that her past involvement in internationalisation committees, she hoped, had led to improvements and success.

A2 had worked in numerous HEIs around the world including England, other parts of Europe and in Australia. She shared that each experience had been somewhat different

and had probably, in some way, influenced her current experience and understanding of internationalisation. Having been a member of the internationalisation committee within her current HEI she became frustrated with the lack of output or improvement led her to decline further invitations to be involved. A2 was eager to demonstrate her range of experiences as an educator in various HEIs, sharing positive as well as negative experiences. She noted that internationalisation was very different in Australia compared to what she had experienced in England and that lessons could be learned from both.

Research Question Three: Future of Internationalisation and Recommendations

IPA is committed to situating personal meaning in context, therefore the recommendations provided are directly related to the individual participant's experience. Each of the interviewees were asked questions such as "What do you envisage for the future direction of internationalisation for your HEI?" "How could your experience of internationalisation in HE be improved?" Evidence of convergence amongst educators was demonstrated in some of the recommendations that were similar amongst interviewee responses. Several participants had lots to contribute in terms of future ideas, particular more so interviewees in Australia and Scotland than in Japan. Recommendations referred to professional development, improved communication and clearer vision and values surrounding internationalisation.

A point of divergence in terms of the answer to this research question included A4's response which was quite forthright in her responses and noted this about herself and her approach to the interview. She was opinionated in terms of her experience and shared that she was about to retire. A4 expressed that she had contributed to her best

ability but the issue of internationalisation was no longer her responsibility and was sceptical that attitudes or practice surrounding this phenomenon were going to change anytime soon.

Summary of Further Detailed Interview Evidence

When using IPA as an approach to data analysis the researcher has two aims in mind. One aim is to try and understand what their participant's world is like in terms of an experience of a specific event. The other aim is to develop an interpretative analysis so that the researcher can try to make sense of the participant experience in relation to a "wider social, cultural, and perhaps even theoretical context" (Larkin et al., 2006, p.104). With this in mind, the next section provides direct responses from the participants in this study. They are presented in relation to particular themes within each research question.

RQ1- How do educators in Higher Education understand and define internationalisation?

This section answers attempts to answer Research Question One: **How do educators in HE understand and define internationalisation?** The findings are based on the analysis of the data from the questionnaires (94 responses) and eleven semi-structured interviews with educators from the education department in one Australian HEI (four), educators from the education department in one Japanese HEI (three) and educators from the education department in one Scottish HEI (four).

Research Question One: Questionnaire Findings

The study's first research question links directly to the questionnaire question aiming to establish *the extent to which the respondents felt that they had a clear understanding of internationalisation within their current HEI context*. Table 4.3 below compares the responses of the three groups of respondents. The responses suggest that levels of understanding of internationalisation vary amongst educators across the sample but also within each group, indicating lack of consensus about what internationalisation is even within the same department of the same institution. Whilst in the responses from each institution a high percentage of educators stated that they had a clear understanding of internationalisation within their current HEI context that is 41% of the Australian participants, 40% of the Japanese participants and 62% of the Scottish participants, a significant number of educators from each institution appeared to be unsure about what internationalisation means within their current HEI context: the percentage of responses for the neutral response 'neither' was 23% for the Australian HEI, 40% for the Japanese HEI and 19% for Scottish HEI, while the corresponding percentages for 'disagree' and 'strongly disagree' (with the statement that I have a

clear understanding of internationalisation within my current HEI context) were 36%, 20%, and 19% respectively. These responses indicate variability in the educators' understanding of internationalisation within their current HEI context and across the three HEIs. The responses are illustrated in Table 4.3 below.

Table 4. 2 Results from Question 1 of Questionnaire

(Key: TITLE: *A*= Australia, *J*=Japan, *S*= Scotland

Data: *SA*=Strongly agree, *A*=Agree, *N*=Neither, *D*= Disagree, *SD*=Strongly Disagree)

An open ended question was included in the questionnaire to gather comments from the educators in the form of qualitative data. The question asked questionnaire

respondents to define internationalisation. The response rates to this open ended question were fair as 73% of the participants from the Australian HEI, 92% of the participants from the Japanese HEI and 85% of the participants from the Scottish HEI responded to this open ended question. The responses captured broad and varied definitions of internationalisation within and across the three HEIs. No definition was identical or significantly similar; a range of opinions were noted.

Upon analysis of the responses to this open ended question, it became clear that respondents conceptualised internationalisation as a process that serves specific purposes. In line with the definitions provided through the questionnaire, the definitions of internationalisation provided through the semi-structured interviews also framed internationalisation as a process aiming to fulfil certain purposes. Based on this, responses were clustered into the following themes:

Internationalisation is a process aiming to

1. promote inter-cultural awareness and global citizenship
2. facilitate staff and student mobility
3. infuse the curriculum with international perspectives
4. generate financial gain

1. Internationalisation is a process of promoting inter-cultural awareness and global citizenship: Questionnaire Responses

Over half of the participants who responded to the open ended question associated internationalisation with opportunities for staff and students to become more aware of international issues and to develop their understanding of other cultures and education

systems. As one of the Australian respondents put it, internationalisation is about developing:

'Knowledge, understanding and a cultural awareness of international issues and education systems, and of the needs and customs of the diverse range of students in our institutions' (Australian questionnaire respondent 3)

Participants defined internationalisation with reference to inter-cultural understanding and sensitivity:

'I think that 'internationalisation' means going beyond ethnocentrism' (Japanese questionnaire respondent 13)

'To fulfil its social responsibilities, institutions need to understand the multiple cultures they are exposed to and to accommodate their values and beliefs in the processes of dissemination of new knowledge' (Australian questionnaire respondent 15)

Furthermore, respondents perceived internationalisation as a process of promoting global citizenship. A respondent from the Scottish HEI noted that internationalisation is instrumental in helping students to *'become global citizens in a global community with understanding of global perspectives'* (Scottish questionnaire respondent 6). And its aim is *"to facilitate the development of intercultural competences, international perspectives and ethical sensitivities and global citizenship amongst graduates"* (Scottish questionnaire respondent 47).

Similarly, respondents from the Japanese HEI noted:

[Internationalisation refers to] *'efforts to collaborate with each other, considering the earth to be the world without borders and understanding different values and rules'* (Japanese questionnaire respondent 5)

'Whether your students can communicate and do well at any time, in any place, and with anybody, I believe, is the barometer for internationalisation' (Japanese questionnaire respondent 16)

A commonality between responses from the Australian and Japanese HEI was the reference to internationalisation as a 'peaceful process'. This is illustrated by the following response from an Australian participant:

[Internationalisation refers to] *'the acceptance and promotion of shared values and practices demonstrating that all our world's peoples are one. Moreover, [internationalisation refers to] a common aspiration to ensure that differences are not impediments to collaboration. More so, that ideas and responses enhancing human life are vigorously pursued. Furthermore, that empathy for others and not antipathy are a first acknowledgement'* (Australian questionnaire respondent 22)

Similarly, some of the Japanese participants defined internationalisation as:

'The peaceful mixing of people from different cultures, coming together and exchanging ideas and ways of doing things to improve society' (Japanese questionnaire respondent 19)

And

'The process of building a peaceful world' (Japanese questionnaire respondent 3).

1. Internationalisation is a process of promoting inter-cultural awareness and global citizenship: Semi-Structured Interview Responses

One interviewee from the Australian HEI defined internationalisation as *“providing an experience for students to go to an international destination and experience another culture [because] students ought to be out in the world”* (A1). She also noted that her HEI is keen on the idea that

“Other cultures and other societies are experienced by students and staff giving people a broader view of the world and possibly their own place in it. So, teachers in training at various stages of their Bachelor of Education degree go to another setting. So the latest one that I know about was a group of early years’ educators went to Japan and worked with colleagues there”.

A1 also noted that

“There’s maybe an intuitive sense among educators that we need to create experiences for these students to step outside of their own comfort zone”.

A Scottish interviewee (S3) shared that

“Intercultural citizenship should be a key part, a key element of internationalisation.”

2. Internationalisation is a process of facilitating staff and student mobility: Questionnaire Responses

Staff and student mobility was mentioned frequently (42%) in response to the open ended question asking respondents to provide a definition of internationalisation based on their understanding of it. Respondents from the Australian HEI defined internationalisation as:

'Having students from other countries come to study at our institution' (Australian questionnaire respondent 11)

And

'Bringing students into our university from other parts of the world, engagement with institutions, students and communities outside Australia. In the broadest sense, it includes teaching, research and other types of engagement, onshore and offshore' (Australian questionnaire respondent 7)

Such perspectives were also present in the Scottish sample with respondents from the Scottish HEI stating that internationalisation could be defined as:

[Internationalisation means] *'opening the university to the world with active exchanges of students and teachers'* (Japanese questionnaire respondent 7)

'Student and staff mobility' (Scottish questionnaire respondents 19, 41, 46).

2. Internationalisation is a process of facilitating student and staff mobility:

Semi-Structured Interview Responses

Several of the interviewees defined internationalisation in terms of student mobility. One of the interviewees from the Australian HEI spoke about her experience of organising international experiences for her students:

"So they go to a developing country which I specify based on the agreements that we have at the time [...] they go for 4 weeks in groups, yeah they are hosted by another organization that you know we are close with—they have facilities on ground. So I send the students out there, and they are learning about development issues. But also

those communities are benefiting from having our students there, either financially benefiting or hopefully just in building some sort of mutual relationship” (A3).

Another interviewee from the Australian HEI referred to internationalisation as reciprocal student mobility:

“It’s a physical exchange and also an exchange of ideas and the building of relationships between students in our institution with the students of another institution or community elsewhere and that means our students going there or other students coming here - it works both ways” (A4).

Interviewees from the Japanese and Scottish HEI also spoke of internationalisation in terms of student mobility:

“Our students are required to go abroad once or twice and do fieldwork in a different country in order to graduate” (J1).

“For me, internationalisation is people coming from other parts of the world to study here but also giving our students an international experience [...] work experience abroad or something like that” (S1).

Internationalisation was also defined in relation to international experiences of staff such as cross-national research collaborations, membership in committees of international professional associations, attendance in international conferences, but also recruitment of staff of different nationalities:

“As a researcher I’m being encouraged to promote, develop and otherwise enhance research relationships with partners at the big universities and those are all overseas” (A4)

Examples of international research collaboration included:

“Well, we get research funds every year and at least I and most of us use those to go to academic conferences, usually international academic conferences where researchers from other countries gather” (spoken with positivity and as if it should be the norm everywhere) (J1)

“For me, part of internationalisation is going to international conferences and joining other international networks and meeting other colleagues from around the world” (S4)

Despite the positive comments regarding international research collaboration it was noted by two Scottish interviewees that the opportunities may be unequally distributed and not experienced by the majority of educators:

“There isn’t enough money to fund everybody to do that [for staff to have an international experience]” (S3)

“A lot of my colleagues have actually been abroad and on visits and things like that...and I haven’t done that” (S4).

3. Internationalisation is a process of infusing the curriculum with international perspectives: Questionnaire Responses

A commonality between responses from educators from the Australian and Scottish HEI was that many defined internationalisation in terms of teaching, learning and the curriculum. A sizable number of the respondents from the Scottish HEI defined internationalisation as:

‘A process of bringing international perspectives to teaching and learning’ (Scottish questionnaire respondent 47)

'Providing teaching and learning activities and resources which reflect international approaches' (Scottish questionnaire respondent 41)

And

'The use of international perspectives and capital in learning and teaching' (Scottish questionnaire respondent 46)

Similarly, educators from the Australian HEI also defined internationalisation in relation to teaching, learning and curriculum, mentioning *'considerations of international dimensions in education'* (Australian questionnaire respondent 17) and *'a curriculum and educational ethos that is inclusive of global perspectives and intercultural understanding'* (Australian questionnaire respondent 19).

Teaching, learning and the curriculum did not feature in the definitions provided by the educators in the Japanese HEI in the responses to the open ended question in the questionnaire. Only one indirect reference to this was noted in the following comment:

[Internationalisation] *'is the process involving Japanese educators, in reviewing the present Japanese education by exchanging ideas with educators from abroad'* (Japanese questionnaire respondent 1)

3. Internationalisation is a process of infusing the curriculum with international perspectives: Semi-Structured Interview Responses

Several of the interviewees defined internationalisation as a process of infusing the curriculum with international perspectives. One of the interviewees from the Australian HEI defined internationalisation as *"bringing in any sort of discussion around how other countries look at education, so let's say, what Hong Kong does or*

what does Singapore do?” (A4). This point was echoed in the response of another interviewee from the Australian HEI, who noted that “internationalisation is about helping our students to understand how other systems work, including developing and delivering [international] programs within their undergraduate courses” (A3). Additionally, a fellow Australian interviewee noted that in order to abide by quality assurance processes she has to “demonstrate and incorporate a much more internationalisation perspective within the curriculum and within the faculty” (A4).

Interviewees from the Scottish HEI also defined internationalisation in relation to the curriculum:

“Internationalisation is ‘a way of making sure that anything that we teach does not simply relate to our local or even national context, but to an international context” (S1).

“Internationalisation is about us thinking about our curriculum and asking key questions about how our curriculum supports and engages learning for individuals from other parts of the world” (S2).

One of the interviewees from the Japanese HEI also linked internationalisation to the curriculum noting how important it is that students get opportunities to discuss global issues in class so that they can understand *“how the whole world is connected essentially” (J1). The same interviewee also spoke of “two classes specifically on ‘international understanding’, both required courses for graduation” (J1). Another interviewee from the Japanese HEI referred to internationalisation as a process of “promoting English proficiency amongst the Japanese students” (J2). In his view, this is because “in Japan, the priority is not to be behind other countries and the government wants Japanese kids to be more global so that they can compete with*

people with other countries when they go out” (J2). The third interviewee from the Japanese HEI also linked internationalisation to learning other languages. He mentioned *“different foreign language classes to choose from other than English [which is compulsory] and some, like events for students to interact with the foreign students in their native language and in Japanese”* (J3). Reference to languages was also made by an interviewee from the Scottish HEI who suggested:

“I think promoting languages is also part of internationalisation” (S4).

4. Internationalisation is a process of generating financial gain:

Questionnaire Responses

Several educators in Australia suggested that internationalisation could be defined as a process aiming to generate financial gain:

‘Internationalisation simply means \$\$\$\$’ (Australian questionnaire respondent 12)

‘As applied to higher education, internationalisation seems to be mostly about profit-making through tapping into markets outside Australia to run programs badged by our university. It is partly about our branding internationally’ (Australian questionnaire respondent 1)

Internationalisation as a process of profit making also featured in the responses of the participants from the Scottish HEI:

‘Partly, internationalisation is about international students bringing money to the university’ (Scottish questionnaire respondent 35)

‘There is an element of selling of education in/to other countries’ (Scottish questionnaire respondent 15)

However, only one educator in Japan mentioned finance when defining internationalisation and even this mention did not explicitly link internationalisation with financial profit:

'[internationalisation means] the movements of people, things, money and information to strengthen reciprocity between countries in the field of education'
(Japanese questionnaire respondent 4)

4. Internationalisation is a process of generating financial gain: Semi-Structured Interview Responses.

Some of the interviewees from the Australian and Scottish HEI defined internationalisation as a profit-oriented venture. According to A2, Federal Government funding relates to how many exchange programs run to how much money the HEI makes from internationalisation is important. In their view this is *"turning into a business model [because] there is a lot of money to be made from internationalisation"* (A2). She also stated that her HEI *"pushes the idea of internationalisation"* which, in her opinion, is *"dictated by profit"*.

Furthermore, an Australian interviewee shared that *"the HEI recruits international students in order to help pay the bills"* (A2).

Summary of the Research Question One Findings

Overall, the definitions the educators provided in response to the open ended questionnaire question asking them to define internationalisation based on their understanding of it were varied. Also, the findings from the semi-structured interviewees provided an array of definitions and understandings of internationalisation from educators within the School of Education in HEIs. However,

despite the variation, some commonalties have been identified through the themes presented in this section.

These findings show that participants from all three HEIs understand internationalisation as a process that aims to promote inter-cultural awareness and global citizenship, facilitate staff and student mobility, infuse the curriculum with international perspectives and generate financial gain.

The next section further explores the lived experience of educators in HEIs by providing specific examples from three HEIs.

RQ2 - What are the educators' experiences of internationalisation in their Higher Education Institutions (HEIs)?

This section answers attempts to answer Research Question Two: What are the educators' experiences of internationalisation in their Higher Education Institutions (HEIs)? The findings are presented in terms of responses to questionnaires and also the themes identified from the interpretative phenomenological analysis of the semi-structured interviews which include:

1. Educators' Personal Encounters with Internationalisation
2. Educators' Experiences of Professional Development and Support
3. Educators' Experiences Challenges and Barriers
4. Educators' Contribution to Development of Internationalisation

1. Educators' Personal Encounters with internationalisation

In order to learn about these educators' experiences of internationalisation in their HEI, the second question of the questionnaire asked them to identify *how often they encounter internationalisation in their current role*. The responses (presented in Table 4.4) demonstrate that more educators than not encounter internationalisation in their role. Of note is that the responses were varied within each institution: whilst most educators from the same HEI and across HEIs agreed that internationalisation was encountered in their role, there were many who did not agree with this statement suggesting variability in the experiences of internationalisation within each institution.

Table 4. 3 Results from Question 2 of Questionnaire

(Key: TITLE: *A= Australia, J=Japan, S= Scotland*)

Data: SA=Strongly agree, A=Agree, N=Neither, D= Disagree, SD=Strongly Disagree)

As shown in the Table 4.4 above, over half of the questionnaire respondents stated that they encounter internationalisation in their current role. The highest percentage of respondents who agreed or strongly agreed that they encounter internationalisation in their current role was in the Japanese sample (72%), followed by the Scottish sample (56%), and Australia (50%).

While these percentages provide an indication of the extent to which the participants encounter internationalisation in their current role, they do not provide information about what form these encounters take. Such information was gleaned from the semi-

structured interviews. The interviewees spoke of encounters with internationalisation in relation to academic and support activities, as explained in the following sections.

Educators' Personal Encounters with Internationalisation: Academic Activities

Some of the interviewees stated that they encounter internationalisation in the way of academic activities.

One of the interviewees from the Australian HEI talked about encounters with internationalisation in the classroom where she prepares students for work beyond their local context:

“We are educating our teachers to teach in New South Wales [...] but many of our students go to other jurisdictions to teach, some to Europe or North America and so they need to be able to interpret other curriculum documents. It is important for them to know what this means in a different context or how you interpret a document that's come out of a different cultural context. So, we are broadening their horizons and helping them understand that being a good teacher is more than just doing what New South Wales says you should do” (A1).

Another interviewee from the Australian HEI spoke of encounters with internationalisation in the form of insights shared in class by students who have been on visit or placement in another country:

“I'm teaching a subject called language culture and communication and they are all bringing me their experiences” (A2)

The further interviewee from the Australian HEI spoke about experiences from PhD supervision of international students and the academic activity involved.

The interviewees from the Japanese HEI spoke of encounters with internationalisation in activities aiming to support home students in developing English language proficiency:

“At our university they did an event every other week where it was called ‘English lunchtime’ and there were maybe 6-7 tables and each table had one foreigner, so I was at one table, each week and then either foreign teachers or foreign students with other Japanese students, it was basically 45 minutes of using only English to chat” (J1).

One of the interviewees from the Australian HEI also shared an experience focusing on the development of English language proficiency. However, in this case the beneficiaries are international students who *“are coming here to practice their English, to get a master's degree in an English speaking university in which then they hope to translate into a Ph.D. from an English speaking university and status at home”* (A3).

The prestige that many associate with a degree from a HEI based in an English speaking country was also alluded to by another of the interviewees from the Australian HEI who encounters internationalisation in her school's doctoral programme:

“So, many students in our [doctoral] programme come from other countries [...] They may be educators where they're from. They do a doctorate in education or we do ED as well. So, it could be a Ph.D. or ED. They may be administrators or they may be senior officials in schools or government officials [...] They come and seek that credential because there are several of Southeast Asian nations particularly looking to boost their own credentials” (A1)

Two of the interviewees from the Australian HEI mentioned academic activity with an international focus in the context of professional associations and publications:

“The other thing I do which is internationalisation, I think, is I work in international professional associations” (A3)

“In this faculty we are pretty big on international publications” (A2)

One of the participants from the Scottish HEI spoke of encounters with internationalisation as part of an EU funded research project in which she was involved:

“I’ve been very lucky, I’ve been part of the EU project. I’ve gone to Greece to work with colleagues there on this project. And, that’s been wonderful, it’s been a really, really good learning experience. It’s been a learning experience, we even took students with us. We’re working with students from Poland and Greece” (S3)

Another participant from the Scottish HEI also spoke of encounters with research collaborators from HEIs in other countries, specifically Sweden and Iceland. The participant highlighted the importance of intercultural competence in building and sustaining positive international relationships.

Educators’ Personal Encounters with Internationalisation: Support Activities

Some of the interviewees stated that they encounter internationalisation in the course of related support activities. One of the interviewees from the Australian HEI spoke of involvement in the admission of international students into her programme:

“I am the gatekeeper of international students into my program, so it is a balancing act... trying to meet the right target... and maintaining quality” (A3).

This interviewee referred to a recent case of an international applicant who had not met the English requirements and was

“going to take another test next month [...] I have been in those exams and I do not do it anymore [...] I don't know how long it takes to get from a to b, [...] you're raising unrealistic expectations for that yeah and you're also pushing her to go to a place she might get a falsified document” (A3).

One of the participants from the Scottish HEI spoke about her experience as part of the recruitment team:

“So I've been to China to talk to groups of students about the university and that is really to talk about courses that I run and courses that my colleagues run and for me, it's really important to have integrity while you're doing this because I think, the marketing people go there to get numbers. But for me, it's to really try and make initial relationship, I mean that's difficult, because we've got groups of forty or seventy or hundred students but, I think it's really important for students to make a connection with the person that will be teaching them when they come here, and the subject area they're coming to study. It's also important for me as I've seen where my students come from and that's been such a positive experience for me you know because you bring back that understanding of where students come from...I've been so lucky!” (S3)

This Scottish participant believes that the presence of academic staff in recruitment events is important because it could be people-centred rather than target-led. However, she displays her dissatisfaction by emphasising she was ‘told’ by policymakers that she needs to bring in more students:

“For me it's about the human touch but for the institution internationalisation is all to do with targets [...] and those targets are intrinsically linked to financing as well.

I think it's, you know that seems to be the main drive for, for bringing students and we've been told that we need to bring more students” (S3).

Another participant from the Scottish Institution spoke of organising a yearly educational trip for undergraduate students:

“So I took the lead in this because at that time there were no opportunities for undergraduates to be going anywhere. And I felt as students on a teacher education programme they needed to develop wider perspectives because most of them were from the local area and hadn't ventured out much” (S4).

2. Educators' Experiences of Professional Development and Support

Three of the questionnaire questions asked the participants to indicate the extent to which they are satisfied with the opportunities for professional development and with the support they receive from their HEI with regards to internationalisation.

The first of these questions asked about the participants' satisfaction levels in relation to the training for internationalisation available in their HEI. The responses indicated a high level of dissatisfaction from these educators towards their HEI in regards to its investment in educating their staff about internationalisation. As can be seen in Table 4.5, the Japanese educators expressed the highest levels of dissatisfaction with 56% disagreeing or strongly disagreeing that their HEI provides adequate training and education about internationalisation, followed by nearly half their Scottish counterparts (48%) who felt the same way. Only just over a quarter of the Australian participants (27%) expressed dissatisfaction but half of them selected the neutral response 'neither' indicating that they are not satisfied either. Satisfaction levels were the same in the Australian and Scottish sample at 23%, but only 12% of the Japanese participants expressed satisfaction.

Table 4. 4 Results from Question 3 of Questionnaire

(Key: TITLE: *A= Australia, J=Japan, S= Scotland*)

Data: *SA=Strongly agree, A=Agree, N=Neither, D= Disagree, SD=Strongly Disagree*)

The second question asked participants to indicate the extent to which they receive support and professional development from their HEI in order to further understand internationalisation.

The respondents from the Australian HEI had the highest percentage who strongly disagreed (23%) or disagreed (41%) that they receive support and professional development to understand internationalisation, followed by the respondents from the Japanese HEI, 24% of whom disagreed and 28% of whom strongly disagreed. The respondents from the Scottish HEI had the highest levels of agreement as 10% strongly agreed and 25% agreed that they are supported in the understanding of internationalisation. It is interesting to note the variability in the responses from each HEI, particularly in Japan and Scotland. This variability suggests that individual educators within the same institutions can have very different experiences of support and professional development in relation to internationalisation. This may reflect differences in the actual opportunities available to these educators within their HEI or differences in their perceptions of what constitutes support and professional development and their expectations. The findings from this particular question could also reflect the fact that support and professional development may be unequally distributed or available to educators in whatever country they work.

Table 4. 5 Results from Questions 5, 6 and 7 of Questionnaire

(Key: TITLE: *A= Australia, J=Japan, S= Scotland* Data: *SA=Strongly agree, A=Agree, N=Neither, D= Disagree, SD=Strongly Disagree*)

Question 5 I believe my HEI provides me with sufficient resources to support the process of internationalisation	Question 6 I receive support and professional development from my HEI in order to further understand internationalisation	Question 7 I was involved in the creation of internationalisation policies and procedures at my HEI																																				
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The third questionnaire question relating to professional development and support asked the respondents to indicate the extent to which their HEI provides them with sufficient resources to support the process of internationalisation. Responses to this question indicated that educators in all three HEIs felt that they were not provided with sufficient resources to engage effectively in the process of internationalisation. This is

due to the significant disagreement that their HEI provides them with sufficient resources to achieve in this process (Disagree= A27%, J 36%, S 29% Neither A36%, J36%, S 35%). Australian educators report a higher level of satisfaction (27%) compared to those in Japan (16%) and Scotland (17%).

In order to gain further insights in relation to professional development and support, after these three questions, space was provided for the educators to add any comments they considered relevant to this topic. This section was fairly well answered with 59% of Australian educators, 64 % of Japanese and 42% of Scottish educators making comments. Only a small number of the comments were fairly positive or positive.

Indicative comments included:

[In regards to resource allocation] *'Everyone is treated equally'* (Australian questionnaire respondent 21)

'It's there if you go after it yourself' (Scottish questionnaire respondent 20)

'When it comes to internationalisation, I'm not sure you can ever receive sufficient resources. There are many opportunities out there to expand to or reach out to foreign countries' (Japanese questionnaire respondent 5)

However, the Australian respondent continued to comment

'...but there is limited staff, time and money to do so. The larger the presence of academic staff at international conferences, seminars and workshop, the better.' (Australian questionnaire respondent 21)

Similarly, other respondents from all three institutions shared negative responses including:

'Few resources are provided, and the faculty are not motivated or committed.'
(Japanese questionnaire respondent 7)

'I know there is a training course although the one I applied for was cancelled due to lack of interest' (Scottish questionnaire respondent 20)

The majority of comments in relation to professional development indicated limited or no professional development and support for internationalisation, and highlighted this as a barrier to the educators' effective engagement with internationalisation. Barriers and challenges emerged as one of the subordinate themes under the superordinate theme "educators' experiences of internationalisation" so relevant comments from the open ended question asking about the questionnaire respondents' experiences of professional development and support are presented below as part of this subordinate theme.

3. Educators' Experiences of Challenges and Barriers

Challenges and Barriers: Lack of Clarity

Several questionnaire respondents and interviewees referred to lack of clarity as an obstacle to their engagement with internationalisation:

"I don't really understand the HEI's agenda in this regard nor what is expected of me in order to support it" (Australian questionnaire respondent 1, 2/5= Disagree on Likert Scale)

"Unpacking policy and process is often difficult, and with internationalisation, there seems to be another layer of complications." (Australian questionnaire respondent 5, 3/5= Neither on Likert Scale)

“We are not very clear about what this means on the ground” (Scottish questionnaire respondent 6, 2/5=*Disagree on Likert Scale*),

One of the interviewees from the Scottish HEI referred to tensions arising from conflicting understandings of what internationalisation is and shared his distaste for institutional hierarchy:

“I’m thinking an awful lot of people mistake internationalisation for pulling in international students which I don’t think is exactly what it should or is meant to be. Particularly people think this way because of the sheer amount of money that the international students will bring in. And I think a lot of people get those two [internationalisation and profit] mixed up. And I don’t necessarily think it is the lower level (referring to educators) people either” (S2).

A fellow Scottish interviewee echoed a sense of frustration by stating:

“I think we are told from ‘high above’, but I am not the international lead. So that’s my perception of it...but obviously, it’s in the, what do you call them...the KPUs, whatever!” (S4).

Challenges and Barriers: Logistical Constraints

A fair number of questionnaire respondents and interviewees referred to logistical constraints, such as lack of time, support and resources, as an obstacle to their engagement with internationalisation. They mentioned:

“[We have] no time nor workload allocation but expectation to take part.” (Australian questionnaire respondent 12, 2/5 = *Disagree on Likert Scale*)

“Although internationalisation is important I don't think we devote enough resources to supporting it. “(Australian questionnaire respondent 7, 2/5 = Disagree on Likert Scale)

“Misplaced resource allocation...no measureable outcomes are provided. No tangible outcomes” (Scottish questionnaire respondent 16, 2/5)

“No extra resources to support students with language” (Scottish questionnaire respondent 5, 2/5)

One of the interviewees from the Australian HEI commented that internationalisation is work that

“Requires defining as you go. I tend to stay away from those because that becomes a time and energy suck trying to figure out what to do could take all your time” (A2).

Two of the interviewees from the Scottish HEI also commented on the issue of time:

“In my opinion, we have been asked to do far too much [in regards to internationalisation] (S4)

“My problem is that I'm continually being forced because of other policies to think of my time and it's that competition between research, teaching and internationalisation” (S1).

An interviewee from the Australian HEI also commented on the additional resources required to develop the English language skills of international students coming to study in their HEI:

“We have limited capacity, there is limited capacity particularly for international students whose English is not at the scholarly level required for academic work [...]

we have limited resources to boost the English language skills of these people, to help them develop those skills” (A1).

This concern was echoed by another interviewee from the Australian HEI:

“Typically, those [international] students you know they might be highly qualified in their own home environment but their language skills typically are not up for graduate work. And so there's a lot of extra work involved for those who teach in those programs to support those students adequately for progress through the program” (A2).

In addition to concerns about the academic needs of international students, as illustrated by the comments above, concerns were also expressed about the international students’ emotional and social needs and the extent to which they are understood and met in the host HEI. As one interviewee from the Scottish HEI noted:

“Some international students are completely unprepared for coming here, they're completely unprepared for the size of the university, the size of the place they'll be living with. They haven't any sense of what it's like to be leaving family and friends [...] thousands of miles away [...] we've got to give them the best experience they've paid for this experience. They have committed intellectually, emotionally and financially to this experience and we have a duty of care. You know we need to support our international students holistically and I'm not entirely sure this is implemented across the board at this university (S3).

This Scottish interviewee highlights the responsibility and pressure experienced by the educator in trying to ensure the international students are well supported. In this case she feels somewhat obliged to support the international student as part of her role.

Challenges and Barriers: The Context Specific Nature of Teacher Education

Interviewees also identified as a challenge, the tension between the context specific nature of teacher education and the internationalisation agenda. One of the interviewees from the Australian HEI stated:

“We would like to bring in more international students but that's pretty much limited to graduate students because the purpose of our bachelor of education programme is to train teachers from New South Wales and that's where it's certified [...] there's no recognition that just because it's a good degree here it can translate more broadly”

(A1)

The potential incompatibility between internationalisation and the context specific nature of teacher education was also brought up by interviewees from the Scottish HEI. One stated:

“We offer national teacher education. And a national teacher education by its very nature and by the fact that it's strictly controlled by government is difficult to internationalise because it's all-Scotland focused, driven by the [General Teaching Council for Scotland] standards [...] For me, that is a real issue because actually it mitigates against international students coming to study in our teacher education programme because it's Scotland- focused, Scotland-centric [...] We make attempts to relate Scottish policy to the wider international policy but it's still colloquial and that's where my problem is and I don't see how we will be able to square that round peg based on the fact that that's the attitude that the Scottish Government has” (S1).

Challenges and Barriers: Ethical Issues

A number of the interviewees raised ethical issues in relation to aspects of internationalisation in HE that they considered questionable. One of these issues

pertains to what one of the interviewees from the Australian HEI perceived as marketisation of HE:

“I find it really embarrassing the way Australian universities go and market themselves in Asia [...] and they outbid each other for fees. I just said, well, the university should be rethinking what it's doing because that's not really internationalization, that's just money making” (A2).

Another ethical issue raised by interviewees from the Australian HEI concerned what this interviewee perceived as limited opportunities for outward mobility for home students who do not have the money required to finance such experiences:

“Not that many students take up that opportunity, I mean those who are well funded do, but those who have limited access to resources can't or don't have the resources to do that and in the school of education, that's probably half of our students...”

Similarly, Australian HEI Interviewee A2 noted that funded outward mobility opportunities tend to be more accessible to students with family connections who know *“the right person, the right door to knock on or, you know, how to get the attention of the right agency. So, in some ways I think of this internationalisation agenda as just yet another elitist agenda” (A2).*

Another ethical issue was raised by one of the interviewees from the Scottish HEI who commented on what the educator is required to do in regards to the monitoring of international students with Tier 4 visas. Furthermore, an interviewee from the Australian HEI raised an issue in relation to border control:

“Internationalisation is driven by immigration processes sometimes. I come on a student visa, I get my degree. If I can get a job and I'll do my paperwork, I can stay. So there's a long history of that and we've had some shonky operators” (A2).

The same interviewee raised another ethical issue, associated with what she referred to as ‘colonial tradition’:

“I was involved in this programme that sent student teachers to Ghana, to teach, to demonstrate to the Ghanaian teachers’ good pedagogy. Now I thought that was colonialism and I found that very distasteful. I just stopped getting involved because it’s just neo-colonialism. It’s just, here we are, you know, we’re bringing all these books and these ideas and you’ve got nothing, you are empty. [...] This is a colonial tradition and there is also colonial cringe about that” (A2).

Another interviewee from the same HEI highlighted a similar issue:

“Our university traditionally has done teacher education, [following] the Catholic tradition, in places like Myanmar, Timor-Leste and like somewhere in the South Pacific. We’ve been doing teacher education in these places forever and that’s based on the tradition of the nuns and brothers and things [...] But you can’t ignore the fact that there’s a sense of religious recruitment in this” (A4).

As noted in the previous section entitled ‘logistical constraints’, some of the interviewees mentioned the English language needs of international students and the limited resources available to support them. Two of the interviewees also highlighted an ethical dimension to this issue:

“One of the big focuses we have had has been on English language proficiency. You know, how do we help our students for whom English is not their first language, actually deal with the sorts of things they are supposed to do at an undergrad level? And, at a post grad level, that increases even more [...] When you get a failure rate like 70% you know, you have to think, ‘what’s happening here?’ Then you realise that students come in with fairly low IELTS score, around about 6 and the English

language written component is pretty poor [...] it doesn't mean they can't improve but how can we help improve that when we have one year and limited resources to get them through a course? And, in various points in time we've had discussions around, it's not ethical really to have students coming in to the course when their English is so poor but yet expect them to pass at the level that your domestic English speaking students do. And you can't have different rates for different students" (A3).

"I have always been quite critical...I have been quite concerned and ashamed of the low level of literacy amongst these students, and really questioned their ability. I thought it was unfair [...] they shouldn't have been started; they can't possibly understand the exam they are getting, because they cannot communicate in Basic English across a table" (S4).

4. Educators' Contribution to the Development of Internationalisation Policy

Two questionnaire questions asked about the respondents' contribution to the development and review of the internationalisation policy of their HEI. The first of these two questions asked the respondents to indicate the extent to which they agreed with the statement 'I was involved in the creation of internationalisation policies and procedures in my HEI'.

Table 4. 6 Results from Question 7 of Questionnaire

Key- TITLE: *A= Australia, J=Japan, S= Scotland*)

Data: *SA=Strongly agree, A=Agree, N=Neither, D= Disagree, SD=Strongly Disagree*)

The responses, shown in Table 4.7, demonstrate that most respondents were not involved in the creation of internationalisation policies and procedures at their HEI. No respondents from the Australian HEI agreed or strongly agreed that they were involved in the creation of internationalisation policies and procedures at their HEI. A small percentage of the respondents from the Japanese and Scottish HEI indicated involvement by strongly agreeing with the statement: 8% of the respondents from the

Japanese HEI strongly agreed and 12% agreed, while the corresponding responses from the Scottish HEI were 6% (strongly agree) and 11% (agree).

The second of these two questions asked the respondents about their involvement in the review of internationalisation policies and procedures in their HEI. Responses to this question suggested that only a few of the respondents had significant input in the review of internationalisation policies and procedures in any of the HEIs. Specifically, in each HEI a small number of educators indicated that they had been involved in such review. Only 4% of the questionnaire participants strongly agreed with this statement in Australia. In Scotland, only 8% strongly agreed and 10% agreed, and 16% of the Japanese respondents strongly agreed and 12% agreed with this statement, as illustrated in the Table 4.8:

Table 4. 7 Results from Question 8 of Questionnaire

Key-TITLE: *A= Australia, J=Japan, S= Scotland*)

Data: *SA=Strongly agree, A=Agree, N=Neither, D= Disagree, SD=Strongly Disagree*)

The semi-structured interviews provided insights that illuminate the responses to these two questionnaire questions. The interviewees from the Scottish HEI spoke of limited opportunities and tokenistic involvement:

“I would feel uncomfortable with being involved in policy because of how almost disconnected I feel from that aspect of internationalisation” (S2).

One of the interviewees from the Australian HEI commented on her involvement in the international committee in her HEI and her dissatisfaction with the way internationalisation was developing:

“When they started the international committee, ... there were crazy targets in relation to the numbers that came from above [...] I did push back on a lot of these things [but] all these administrators just got in there, so it would be all those long talks about selection criteria and scholarships, and I just did not bother about all that, I was interested in those big ideas and I did not go for re-election because I thought ‘my work is done’” (A2).

Another interviewee from the Australian HEI expressed concerns about the top-down approach to internationalisation in her HEI:

“[Internationalisation] gets strategically defined at the university executive level here to serve whatever purposes they've got and then it trickles down from there. So, we've got this internationalization agenda, we want to make these connections, we want to send students overseas but on the ground where you have to make it happen it's not necessarily supported in the ways we need to make it work [...] But there's rhetoric around and it's pervasive across the university sector” (A1).

Lack of awareness amongst staff was mentioned as an issue in relation to the HEI's internationalisation policy:

“There is a real lack of awareness in our faculty [...] Some staff members don't even know that we have an internationalization strategy [...] internationalization policies and KPIs, I don't think that I fully understand those. I certainly hear them spoken about when we have our internationalization committee meetings every three months

[...] but I don't feel I have a really good appreciation of what they are and what strategies are used to achieve them [...] I only get snippets of those" (A3).

One of the reasons for the lack of awareness mentioned by this interviewee could be the way information about the HEI's internationalisation agenda is communicated. This was suggested in the response of another interviewee from the Australian HEI who expressed scepticism about the way internationalisation information is disseminated in her HEI and about the impact it has on the ground:

"You can put these things in documents in front of people to read but they don't always read them. So important information is missed. For me, I've got a lot of information about these through my really good working relationship with some members of the international centre. I've been working really closely with them now for about five years. And I really can't underestimate how useful that's been for me. But I think other staff members who haven't been as involved with them [...] they have missed out a lot. Which is where I guess the international committee must try to share that knowledge better with everybody" (A4).

Summary of Research Question Two

In an attempt to understand the educators' experiences in regards to internationalisation in their HEI context, a variety of themes arose from the findings including the Encounters, Professional Development and Support, Challenges and Barriers, and their Contribution to Policy Development.

The following section explores way in which educators view the future of internationalisation in HEIs relative to their own experience.

RQ3 - What are the educators' views about the future of internationalisation in Higher Education (HE) and their recommendations for improvement?

This section answers Research Question Three: What are the educators' views about the future of internationalisation in Higher Education (HE) and their recommendations for improvement?

One of the questions in the questionnaire invited participants to indicate the extent to which they would appreciate the opportunity to have future involvement in the internationalisation process of their HEI. A sizable number of respondents indicated interest in this and many responded positively. In Australia 55% of educators agreed (41%) or strongly agreed (14%) that they would appreciate the opportunity to have future involvement in the internationalisation process in their HEI, as well as 50% (31% agreed, 19% strongly agreed) in Scotland and 40% (20% agreed, 20% strongly agreed) in Japan. Very few educators disagreed or strongly disagreed. Please see Table 4.9.

Table 4. 8 Results from Question 9 of Questionnaire

Key- TITLE: *A= Australia, J=Japan, S= Scotland*)

Data: *SA=Strongly agree, A=Agree, N=Neither, D= Disagree, SD=Strongly Disagree*)

Space was provided underneath this question for respondents to provide a qualitative response if they wished. Three subordinate themes arose from these responses:

1. Student Experience
2. Vision and Values
3. Systems and Resources.

These subordinate themes were closely aligned with the subordinate themes contributing to the superordinate theme 'Future Prospects' which arose from the semi-structured interviews determined by IPA. For this reason, the relevant qualitative responses from the questionnaire and from the interviews are presented together below.

1. Student Experience

The educators who participated in this study expressed strong concern about the student experience and keen desire to enhance it. A key reason for this was highlighted in the following questionnaire comments from two Japanese participants:

'It's going to be more and more important for our students to have global perspectives'
(Japanese Questionnaire respondent 3)

'We need to help our students see a world without borders' (Japanese questionnaire respondent 10)

One way to do this could be through the internationalisation of the curriculum, as noted by another Japanese questionnaire respondent and one of the interviewees from the Scottish HEI:

'In our professional degree programmes, domestic aspects have been stressed, but it's time to be more aware of international aspects' (Japanese questionnaire respondent 5)

"I would like to see a little bit more movement in terms of how we make our curriculum more engaging for our international audience. It's a much deeper philosophy, it's about understanding comparative studies. We don't do much on that [...] comparative studies between different cultures. Also, it's about taking forward thinking about pedagogy. Why is it that certain pedagogical approaches work really, really well in

say Canada and Australia but don't really work well in Scotland? It's all about culture, so it's about understanding the incumbent cultures in these different places and looking at attitudes and beliefs and mind-sets that kind of thing” (S1).

Another interviewee from the Scottish HEI spoke more broadly about opportunities for students to develop global citizenship:

“I think more work could be done internally [...] for example, we can try and encourage students, home students to work with, to buddy with, or to mentor international students. We need to look at what exactly is global citizenship, and how do we support this and how do we enhance this (S3).

According to a number of questionnaire respondents and interviewees, another way to enhance the student experience of internationalisation could be through student mobility:

‘We need to send more students to study abroad’ (Japanese questionnaire respondent 5)

‘We would like to send more students out and ensure equity, but funding is a problem’ (Scottish questionnaire respondent 19)

And

“Internationalisation should be about experiences for students that really enhance their lives and then the lives of future colleagues” (S3)

2. Vision and Values

The HEI’s vision for internationalisation and the values that should underpin this came up in the qualitative responses of the questionnaire and in the semi-structured interviews as an area for future development that would benefit from staff educator

input. As some of the Australian questionnaire respondents put it, *'educators should be invited to consultation'* (Australian questionnaire respondent 17) and should have *'input in policy development/review'* (Australian questionnaire respondents 5, 17 and 18). Furthermore, they should be given opportunities to *'provide feedback and comment on current practices'* (Australian questionnaire respondent 5) and to *'think conceptually about directions we might like to take and possibly brainstorm on what we could/should do'* (Australian questionnaire respondent 1).

The participating educators also mentioned staff development as an essential factor in shaping the future of internationalisation in their HEI:

"There should be opportunities for colleagues across disciplinary borders to meet and to really kind of drill down into what they're doing [with regards to internationalisation], why they're doing it, what works, and what doesn't work" (S3)

A similar point was made by one of the interviewees from the Australian HEI:

"There should be staff development, perhaps even in groups across schools, where you look at what you do now, and what you don't do, what should we be doing? It's really what you do now for a start and then is there anything that we think is missing? And how could we, how could we make the international student experience better and how could we make our own experience better as well?" (A2)

The importance of looking at the big picture and taking stock was noted by an interviewee from the Scottish HEI who noted:

"There needs to be much more of an understanding of the fact that we are a young university, we don't have history. In order to create that history, we have to start small build, modify, apply our research-based approach to promote internationalisation" (S2).

And another Scottish interviewee who suggested that:

“One has to understand the main reason why we are doing it [internationalisation], we have to recalibrate our attitude to internationalisation” (S4).

3. Systems and Resources

The limitations of systems and resources in supporting internationalisation emerged as a subordinate theme when educators spoke about barriers and challenges that hinder effective internationalisation (in Research Question Two). Therefore, it is no surprise what when considering the future prospects of internationalisation in their HEI, the participating educators spoke of the need to improve the systems required to support internationalisation and to allocate more resources to it.

One of the interviewees from the Scottish HEI pointed out that:

“If we're going to continue with internationalisation as a major thing, we need to radically overhaul our systems so it's a smooth as possible transition for these students... there needs to be someone that actually just sorts stuff for them... So I think we need to think a lot about how we actually support international students within our schools [...] it's a systems problem” (S1).

Furthermore, a Scottish questionnaire response suggested:

‘Provide a training programme to develop people in roles where they have responsibility for internationalisation because ad-hoc information is the current status quo’ (Scottish questionnaire respondent 25).

This sentiment was echoed in the response of one of the participants from the Australian HEI:

“We need to develop systems that don't hinder but actually facilitate smooth transitions for the international students so that when they're here they can concentrate on their experience rather than the bureaucracy” (A3)

Another interviewee from the Australian HEI spoke about the need to address the mismatch between policy and practice through improved systems and structures:

“There is a disconnect between what the policymaker thinks internationalisation is and what's actually happening on the ground. The global engagement plan is obviously about numbers but I think, you know, there are sections of that plan that are worthy. But, the structures and systems within the university do not fully support them so much more needs to be done there” (A2)

Similarly, a fellow Australian interviewee noted:

“I want to know from higher up what they mean by that [internationalisation] and what they expect me to do” (A1).

Questionnaire respondents in the Australian HEI said that they would benefit from *‘being given guidelines’* (Australian questionnaire respondents 7 and 11) and *‘have an opportunity to feedback’* (Australian questionnaire respondent 5).

With regards to resources, much emphasis was placed on current limitations and the need for improvements. Time and funding were highlighted as the two most valuable resources in the context of internationalisation:

‘There is little scope to pursue the international agenda within my current workload so more time is needed’ (Scottish questionnaire respondent 30)

[In terms of internationalisation] *“I'd like more time for guidance, for peers, for proper support”* (S3)

'We need more funds for overseas travel to international institutions. Face to face interaction and relationship building is done more effectively in person. Only through developing solid relationships first can collaborations be successful' (Australian questionnaire respondent 9)

'In order to do our best we need more support as subsidy from the government is decreasing year by year' (Japanese questionnaire respondent 1)

And

'Our university has international projects, but there exists no systematic tactic. Few resources are provided, and the faculty are not motivated or committed. More resource and effort is needed for future progress' (Japanese questionnaire respondent 7)

To conclude, several educators shared that they would like to *'be a part of policy or process development'* (Scottish questionnaire respondents 26, 28 and 35), *'play a key role on the progression of internationalisation initiatives across the institution'* (Scottish questionnaire respondent 47) or *'be involved in an iterative process of defining, reflection and evaluation'* (Scottish questionnaire respondent 35) when it comes to the future of internationalisation in HEIs.

Summary of Research Question Three

Research Question Three attempted to discover how educators' view the future of internationalisation in HEIs and what recommendations they could provide for improvement. Three subordinate themes arose from the responses of the research participants including: Student Experience; Vision and Values; Systems and Resources. Several recommendations for improving internationalisation were shared from educators in HEIs in Australia, Japan and Scotland.

Chapter Summary

In this chapter, findings from data analysis of quantitative and qualitative data have been presented to try and capture the phenomenon of internationalisation of HEIs from an educator's perspective and interpreting their lived experience.

This comparative study of educators' lived experiences of internationalisation in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) has revealed a number of relationships and variability between educators' definition, understanding and experience of internationalisation in their HEI context whether it be in Australia, Japan or Scotland.

Themes that arose in the findings included:

Internationalisation was defined and experienced differently by research participants however definition and understandings of internationalisation can be aligned to internationalisation is a process aiming to promote inter-cultural awareness and global citizenship, facilitate staff and student mobility, infuse the curriculum with international perspectives and generating financial gain. Internationalisation was experienced differently by research participants however experiences of internationalisation can include Personal Encounters, Professional Development and Support, Contribution to Policy, and Challenges and Barriers. The ways in which they view the future of this phenomenon was also quite varied however the future contributions and recommendations for improved internationalisation in HEIs, from educators included factors relating to student experience, values and vision and systems and resources.

Therefore, the lived experience of an educator can vary. There are significant commonalities and differences that occur between educators in HEIs and variability occurs in the experiences of internationalisation within each institution.

Overall, the findings from this research suggests that the educators lived experience of internationalisation in HEIs has many variables, consequences and outcomes. The next chapter will provide a critical discussion of the findings and their linkages to the existing literature and research in order to ascertain whether this new data support or contradicts the existing information.

CHAPTER FIVE Discussion

Introduction

The overall aim of this research was to understand educators' experiences and perspectives in regards to internationalisation within their HEI context. The study included educators from three different countries: Australia, Japan and Scotland. A sequential mixed method research approach, including questionnaire and semi-structured interviews was utilised to collect data from participants. The data collected were analysed using a descriptive approach to quantitative questionnaire data, a thematic approach to qualitative questionnaire data and an interpretivist approach to the semi-structured interview data.

This chapter includes an explanation of the findings and how they fit in with previously published knowledge of internationalisation in HE. It will provide a critical discussion of the findings set against the existing literature in Chapter Two. In particular, referenced throughout are the conceptual frameworks of Knight (1997; 1999). An adaptation of Knight's (1997, 1999) 'Rationales and Approaches of Internationalisation' is presented as one way to understand the relationship between the findings of this study and relevant literature. Furthermore, this chapter will identify how such findings, presented as participant voice, build upon the research of others and why this research has been necessary.

The structure of the present chapter is in the format of each research question; Research Question One, Research Question Two and Research Question Three supported with associated themes as demonstrated in Figure 5.1 Final Overall Theme

Chart. By doing so, the chapter aims to identify and discuss the varying experiences that exist amongst educators in Australia, Japan and Scotland.

Figure 5.1 Final Overall Theme Chart

RESEARCH QUESTION ONE How do educators in Higher Education (HE) define and understand internationalisation?		
Subordinate themes	Superordinate theme	Presentation order in Chapter 5
Internationalisation as a process relating to:	Definition and Understanding of Internationalisation is Evolving and Indefinite for Educators in HEIs	The evolving nature of Internationalisation Definition
Students and Staff Mobility		Understanding
Infuse the Curriculum with International Perspectives		Process
Intercultural Awareness		Alignment of Rationales and Educator Definitions of Internationalisation in Higher Education
Global Citizenship		Academic Rationale: Facilitate Mobility of Staff and Students Infuse the Curriculum with International Perspectives
Financial Gain		Cultural and Social Rationale: Intercultural Awareness and Global Citizenship
		Economic Rationale: Financial Gain International Students in Relation to Financial Gain
RESEARCH QUESTION TWO: What are the experiences of educators' in their Higher Education Institutions (HEIs)?		
Personal Encounters	Many Challenges and Barriers are Experienced by Educators in HEIs in regards to Internationalisation.	Educators' Encounters with Internationalisation Academic and Support Activities
Professional Development		Educators' Experiences of Professional Development Input and Influence
Challenges and Barriers		Educators' Experiences of Challenges and Barriers: Lack of Clarity and Disconnect Logistical Constraints Context Specific Nature of Teacher Education Ethical Issues
Contribution to Policy		Educators' Contribution to the Development of Internationalisation Approaches to Internationalisation

RESEARCH QUESTION THREE:		
What are the educators' views about the future of internationalisation in Higher Education (HE) and their recommendations for improvement?		
Student Experience	Educators are keen to propose Future Prospects and Recommendations for Internationalisation in their HEI context.	Student Experience: Leadership Professional Development Internationalisation of the Curriculum and Internationalisation at Home Home Students and International Students
Values and Vision		Values and Vision: Establishing and Communicating Clear Goals and Aims Improve Understanding (allow educator to be involved) Ensuring Staff Agency
Systems and Resources		Systems and Resources Intercultural Awareness and Global Citizenship Collaboration as a way to improve system and resources Context Geography Government (Australia, Japan and Scotland)

RQ1 - How do educators in HE understand and define internationalisation?

The educators from the Australian, Japanese and Scottish HEIs who participated in this research shared a variety of definitions and understandings of internationalisation within their HEI context. The answers to Research Question One and associated literature will be presented according to sections displayed in Figure 5.1. that are directly linked to the themes created during data analysis.

The subheadings include:

1. The Evolving Nature of Internationalisation in Higher Education (Definition and Understanding)
2. Alignment of Rationales and Educator Definitions of Internationalisation in Higher Education.

1. The Evolving Nature of Internationalisation in Higher Education (Definition and Understanding)

According to the findings of this research, internationalisation in HE continues to be a nebulous and ever changing concept for educators. Based on a variety of participants' understandings and definitions of internationalisation within their HEI context, a common theme that emerged from the analysis of qualitative data was the Evolving Nature of Internationalisation in Higher Education (Definition and Understanding).

Some of the interviewees noted that internationalisation in HEI is an evolving phenomenon with varying conceptualisations depending on who is using the term and for what purpose. An interviewee from the Australian HEI commented

“That term [internationalisation] has been around for what 15 years maybe in faculties of education or universities...and maybe less clear now. Why is that? [...] I think there's a lack of specificity on what anyone means by that [internationalisation] even at the policy level which means that everybody who comes in contact with the concept gets to define it however they see fit” (A1).

Another interviewee from the Australian HEI stated

“If it (internationalisation) doesn't have a definition, and if it requires defining, then it's the wrong word.” (A4).

The analysis of the responses to the open ended question of the questionnaire ‘how do you define internationalisation?’ captured broad and varied definitions of internationalisation within and across the three HEIs. One key finding was that no definition of internationalisation in HE was identical or significantly similar; a range of opinions were noted. This finding confirms that a variety of definitions and understandings of internationalisation from the educators’ point of view are available within and between HEIs.

Definition

The evolving definition of internationalisation in HEIs has been identified in previous research. Specifically, Knight (2004) and de Wit (2002) identify that definitions and processes of internationalisation in HEIs continue to become ever more complex. In particular, that one of the fundamental problems faced with internationalisation of

higher education is the diversity of related terms used to define internationalisation (de Wit, 2002).

There could be several reasons for the variety of responses that were shared by the participants of this study. Understandings of internationalisation can vary enormously (Caruana and Spurling, 2007) and not always favourably (Robson and Turner, 2007). One explanation for the increased complexity could be that a definition of internationalisation in HE can change depending on time and place (Knight, 2013). Another explanation for the variety of responses could be the position a person holds within the HEI or the HEI context as in where and when (Komotar, 2018).

The findings from this study support Knight's (2013) claim that a definition of internationalisation HE can change depending on time and place. The concept (of internationalisation) was not understood in the same way by educators in the same HEI context. A major finding of this research, that there is a lack of consistent definition amongst educators, is in line with the idea of Warwick and Moogan (2013), who state that definitions of internationalisation provided by HEIs do not reflect the experiences of staff within the institution. This may be because if each stakeholder defines internationalisation according to their own perspective, then it is not easily compared or easily defined (Yesufu, 2018; Gao, 2015).

One reason for the variety of responses from educators in this study is compatible with Komotar (2018) who posits that the position of a person within an HEI - including for example a designer of policy or a staff member within the research community - may determine their interest or quality of experience of internationalisation in their HEI context. In regards to this study the position of the person is an educator in a HEI in

either Australia, Japan or Scotland. An educator being someone who teaches, trains or provides education in the HEI.

The findings from this research are similar to several studies (Bedenlier and Zawacki-Richter, 2015; Komotar, 2018; Knight, 2013) as they agree that an educator's context may have an impact on their experience of internationalisation. In particular, Bedenlier and Zawacki-Richter (2015) note "academic faculty members are affected by the internationalisation of higher education at different levels, covering a range from immediate personal involvement in the institutional context to global developments with indirect impacts" (p.197) supporting the idea that internationalisation will always mean "different things to different people" (Knight, 2007, p.1).

Understanding

Internationalisation as a phenomenon within HEIs, is a challenge to understand by educators who work in the HEI context. This was determined from a comparison of responses of the three groups of respondents which indicated variability in the educators' understanding of internationalisation within their current HEI context and across the three HEIs.

The responses from educators in HEIs revealed that levels of understanding of internationalisation vary amongst educators across the sample but also within each group, indicating lack of consensus about what internationalisation is even within the same department of the same institution. One way to understand the differences amongst the educators' understanding and definition of internationalisation could be related to the different processes and rationales used by the whole institution or individual departments in terms of their approach to internationalisation.

Process

It has been suggested that internationalisation exists as a process that is deemed necessary in HEIs (OECD, 2014). The process of internationalisation can appear in several forms and is often a key aim for HEIs. Internationalisation can be defined as “the process of integrating an international/intercultural dimension in the teaching, research and service functions of the institutions” (Knight and de Wit, 1995, p.17). In 2015, the definition of internationalisation provided by Knight (2004), was updated by De Wit and Hunter (2015), who defined internationalisation of higher education as “the intentional process of integrating an international, intercultural or global dimension into the purpose, functions and delivery of post-secondary education, in order to enhance the quality of education and research for all students and staff, and to make a meaningful contribution to society” (De Wit and Hunter, 2015, p. 3). The addition of the term ‘intentional’ indicates that a HEI has specific ways which they aim to internationalise. The findings of this current research support findings from earlier research which determined that the process of internationalisation in a HEI can have many dimensions, and that despite the varying definitions of internationalisation by educators in HEIs, respondents conceptualised internationalisation as a process that serves specific purposes. In particular, common responses from the findings of this research included that internationalisation is a process and can be presented under four main themes: Financial Gain, Intercultural Awareness and Global Citizenship, Internationalisation of the Curriculum, Mobility of Staff and Students.

The four main themes are similar to, and to some extent, support the four rationales provided by Knight (1999): Economic, Social/Cultural, Political and Academic Rationales. They are explained further in the next section.

2. Alignment of Rationales and Educator Definitions of Internationalisation in Higher Education

Rationales of Internationalisation in Higher Education

The conceptual framework of Knight (1997) regarding rationales of internationalisation can be applied to the specific definitions and understandings of internationalisation of the educators within this study. Knight's (1997) conceptual and organisational framework of internationalisation of higher education proposes four main rationales of internationalisation: Political, Economic, Academic and Cultural-Social.

Internationalisation agenda can vary between HEIs (Altbach and Knight, 2007). Findings from this research identified that each HEI has its own specific goals regarding internationalisation. However, despite having unique, context specific goals, commonalities arose in terms of overall rationale for internationalisation in HEIs. The findings from this research support the conceptual framework developed by Knight (1997) in that educators could associate their definitions and understanding of internationalisation of HEIs within their current context with one or more of the rationales acknowledged in Knight's (1997) conceptual framework.

In the same way that there are several ways to define and describe internationalisation, similarly, there are also many rationales and motivations driving internationalisation in HEIs. The unique HEI rationales of the HEIs included in this study may have had an impact upon the educator's definition or understanding of this phenomenon.

The table below illustrates the four overarching rationales presented by Knight (1997) compared to the similar rationales identified from this research.

Table 5. 1 Rationales Driving Internationalisation (adapted from Knight, 1997)

Rationales of Internationalisation in HEIs (1997)	Internationalisation as a process that serves specific purposes and aims (Findings of present study)
<p>Academic</p> <p>International research and teaching</p> <p>Extension of academic horizon</p> <p>Institution building</p> <p>Profile and status</p> <p>Enhancement of quality</p> <p>International academic standards</p>	<p>Academic</p> <p>Infuse the Curriculum with international perspectives</p> <p>Facilitate Staff and Student Mobility</p>
<p>Economic</p> <p>Revenue Generation</p> <p>E-competitiveness</p> <p>Labour Market</p> <p>Financial incentives</p>	<p>Economic</p> <p>Generate Financial Gain</p>
<p>Political</p> <p>Foreign Policy</p> <p>National security</p> <p>Technical assistance</p> <p>Peace and mutual understanding</p> <p>National identity</p> <p>Regional identity</p>	<p>Government</p> <p>Geographical Context</p>
<p>Social/Cultural</p> <p>National cultural identity</p> <p>Intercultural understanding</p> <p>Citizenship development</p> <p>Social and community development</p>	<p>Social/Cultural</p> <p>Facilitate Staff and Student Mobility</p> <p>Promote Intercultural Awareness and Global Citizenship</p>

Academic Rationale

A rationale for internationalisation of HEIs proposed by Knight (1997) is the academic rationale of internationalisation. The academic rationale focuses on how a HEI achieves and works towards international academic standards. Promoting and supporting international dimensions of teaching and research that will hopefully improve the overall quality of the HEI are some ways which HEIs rationalise internationalisation. Improvement within a HEI may occur when “internationalisation is considered to be central to the mission of the institution and not a marginalised endeavour” (Qiang, 2003, p.253). Examples of how educators define and understand internationalisation as an academic rationale in this study was identified and presented as Facilitating Mobility of Staff and Students and Curriculum in HEIs.

Academic Rationale: Facilitate Mobility of Staff and Students

Komotar (2018) claims that “at present, the main form of internationalisation is still (short and long-term) international mobility of students and staff” (p.7). Universities UK International (UUKi) state “internationalisation is not just about students coming to the UK, [there is] a correlation between outward mobility and improved academic and employment outcomes” (p.12). In a similar way, the educator responses in this research defined internationalisation in HEIs as a process that aims to facilitate mobility, including mobility of students and staff.

Responses included internationalisation can be defined as

‘Exchanges with foreigners and working on projects with researchers abroad’
(Japanese questionnaire respondent 11)

‘Coming together and exchanging ideas with educators from abroad’ (Japanese questionnaire respondent 19)

'To understand the culture, education, and welfare of others through mutual exchanges' (Japanese questionnaire respondent 4)

'Providing opportunities for staff and students to learn from relevant experiences in other countries' (Scottish questionnaire respondent 11)

'Engagement with people and organisations from other nations on multiple levels, professional, collaborative, organisational, personal' (Scottish questionnaire respondent 6)

'Increasing the number and breadth of the student body which travels to study in the UK or who are taught by a UK university in their own country' (Scottish questionnaire respondent 5)

And

'Exchanging student and staff visits' (Scottish questionnaire respondent 19)

One commonality between educators in this study was their distinct reference to student mobility as a way of explaining their understanding of internationalisation. This is unsurprising as an increasing number of institutions compete to attract mobile, international students and create offshore satellite campuses or offer online courses in order to do so (OECD, 2018).

The responses to the semi-structured interviews questions revealed an emphasis on mobility of international students as the main example and indicator of internationalisation in each HEI.

Responses supporting this included

'Providing Scottish students the opportunity to study part of their programme in another country' (Scottish questionnaire respondent 19)

And

‘Supporting international learners either on campus or by distance learning’ (Scottish questionnaire respondent 41).

Despite the intake of international students being predominantly perceived in a negative sense due to comments from interviewees including ‘limited capacity’ and ‘systems not fit for that population’, it was also acknowledged as financially beneficial to the HEI. Including

“Internationalisation seems to be mostly about profit-making through tapping into markets outside Australia to run programs badged by our university” (Australian questionnaire respondent 1).

These findings support previous research as overall international student enrolments increased in Scotland in 2013-2014 (Higher Education Statistics Agency, 2015). “In Scotland, international postgraduate students play an important role in sustaining the sector; making up more than a third of the post-graduate student population” (Weedon and Kong, 2015, p.114). However, a challenge for universities in Scotland is the declining number of predicted Scottish students until 2023. The need for students from national or international areas is necessary and may prove to be difficult (Tindal et al., 2014).

Komotar (2018) suggests that the quality of internationalisation could be improved through mobility. Hence, several attempts to increase international student numbers in Japanese HEIs have been evidenced via the MEXT Basic Plan and JET Programmes. It is not surprising that a significant number of educators from this study in Japan define and understand internationalisation to be solely associated with international student and staff exchange. An example includes:

‘Internationalisation is the process of improving and changing the function of universities through exchanges of students and teachers with those abroad, so that we can make our education and researchers better’ (Japanese questionnaire respondent 2)

Contrary to Komotar’s (2018) suggestion of quality improvement through mobility, Stier (2002) and Schuerholz-Lehr et al. (2007) posit that when internationalisation in higher education focuses predominantly on student and faculty mobility, other aspects are largely left behind. One aspect that may be considered left behind is the necessary support required for international students.

International students require support. The findings from this research show that educators are eager to provide support to international students, yet the resources are not in place for them to do so, or their efforts are not in alignment with supporting international students on a larger, institutional scale. It is an additional challenge for educators to support international students, particularly when international students encounter various difficulties when they step out of their ‘cultural comfort zone’ (Kingston and Forland, 2008, p.211) and require assistance when adjusting to their new HEI environment.

Academic Rationale: Infuse the Curriculum with International Perspectives

This study found that educators defined and understood internationalisation in HEIs to be a process. One element of this process is to infuse the curriculum with international perspectives. The emphasis placed on infusing the curriculum with international perspectives varied between educators within Schools of Education and between HEIs. Ways in which infusing the curriculum with international perspectives varied included emphasis on internationalisation of the curriculum and assessment or

curriculum being localised and having to fit into a nation, state or government agenda. Examples such as comparing educational policy and practice in several countries to inviting guest speakers were included in the responses.

Specifically, the responses included that internationalisation can be defined as:

'International approaches, e.g. examining curricula, culture and pedagogy across international settings' (Scottish questionnaire respondent 14)

'A process of bringing international perspectives to teaching and learning, making programmes appropriate for international students and providing opportunities for staff and students to learn from relevant experiences in other countries' (Scottish questionnaire respondent 11)

A further commonality between responses from educators from the Australian and Scottish HEI was that many defined internationalisation in terms of teaching, learning and the curriculum. For example

"Internationalisation in the school of education would be in the curriculum, making sure that our students know what international education actually is and what we can learn from other education systems" (S4).

Teaching, learning and the curriculum did not feature in the definitions provided by the educators in the Japanese HEI in the responses to the open ended question. An explanation for this finding could be that internationalisation in higher education includes a broad range of experiences. The experiences can be within the curriculum or beyond the curriculum (Jones and de Wit, 2012, Leask and Bridge, 2013).

Internationalisation of the Curriculum in Higher Education

The broad range of experiences within and beyond the curriculum are the responsibility of the HEI according to Leask and Bridge (2013) who notes that the experiences should “begin at the institutional level followed by the local, national and regional, and concluding at the global level” (Leask, 2013, p. 84). One key aspect relating to infusing the curriculum with international perspectives included internationalisation of the curriculum (IoC). Leask (2009) defines internationalisation of the curriculum (IoC) as “the incorporation of an international and intercultural dimension into the content of the curriculum as well as the teaching and learning processes and support services of a program of study” (p.209). An additional perception provided by Komotar (2018) is that internationalised curriculum and the creation of “so called international learning outcomes” (p.9) includes training courses and workshops for higher education teachers.

Although the focus and aim of internationalisation of the curriculum (IoC) has changed over time in HE, participants from this study identified its importance by stating internationalisation is

‘Ensuring that the curriculum has global citizenship at its core’ (Scottish questionnaire respondent 19)

And

‘The incorporation of global perspectives and learning experiences into the teaching, learning and assessment of students’ learning’ (Scottish questionnaire respondent 47)

Participants also provided examples of ways in which they incorporate an international and intercultural dimension into their teaching and learning such as promotion of languages and inclusion of international case studies.

Responses from participants of this study also suggested that as an educator they understood the importance of supporting opportunities for staff and students to engage and to learn from international colleagues, promoting international settings as well as developing students' international and intercultural perspectives (Ayuninjam, 2018). This is also similar to the viewpoint of Leask (2015) who posits that an internationalised curriculum, is one which helps students develop “graduate capabilities, global citizenship and intercultural competency” (p.53).

A further aspect of infusing the curriculum with international perspectives raised amongst educators in this study was increase in intercultural awareness. The development of intercultural awareness is one aspect of Internationalisation at Home (IaH) which aims to support students who remain at home throughout their higher education study to develop skills in intercultural awareness and global citizenship (Knight, 2014; Sanderson, 2011). The findings of this study highlighted that IaH has a strong focus on all students and is a way to reduce the misconception that mobility and internationalisation are synonymous (Beelen, 2014).

The findings of this present study support those of the Higher Education Academy (HEA) goal that internationalised curricula should prepare “21st century graduates to live in and contribute responsibly to a globally interconnected society” whilst “promoting a high quality, equitable and global learning experience for all students studying UK HE programmes, irrespective of their geographical location or background” (HEA, 2014, p.1).

Intercultural awareness is referred to further in the following section.

Cultural and Social Rationale

According to the educators who participated in this study, one way to define internationalisation is as a process aiming to promote intercultural awareness and global citizenship. Specific examples include

[Internationalisation refers to] *'the ways the university includes people and resources from countries other than its own. And the ways a university represents and engages itself in contexts outside its own country.'* (Australian questionnaire respondent 2)

[Internationalisation is about] *'the building of effective relationships between one culture or nation and another'* (Australian questionnaire respondent 9)

'Internationalisation is the planned integration of an international, intercultural, or global dimension into the mission and practice of a HEI' (Australian questionnaire respondent 14)

And

'Universities have an obligation to treat all cultures with dignity and respect. Internationalisation is the process through which Universities assume a global role in building understanding of diversity' (Australian questionnaire respondent 15)

Findings from this research indicate that there are links between cultural and social objectives and the goals of internationalisation within a HEI. Aspects of the social and cultural rationale highlighted in the findings include: raising cultural awareness, promoting global citizenship and ensuring research is ethical, all aspects that are similar to Aigner et al. (1992) who note that striving towards fostering of human understanding across nations is a reason for internationalisation in higher education (Aigner et al., 1992).

One of the four rationale's of Knight's (1997) conceptual framework for internationalisation is cultural and social rationale. The cultural and social rationale is one way to understand the reasons behind an HEI striving towards internationalisation. Knight (1997) suggests that "the acknowledgement of cultural and ethnic diversity within and between countries is considered as a strong rationale for the internationalisation of a nation's education system" (p.11).

Cultural and Social Rationale: Intercultural Awareness and Global Citizenship

The research participants of this study associated internationalisation with opportunities for staff and students to become more aware of international issues and to develop their understanding of other cultures and education systems. Some of the educators defined internationalisation with reference to inter-cultural understanding and sensitivity and several respondents perceived internationalisation as a process of promoting global citizenship.

[Internationalisation means] *'wishing to understand different cultures and to accept the differences instead of excluding them mentally. Also showing interest in other countries and being able to accept them positively'* (Japanese questionnaire respondent 3)

Participant A1 defined internationalisation as being an *"exchange between cultures and between their communities in Australia and elsewhere in the world"* and as a process aiming to promote intercultural awareness and continued to share that internationalisation is also

"Understanding of diversity and being culturally sensitive, culturally aware and I think the idea of providing international experiences or having international

viewpoints represented on whatever level it is a way to open that conversation [about inter-cultural awareness] or at least recognize its significance” (A1).

In addition, a commonality between responses from the Australian and Japanese HEI was the reference to internationalisation as a ‘peaceful process’.

Also identified in the findings is that intercultural understanding is required (for staff and students) and could be supported further which is in alignment with Yemini’s (2015) definition of internationalisation as a “process of encouraging integration of multicultural, multilingual, and global dimension within the education system, with the aim of instilling a learner’s a sense of global citizenship” (p.21).

According to the literature, internationalisation is a concept that is rich and complex, yet “the key element in the term is the notion of between or among nations and cultural identities” (Qiang, 2003, p.249). Therefore, “national identity and culture are key to internationalisation of higher education” (Qiang, 2003, p.249). Supporting the national and culture identity of stakeholders within a HEI is echoed by Coelen (2016) who defines internationalisation of higher education as the “provision of an environment containing such elements that a learner is given the opportunity to attain achieved learning outcomes associated with international awareness and intercultural competence” (p.40).

Developing intercultural awareness for all students, whether international or home students was one aspect of internationalisation identified by the participants of this research. Specific examples provided by the educators included introducing home and international student buddy schemes and improved opportunities to learn about cultures. It was acknowledged that increasing intercultural awareness is necessary, yet a significant challenge faced by educators. Similar to the literature,

“internationalisation, particularly intercultural skills development, is a complex and challenging agenda for contemporary higher education institutions” (Mak and Kennedy, 2012).

Economic Rationale

The most dominant argument for internationalisation in HEIs is that of economic rationale. An economic rationale of internationalisation of a HEI is maintaining economic competitiveness (Aigner et al., 1992; Knight and De Wit, 1995; Scott, 1992) and to support a nation’s economic competitiveness (Johnston and Edelstein, 1993). The economic rationale refers to long-term economic gains and is linked to international competitiveness. The significance of the economic rationale was evidenced when educators shared examples of the benefits of international students but also the potential problems including how policy makers viewed international students purely as an economic commodity.

Economic Rationale: Financial Gain

Internationalisation was often defined or understood by educators in this research as a commodity and related directly to financial gain. Throughout the research findings financial gain was often mentioned by the educators in a negative way and expressed with disappointment. An explanation for their disappointment was due to their disapproval of such practices which they thought to be at times unethical.

For example, one the interviewees from the Australian HEI defined internationalisation as a profit making endeavour noting

“I think the master's course is more of a cash cow thing because there is no government sponsored subsidies or anything for masters’ courses and those are

actually worth a lot of money to the university. We are feeding into a consumerist view of internationalisation” (A1).

Similarly, two of the interviewees from the Scottish HEI defined internationalisation as a profit-motivated activity

“One has to understand that a big part of it [internationalisation] is to bring money into the university’. (S4).

“Internationalisation means bringing in international students for the money” (S2)

He continued to share in a negative tone that

“All I ever hear coming from [the Dean of Internationalisation] is about international students, bringing in international students and going on international business” (S2)

The views of the educators in this study are similar to McKinley and Rose (2018) who suggest that “internationalisation is viewed at its worst as an economic ploy to drum up student numbers and tuition and at its best as a way to positively influence universities’ outlook” (p.113).

It has been suggested that the idea that the university sector is becoming corporatised is not a new one. Mitchell (1999) described this belief of “commodification of education as a product” (p.387) whereby teaching and learning is treated more as a commodity than a process (Castree and Sparke, 2000). Several authors support this view, with Slaughter and Rhoades (2009) arguing that education is no longer a public good, rather an “academic capitalist one that blurs boundaries between markets, states and higher education” (Hurt, 2012, p.121). This is evidenced by the fact that according to the World Economic Forum (Schwab, 2015) the Higher Education sector has experienced rapid growth.

Financial benefits have been a key influencer relating to why internationalisation takes place in a HEI. Yesufu (2018) posits that universities are more focused on attracting additional income rather than on the generation of knowledge. According to the findings from educators in this present study, finance may similarly continue to be a driver of internationalisation.

As noted by McKinley and Rose (2018), recent trends for HEIs in native English-speaking nations has been to “tap into the international market as a means to increase funds flowing to the university and to offset lower domestic tuition or a dwindling lack of public funds” (p. 113).

Researchers have highlighted that HEIs are increasingly viewed as commercial ventures and internationalisation is a source of funding and income for such institutions (Altbach, 2015; Tilak, 2015). Findings from this research show that internationalisation is often highly associated to financial income. Similarly, Yesufu’s (2018) case study of a Canadian University presented findings that internationalisation in the University was motivated by economic reasons. Furthermore, financial income and benefit was rated highest by participants in this particular Canadian case study (Yesufu, 2018).

Contrary to other research, a comparative study of Slovenian and Dutch experiences of internationalisation and quality assurance of higher education found that interviewees suggested internationalisation is not guided by economic, market-oriented rationales but academic, quality related goals (Komotar, 2018, p.442) and that if internationalisation is predominantly driven by economic rationales the quality of HE cannot be improved by internationalisation (Komotar, 2018). Therefore, despite the negativity demonstrated in the findings of this present research around

internationalisation as being a ‘cash cow’, internationalisation is sometimes used to help improve the public perception of the university (Yesufu, 2018) which is not unreasonable when institutions are forever marketing themselves in a competitive global market (Christou and Fragouli, 2018). Knight (2004) noted that internationalisation has become one of the main objectives of many higher education institutions who are interested in enhancing their quality, learning and diversity. Frolich (2006) has also argued that reasons to internationalise a HEI can be based upon the academic gain rather than financial gain as the top priority. This was the finding of Frolich’s (2006) case study of Norwegian institutions (three HEIs, two University Colleges and one research institute) and noted that an economic justification of policies and practices is not the major reason to internationalise because academic rationales for internationalisation are currently deeply embedded.

Boundaries are blurred between markets, states and higher education (Hurt, 2012). Such a finding aligns with participant comments in this present study as the educators have suggested that internationalisation is directly linked to neo-colonialism, that internationalisation is purely conceptual as well as that internationalisation creates further inequalities amongst student experiences and accessibility to educational experiences.

Economic Rationale: International Students in Relation to Financial Gain

The “big business” (Altbach and Knight, 2007, p. 291) of education has included the increasing export of higher education. Recruitment of foreign students has been a significant factor for institutional income for over decades (Qiang, 2003). This is no surprise as the number of globally mobile students has expanded to around 4.5 million in 2015 (OECD, 2015). Recruiting international students to UK institutions, continues

to be part of a global trend (Riddell et al., 2015) and Australia, Canada, England and the USA are the top four majority English-speaking host nations for international students (Ortiz et al. 2015).

Making reference to international students was a popular way of defining internationalisation by participants of this study. The experiences of the educators included international students being referred to in terms of the financial gain associated with international students. According to the research participants of this study, international students were deemed a determining factor of internationalisation and a driving force of internationalisation within a HEI although reference was often very critical. The educators in this research rightly acknowledged the link between international students and financial gain and at times its negativity, as according to the literature, a “commercial approach to internationalization has attracted criticism in terms of how universities view their international students” (McKinley and Rose, 2018, p.113).

Several of the interviewees referred to a link between finance and internationalisation of HEIs in some form throughout their semi-structured interview. The majority of participants spoke about finance in regards to internationalisation being a form of income generation purely based on international students, albeit in a negative and critical way. Overall, most educators aligned finance with international students, how much revenue they create and the benefits an HEI gains. However, only a couple (A3 and S2) did not demonstrate negativity towards internationalisation in regards to monetary gains. In fact, A3 referred to how the process of exchange students from Australia to Timor East would financially benefit the communities in the education program. Meanwhile, Japanese interviews only raised the issue of money allocated to HEIs from the government and distributed to the HEI to their individual courses.

To some extent, the findings of this research are in line with the current literature as hosting international (mobile) students is an important source of income for the countries involved. International students pay higher tuition fees than home students and they also contribute to the local economy through spending and living expenses (OECD, 2018) and “it is clear that the financial solvency of UK universities is increasingly based on their ability to recruit international students” (Weedon and Kong, 2015, p.121). Similar to the UK, international education is an important source of income for Australia indeed it is Australia’s largest services export and its fourth largest export overall after iron ore, coal and natural gas (Dodd, 2016). In Australia, export revenue from international students, soared 13 per cent in 2015 to make education a \$20 billion export industry (Dodd, 2016). International students in the higher education sector generated \$11.7 billion in export income, while students in the vocational education and training sector produced \$2.7 billion (Australian Government, 2015).

To sum up, the rationales for HEIs aiming to internationalise can vary and change over time. Whilst some “universities retain a narrow definition of internationalisation, others have developed a broader view” (Warwick, 2013, p.97). The way in which an educator defines or understands internationalisation can also vary.

Summary of Research Question One

There continues to be uncertainty as to how internationalisation is defined in Higher Education Institutions (Robson, Almeida and Schartner, 2017). The findings of this study confirm that, according to educators in HEIs, internationalisation is a nebulous and ubiquitous concept. However, a commonality between the findings of this research and previous research is that internationalisation is considered a process and

an outcome for HEIs (Ryall, 2013). Key concepts in Knight's (2004; 2015) definition of internationalisation include internationalisation is a dynamic process, not isolated activities. The definition is focussed on the functions taking place within a HEI. As discovered from this research, internationalisation is a process attempting to

- Facilitate Staff and Student Mobility
- Infuse the Curriculum with International Perspectives
- Promote Intercultural Awareness and Global Citizenship
- Generate Financial Gain

Furthermore, internationalisation of HE in this thesis is defined as a systematic approach to integrate an international dimension across all aspects of academic and social life in HE, with a view to preparing students to live and work effectively as global citizens in an internationalised world.

According to the findings of this present study, the reasons why a HEI aims for internationalisation are often linked to its rationale of internationalisation. The findings of this research, to an extent, align with Knight's (1997, 1999) framework of rationales of internationalisation. It was determined that several rationales can exist within an HEI, and therefore, in turn, several definitions and understandings of educators in HEIs can exist too.

Several rationales exist for internationalisation in Higher Education Institutions as policy makers aim to internationalise their institutions for economic, political, academic and socio-cultural reasons (de Wit 2002; Hudzik, 2011). Yet, as evidenced in both the findings of this research and the literature, the economic rationale is overarching in terms of internationalisation of Higher Education Institutions and this has an impact on educators.

Leask (2003) claims that internationalisation is critical to the success of a HEI and therefore, the processes as to how internationalisation is achieved must be considered wisely. This is particularly true of the educators in this study who noted that internationalisation in HEI covers a number of different agendas.

The following section aims to relate the educator's experience in HEIs of this present study to the current, relevant literature.

RQ2 - What are the educators' experiences of internationalisation in their Higher Education Institutions?

According to the findings of this study, more educators than not encounter internationalisation as part of their role in their HEI. The responses varied within and across the three institutions: whilst over half of the educators agreed that internationalisation was encountered in their role, there were many who did not agree with this statement (28% Japan, 44% Scotland and 50% Australia) suggesting variability in the experiences of internationalisation within each institution.

The findings of this research highlighted that educators in HE experience internationalisation in several ways. For some of the educators, experiences of internationalisation have been positive and beneficial to them as educators. For others, experiences of internationalisation have been negative and fraught with challenges and barriers.

In the following section, the answers to Research Question Two and links to relevant literature will be presented using the following subheadings:

1. Educators' Personal Encounters with Internationalisation
2. Educators' Experiences of Professional Development and Support
3. Educators' Experiences of Challenges and Barriers
4. Educators' Contribution to the Development of Internationalisation

1. Educators' Personal Encounters with Internationalisation

The findings from the research demonstrated that educators encountered internationalisation in relation to academic and support activities. There were

commonalities in the examples that educators provided in terms of academic and support activities and at times they were context specific. The ways in which educators encountered internationalisation via academic and support activities can be explained with reference to relevant literature.

Academic activities in which educators engaged as part of their role included internationalisation in the classroom, preparing home students for work beyond their local context, developing the English language proficiency of international students, teaching international students in the home campus or in the students' own country, and supervising international PhD students.

An interviewee from the Australian HEI spoke of encounters with internationalisation in class but in this case the insights are provided by international students rather than home students who have been on visit or placement abroad:

“I have in that degree a number of international students. Some from Africa, some from India and elsewhere [...] and it's been really great having them in the classroom. We are looking at development in the world, and so to have these guys in the classroom sharing their experiences [...] more often than not they are from developing countries [...] sharing their first-hand experience brings I think that internationalisation aspect into the classroom” (A3).

Specifically, the fourth interviewee from the Australian HEI spoke about experiences from PhD supervision of international students and the academic activity involved.

“I had several international PhD students over a period of time [...] I had at least four or five PhD students and I think that, from a personal perspective, this begins to force you to think about where they come from, what their educational background is, how they have been trained [...] when you work with Chinese, particularly Chinese

students they have a strong Confucius heritage background, they don't like to challenge so I discovered personally that I had to teach them how to, you know, challenge, the literature and that it was ok to challenge me."

Supporting students is a key aspect for educators in this study in terms of academic activities which is similar to Sanderson's (2008) findings that educators strive to provide a teaching and learning experience that is relevant and "extends beyond local and national perspectives" (Sanderson, 2008, p.277).

Support activities that educators in this study are involved in included the admission of international students into programmes and also being part of a recruitment team for international students. The findings from this research also show that educators, on the whole, support and encourage international students and view this support as part of their role.

An interviewee spoke of her involvement in organising internships abroad for students as part of two degrees, preparing the students for these internships, and visiting some of them when they are there to monitor their experience and progress:

"I prepare them for this international experience, which is a whole semester long, I prepare them culturally and I prepare them logistically for their trip, you know emotionally all that stuff. [...] I also take part in a monitoring exercise. So I have to visit students on internships abroad. And I visited a group of students every year for the past three years. [...] And that's a monitoring exercise" (A3).

Another interviewee from the Australian HEI spoke about the administration of the Colombo Plan grand schemes, the purpose of which is to support Australian undergraduate students to undertake study and internships in the Indo-Pacific region:

“there are a number of people at the faculty level who do those applications, and they promote operations for others to try and access that funding, and at the school of education level we've been successful on a number of occasions” (A1).

Examples of how educators in this study provided support included guiding and mentoring international students with respect and dignity, demonstrating the value of intercultural competence. A participant highlighted the importance of intercultural competence in building and sustaining positive international relationships by stating

“We need to understand culturally where they're coming from, because there are so many cues and things that can be misconstrued or taken the wrong way because we have slightly different customs. (S1)

This is in congruence with Whannell and Whannell's (2015) findings that highlight universities and lecturers should work in partnership with students to help them overcome the difficulties and challenges of being an international student. By doing so, students are enthusiastic about internationalisation (Jackson, Robson and Huddart, 2012).

Academic and support activities encountered by educators relating to internationalisation are varied and not without pressure and increased workload. Pressure is experienced by the educator who feels the intrinsic need to support and care for the international students which may be perceived as above and beyond their regular workload. Furthermore, reliance on the good will of staff was prevalent. This finding supports other studies such as Hanson and McNeil (2012) who noted that faculty members “demonstrated a personal commitment to the practice of internationalisation [via their respective curricula], whilst managing increasingly heavy academic workloads” (Hanson and McNeil, 2012, p.34). As well as Robson and

Turner (2007) who also noted that staff were generally supportive of the university's internationalisation strategy however they had some concerns about the practicalities of implementation as participants thought internationalisation to be time consuming and potentially damaging their individual research careers.

2. Educators' Experiences of Professional Development and Support

The educators in this study were asked about their experiences of professional development and support to perform activities relating to internationalisation as part of their role. The responses indicated a high level of dissatisfaction from the educators towards their HEI in regards to its investment in educating their staff about internationalisation.

Educators were asked how satisfied they were with the investment their HEI makes in terms of training and education specifically for internationalisation. There was variability in the responses from each HEI, particularly in Japan and Scotland. This variability suggested that individual educators within the same institution can have very different experiences of support and professional development in relation to internationalisation.

One reason for the variability suggested by educators within the same HEI may be that there are differences in the actual opportunities available to these educators for example, faculty specific professional development courses relating to internationalisation. The findings from this study also suggest that support and professional development regarding internationalisation may be unequally distributed or available to educators in whatever country they work. Another reason for the variability may be differences in the educators' perceptions of what constitutes support and professional development and in their expectations.

The dissatisfaction of educators in this present study is contrary to the findings of a study involving educators in Slovenian universities. Svetlik and Lalic (2015) found that educators highly valued their involvement in international activities and that internationalisation significantly contributed to their professional development, measured in terms of career promotion.

The majority of comments from educators in this study, in relation to professional development, indicated limited or no professional development and support for internationalisation, and highlighted lack of professional development as a barrier to the educators' effective engagement with internationalisation. Such comments are similar to Yesufu's (2018) findings regarding staff development in Canadian HEIs in the sense that targets are set by the institution in regards to internationalisation despite the fact that "staff training is focused on activities related to international partnerships and not professional development training" (p.162).

3. Educators' Experiences of Challenges and Barriers

Findings from this study identified that there are several challenges and barriers faced by educators in HEIs when experiencing internationalisation. Significant challenges arise due to the fact that the role of the educator in HE is ever changing and impacted upon (Tran & Nguyen, 2015). Examples of how the educator faces challenges and barriers include: lack of clarity and disconnect, logistical constraints, context specific nature of teacher education, and ethical issues.

Challenges and Barriers: Lack of Clarity and Disconnect

Knight (2004) remarks that internationalisation may result in unintended and negative consequences and there is a need to consider such implications. A negative

consequence and particular challenge faced by educators, identified from the findings this study, is disconnect between the educator and the policy maker which leads to disconnect between policy and practice in regards to internationalisation.

One of the interviewees from the Australian HEI commented

“There’s rhetoric around and it's pervasive across the university sector where everybody's got to continue to keep working hard. You've got to be seen to do more, work harder so that you can be seen to work harder. You've got to be seen to be more efficient. All of these things are constantly draining on everybody's ideas, and I think internationalisation is one more thing [...] a way for somebody higher up to say oh you're not performing, even though it's nebulous [...] kind of what is that and what are your goals really? But then if there are no ways to measure it I mean if it's a nebulous concept then you can't do it wrong but you certainly can't do it right either”
(A1).

Another of the interviewee from the Australian HEI pointed out that

“whoever is thinking about internationalisation at the top level, they don't think about how it needs to be implemented or giving everybody a chance to understand the concept in the same way or work out what does this mean in our context and it's almost like one size fits all and therefore it feels like they say: we expect certain things but we're not going to tell you what those are” (A3).

The educators who participated in this research experienced situations in which they felt that knowledge, or information regarding internationalisation, was not communicated effectively from policy makers within the HEI. The policy makers they referred to included Directors of Internationalisation and others who are involved in the creation of internationalisation policy and dissemination of the policy. The

educators at times felt unsure as to how to implement their HEI's internationalisation policy or achieve internationalisation goals successfully in their role. A disconnect between what is expected and what is achieved by the educator in regard to internationalisation in their HEI seemed to be a challenge for many of the participants of this study. This finding supports the point made by De Haan (2014) that there is a need to help universities reduce the 'implementation gap' between internationalisation plans and actual outcomes. One solution to reducing the gap and ensuring success is to make certain the educator understands the [internationalisation] strategy and has an adequate connection to the vision (Alashoo et al., 2005). By doing so, it may reduce the pressures placed upon educators from policy makers and line managers which was evidenced in the findings of this research.

Challenges and Barriers: Logistical Constraints

The educators who participated in this study identified logistical constraints as a persistent obstacle to their engagement with internationalisation in their HEIs. A fair number of participants referred to specific logistical constraints such as lack of time, support and resources.

“Our university has international projects, but there exists no systematic tactics. Few resources are provided, and the faculty are not motivated or committed. Compared to other universities I have formerly worked for we are far behind.” (Japanese questionnaire respondent 7, 1/5 = *Strongly Disagree on Likert Scale*)

“I don't think I can expect any support from (the) university.” (Japanese questionnaire respondent 21, 2/5 = *Disagree on Likert Scale*)

“I understand it is an important issue, but I have little time to cope with internationalisation. Besides it's not my top priority.” (Japanese questionnaire respondent 13, 2/5)

“This HEI is active for developing internationalisation. But its organization is very bureaucratic so the activities are not so effective.” (Japanese questionnaire respondent 23, 2/5)

“We're conscious of the necessity of internationalisation, but actual situation is not favourable due to lack of support on the ground” (Japanese questionnaire respondent 3, 2/5)

And

“Not enough time to give a lot of focus” (Scottish questionnaire respondent 11, 2/5)

The same interviewee spoke of systemic issues that act as barriers to effective internationalisation in his HEI

“I do not believe that our systems are geared up to support these [international] students when they do come. I think personally if we want an international cohort of students, the students experience is key, it's of prime importance and it's not being given due consideration [...] Our systems are just not fit for that population [international students]. We're not as developed as we could be and when I say that what I mean is that it just seems that our systems are clunky” (S1).

The lack of time given to educators to successfully follow through with the process of internationalisation was a significant challenge experienced by educators in this research and resulted in them experiencing increased stress. This finding supports that of Bedenlier and Zawacki-Richter (2015) who claim that increased workload resulting

from the individuals' international engagement leads to feelings of stress on the individual level.

Challenges and Barriers: Context Specific Nature of Teacher Education

The potential incompatibility between internationalisation and the context specific nature of teacher education was highlighted by several educators in this study.

An interviewee from the Australian HEI commented

“I'm in teacher education. And teacher education traditionally in the universities doesn't really have internationalisation as such because we train teachers very much for the jurisdiction that we're in. That means all the teacher education programs have to deal with those contexts and we find that international students don't necessarily come into those programs. We don't attract them. International students might go into business or other courses and I found out that consistently over the years, although you always get one or two and they are usually interesting characters who don't mind that the qualification they get to teach in the classroom may not work in their own jurisdiction or country” (A3).

This was echoed by another interviewee from the same institution who said

“In my experience, in education, internationalisation was talked about but never really put into practice because we were, and still are, so governed by the New South Wales curriculum and the accreditation process, so other than the experience of taking our students overseas, to do practicum and so on, there is not much scope for internationalisation” (A4).

The tension between the context specific nature of teacher education and the internationalisation agenda of the HEI was identified as a challenge for educators in

this present study. Furthermore, the challenge included aims of the HEI to internationalise the curriculum not being met because the content taught is predominately specific to the state's or country's education system.

A Scottish interviewee shared

“I think internationalization in the School of Education would be making sure that our students know what international education in the curriculum actually is, for you to make them efficient teachers. Because that is an important part of this Scottish Government Agenda, the Curriculum for Excellence” (S4).

This finding and others supports that of Larsen (2016) who identified that there is complexity in understanding the many different forms of internationalisation in twenty-first century teacher education institutions due to the influential factors of both global and local contexts.

Challenges and Barriers: Ethical Issues

A challenge of internationalisation experienced by educators in this study and in previous studies, were the ethical implications of internationalisation (Hoey, 2016). At times educators referred to the social, cultural and values-driven goals of internationalisation (Pashby, 2015). It was noted by educators in this study that goals of internationalisation are at times unethical and perhaps not the standard expected of the OECD (2018). The OECD expect that institution-wide ethical commitment occurs when actions, values, methods and principles lead to equitable access to good quality education and professional treatment of staff (OECD, 2018).

An ethical issue raised by interviewees from the Australian HEI concerned what this interviewee perceived as limited opportunities for outward mobility for home students who do not have the money required to finance such experiences

“Not that many students take up that opportunity, I mean those who are well funded do, but those who have limited access to resources can't or don't have the resources to do that and in the school of education, that's probably half of our students. Well, maybe 40% of our students are part-time students and they are studying part time because they're working full time. So, they have family commitments and job responsibilities that may preclude them from entering this dialogue or this possibility of participating in these kinds of international experiences. [...] So it doesn't seem to enable those who have limited resources to actually take advantage of it. So, while there is this range of opportunities, it doesn't seem to be taken up by those who possibly could benefit most from it or wouldn't otherwise have the opportunity. So it's certainly not an egalitarian notion” (A1).

Another ethical issue was raised by one of the interviewees from the Scottish HEI who commented on what the educator is required to do in regards to the monitoring of international students with Tier 4 visas

“You've also got to take into account the border agency's requirement for attendance monitoring [...] And this is a particular issue that I have. I've got students who are from overseas and every time they come to my class I've got to sign their UKVI attendance card. And for me, I think that type of labelling is an issue and I had to do that for my PhD student as well. We had to make sure that we had at least one meeting a month so that we could sign the UKVI attendance card. I understand that's a legal requirement that we just have to get on with it but come on, it is a barrier” (S1).

4. Educators' Contribution to the Development of Internationalisation

The educators in this study identified differing levels of experience in terms of contribution to the development of internationalisation in their HEI context. Similarly, Li and Tu (2015) investigated factors that drive educators to get involved in internationalisation in higher education. The study of educators in China determined that there are individual and environmental motivations for educators to be involved in internationalisation in their HEI context. Individual factors referred to intrinsic motivation including support career progression whereas environmental motivations linked to rewards structures and material support in terms of international student recruitment. The study (Li and Tu, 2015) highlighted “the relationship between the two factors and faculty engagement in internationalisation underpins the significance of making an effort to meet faculty’s individual willingness and to establish good institute environmental contexts to promote international involvement” (Li and Tu, 2015, p.93.)

The involvement of educators in internationalisation is important because faculty [members] can lead internationalisation, in fact, be drivers for successful internationalisation (Turner and Robson, 2017). This is also noted by Stohl (2007) who posits that “if a university wants to be internationalised they must internationalise the faculty” (p.367).

Faculty participation is crucial to the success of internationalisation in HE and developing a “critical mass of faculty supporters’ can enable an international dimension to be infused into an institution’s ethos and activities” (Childress, 2010, p.16) because it has been acknowledged that educators have authority over the focus of their curriculum and research. Furthermore, Robson et al. (2017) and Hoey (2016)

recommend a faculty member bottom-up approach that is participant driven, as a way to have educators more involved in the process and development of internationalisation.

However, findings from this research indicated that most educators were not involved in the creation of internationalisation policies and procedures at their HEI. Furthermore, only a few of the respondents had significant input in the review of internationalisation policies and procedures in any of the HEIs.

The interviewees from the Scottish HEI spoke of limited opportunities and tokenistic involvement

“I'm not entirely convinced that the internationalisation policies that we have are informed by our experiences as staff members. I'm not convinced that our voices are heard because they [senior leadership team] are more interested in how to operationalize this thing [internationalisation], not in the actual thing. Nobody would argue against the policy of increasing internationalisation in terms of global outlook, broadened perspectives, understanding of education beyond national borders [...] we all buy into the values that underpin that, but the systems aren't there to support the practice and there's another underlying tension as well: the expense that the university incurs in pursuit of international student recruitment is disproportionate in relation to potential gains” (S1).

This was echoed by another one of the interviewees from the Scottish HEI:

“It's all top-down, top-down. Very rarely, if at all, do we get the opportunity to engage in consultation about internationalisation that actually has any meaningful impact on policy [...] We are involved on the surface [...] We were invited to contribute to the global strategy, the next iteration of the global engagement plan, within a school

meeting. But, that's an enlarged group, where maybe we have half an hour to contribute to that so there is no real opportunity for debate and meaningful involvement” (S3).

The findings from this study indicate that educators could be more involved in the development of internationalisation policy as widespread faculty engagement and planning are critical to internationalisation (Childress, 2010; Harari, 1989; Knight, 1993).

Approaches to internationalisation

There are several ways that a HEI may approach internationalisation. Sometimes, the approach is based upon the way the leaders in HE prefer to promote or implement internationalisation (De Wit, 1995; Knight, 1994). The four approaches to internationalisation in HEIs suggested by Knight (1994) and de Wit (1995) include Activity, Competency, Ethos and Process approaches. Such approaches could be considered to have an explicit link to the challenges and barriers faced by educators when experiencing internationalisation in their HEI.

The *activity approach* to internationalisation in HEIs relates to certain activities including student and staff exchange, activities that attract and include international students, and an international curriculum. The activity approach has been a popular approach for HEIs as it could be considered that an array of activities equals successful internationalisation (Qiang, 2003). However, the activity approach could be viewed as a fragmented approach to internationalisation. A possible disadvantage of the activity approach to internationalisation is that although many activities take place, they may not be coordinated and could be viewed as unsustainable. The activities may also lack consistency in approach, questioning the benefits and impacts of the activities.

Findings from this research align with the activity approach to internationalisation and was mentioned often and openly by educators in this study. Participants identified several activities as internationalisation activities including exchange programs, international student activities, language classes and social events. Recommendations from the educators in this present study for the future of international activities were that the activities have clear, aligned goals and that the activities are directly linked to internationalisation policies. Additionally, it was noted by educators from this study that more activities should focus on home students and IaH.

The *competency approach* to internationalisation in HEIs includes a focus on the development of skills in staff and students relating to their values and attitudes towards internationalisation. This involves efforts to develop competencies to ensure that staff and students are more “internationally knowledgeable and interculturally skilled” (Qiang, 2003, p.250). The *competency approach* was referred to in the findings of the research when educators identified that internationalisation is linked to global citizenship, and to being interculturally competent and internationally knowledgeable. The competency approach may be facilitated via internationalised curricula (Qiang, 2003). It was evidenced in the research findings that internationalisation of the curriculum can be one way in which staff and students can be more culturally aware and develop their skills to be successful international citizens despite the challenges and barriers that may be faced in the interim.

An *ethos approach* to internationalisation in a HEI supports events relating to international initiatives that are aligned with the HEI goals and objectives. Qiang (2003) notes that the ethos approach emphasizes creating a culture or climate that values and supports intercultural/international perspectives and initiatives. The ethos approach acknowledges that an international dimension is a fundamental dimension

of an HEI and attempts to ensure ways to promote a culture that supports international perspectives. Findings from this research alluded to the fact that an ethos approach was of some significance because it was noted that there was need for increased intercultural understanding amongst staff and students. Similar to Guo and Chase (2011), “with this approach, the institution’s leaders must be committed to building a culture that embraces multicultural perspectives and the internationalisation of practices and classroom pedagogy” (Guo and Chase, 2011, p.307).

The *process approach* to implementing internationalisation places a strong emphasis on integration of international dimension through combining practice and policies relating to internationalisation. The process approach requires sustainability in order to be successful. In regards to the findings of this research, sustainability was lacking in terms of internationalisation policy and processes according to the participants. The approach was described as adhoc, tokenistic and inconsistent amongst several educators. A process approach may be an approach to be adopted in the future to reduce the challenges and barriers faced by educators when experiencing internationalisation in their HEI context.

There are several approaches to internationalisation that may have an effect on the experience encountered by educators in HEIs. Additionally, there are various ways in which internationalisation is practised and experienced by stakeholders despite sharing the same mission statement (Tadaki and Tremewan, 2013) or in the case of the present study, the same institutional or departmental goals.

Summary of Research Question Two

According to the findings of this study and literature reviewed, internationalisation is experienced by most educators in HEIs. However, the understanding the educator's lived experience of this phenomenon is still questionable despite the investment made by HEIs to be internationalised. Indeed, as suggested by Tran and Nguyen (2015), the role of the educator in regards to internationalisation, is ever changing and impacted upon. Furthermore, as suggested by Warwick and Moogan (2013), the definitions used by HEIs do not necessarily reflect the views or experiences of many university staff. Finally, the approach(es) of a HEI to internationalise (De Wit, 1995; Knight, 1994) could be aligned with the educators' experiences in their HEI context, whether it be an activity, competency, ethos or process approach.

The following section aims to provide suggestions and recommendations for how to improve internationalisation in the future in terms of educator experience and contribution relating to research findings and literature.

RQ3 - What are the educators' views about the future of internationalisation in Higher Education (HE) and their recommendations for improvement?

The findings from this research and others identify that internationalisation will remain a goal for HE in the future and continues to be a priority for HEIs (Galloway and Rose, 2015) possibly because internationalisation in HE is a cyclical and non-linear process (Qiang, 2003, p.249). As internationalisation remains to be an integral part of HE that cannot be avoided (Rider-Grant, 2015) Research Question Three sought to discover how educators envisaged the future of internationalisation in their own HEI context.

As part of this study, educators from Australia, Japan and Scotland were asked to what extent they would appreciate the opportunity to have future involvement in the internationalisation process of their HEI. A sizable number of educators (Australia 55%, Scotland 50% and Japan 40%) indicated that they were interested in having future involvement in the internationalisation process of their HEI and many responded with positive ideas as to how internationalisation in their HEI can be improved or how they envisaged the future of internationalisation of their HEI. They provided examples of how they wish to contribute to internationalisation within their own HEI context. The ideas and suggestions fell into four themes: Student Experience, Vision and Values, Systems and Resources, Context.

The following section will provide answers to Research Question Three. These will be presented using the following subheadings:

1. Student Experience
2. Vision and Values

3. Systems and Resources
4. Context (Geography and Government)

1. Student Experience

A common theme that arose when educators were asked about how internationalisation in their HEI context could be improved was the need to focus on student experience and how to make it better. The educators who participated in this study expressed strong concern about the current level of student experience in terms of internationalisation and a keen desire to enhance it for example providing increased opportunities for students to develop global citizenship skills and authentic cultural learning experiences. Several ways to enhance the student experience were suggested, including increased leadership and improving professional development for all staff involved. Specific reference was made to professional development linked to internationalising the curriculum, supporting home students to enhance their cultural understanding and citizenship skills as well as supporting international students to be fully immersed in their exchange experience. Each will be discussed further in the following sections.

Student Experience: Leadership

Professional development of staff in terms of internationalising the curriculum and improving student experience requires strong leadership in order for them to move beyond the status quo (Mak and Kennedy, 2012). In order to improve the student experience in relation to internationalisation in HE, educators in this study made requests and suggestions for further support from the leaders or policy makers in their HEIs when endeavouring to achieve internationalisation in their current role.

Specifically, they requested more opportunities to learn from experiences in other countries, more funding to allow equity in terms of who can access said experiences and improved activities within the HEI to encourage relationships between home students and international students. This finding supports the work of Li and Tu (2016) who note that leaders of HEIs need to have a greater understanding of the policy and practice and consider how to satisfy individual faculty member's needs. They must also "stimulate their individual motivation and how to transfer the policy and practice of institutes to faculty's individual competence and efficacy" (p.93).

Leaders within HEIs should be actively involved in supporting and promoting Internationalisation at Home (IaH) (EUA, 2013) as well as other internationalisation processes. Findings from this present research identify the need for the leaders in HEIs to support the educators in internationalisation processes and in the delivery of internationalisation in terms of the particular HEI goals.

Student Experience: Professional Development

Participants from this study demonstrated enthusiasm for professional development. Professional development was noted as something they could participate in to improve their understanding and practice of internationalisation. Certain areas of professional development thought to be worthwhile by the educators in this study included internationalising the curriculum and organising student exchanges. The areas of professional development suggested by educators in this study to support them in terms of internationalisation reflect the research of others who have already noted the need for continual professional development of university teachers in regards to internationalising the curriculum effectively (Leask, 2015) and having international

collaboration amongst educators (British Council, 2016; Iuspa, 2010). Specifically, two participants stated

“Internationalisation is also about international conferences [...] in a very broad sense of gaining opportunity to network, meet key individuals in the field, listen to key researchers, advancing their own understanding of their field plus their awareness of what's going on beyond the walls of [this HEI] and possibly Australia” (A2)

‘There should be more opportunities to exchange within the HEI and with research institutions abroad’. (Japanese questionnaire respondent 11)

According to Hudzik (2011) the most important variable in comprehensive internationalisation is the faculty. Therefore, faculty level professional development could be a way to improve curriculum design, assessment tasks, and cultural awareness and skills of educators in terms of internationalisation (Mak and Kennedy, 2012). The findings from the semi-structured interviewees in this present study demonstrated that all educators tried to actively pursue professional development opportunities to support internationalisation in their role whether in an attempt to internationalise curriculum design to promote global citizenship, teaching and supporting international student or collaborating with international researchers and attending international conferences. Findings from this study further highlighted that individual educators are to some extent attempting to implement internationalisation in their role and to some extent are doing so effectively.

Student Experience: Internationalisation of the Curriculum (IoC) and Internationalisation at Home (IaH)

Participants of this study suggested that providing an internationalised curriculum for home students could be a way to improve internationalisation in HE. However,

implementing an internationalised curriculum can be complex and challenging for educators in HE (Leask, 2008). Professional development for staff in terms of curriculum development and how to internationalise their own courses is necessary in the future (Mak and Kennedy, 2012).

Student Experience: Home Students and International Students

Previous research has indicated that internationalisation can be improved through the provision of an internationalised classroom and an international university experience for home students, because it allows students from different cultural backgrounds to work together (Mak and Kennedy, 2012). Findings from this research included several suggestions from educators that home students would benefit from having the opportunity to engage with international students.

“I think that through this [opportunities for students to develop global citizenship] we can really enhance the experience of our international students but also our home students because for many of our students the notion of diversity is very, very limited. So, I think there’s lots, lots that we could do, to enhance their understanding and citizenship skills. I think we should be aiming for that as a key part, a key element of internationalisation” (S3).

By being involved, the home students can improve their cultural awareness and understanding without having to take part in an exchange program themselves. Educators in this study were keen to support this initiative as increased cultural exchange in more diverse communities is a benefit of internationalisation (Knight, 2013).

It has been suggested by educators in this study that more has to be done by HEI policymakers to prepare educators to support international students. It was shared that

enhancing the student experience of internationalisation could be through student mobility.

'I wish there were more opportunities for both undergraduate and graduate students to participate in international exchanges and to learn about foreign language education, history and culture.' (Japanese questionnaire respondent 9)

'I hope to be able to host more exchange students.' (Japanese questionnaire respondent 11)

And

"Make programmes appropriate for international students and providing opportunities for staff and students" (Scottish questionnaire respondent 11).

The recommendations from the educators in this study support the recommendations to the UK Government by Universities UK that the future of internationalisation in Higher Education includes making a "renewed effort to communicate a consistent message that Britain welcomes international students, to promote British universities overseas, build new international partnerships and attract more international students to Britain" (Universities UK, 2014, p.27).

Types of support acknowledged by participants of this study are similar to those noted by Mak and Kennedy (2012) who suggest that "attention to providing cultural support to a rapidly increasing international student body is critical" (p.330). Cultural support is also required for educators. As the findings indicate, attracting international students is not necessarily a positive experience for the educators who take on the responsibility of mentoring or supervising the international students. Therefore, increased support is necessary.

2. Vision and Values

The HEI's vision for internationalisation and the values that should underpin this came up in the qualitative responses of the questionnaire and in the semi-structured interviews as an area for future development that would benefit from educator input. The findings showed that educators should contribute to the development of the vision and values regarding internationalisation. Three areas of focus emerged including: establishing and communicating clear goals and aims, improving understanding of the vision and values, and ensuring educator agency.

Vision and Values: Establishing and Communicating Clear Goals and Aims

Most participants in this study expressed interest in understanding internationalisation better within their HEI context. Suggestions made by the educators to improve understanding of vision and values included increased or improved professional development, clearer policy guidelines and expectations as well as specific targets and goals. This is similar to the findings of Qiang (2003) who notes that the process of internationalisation in HEIs can be implemented through “continuous support and monitoring, recognition and rewards” (p.249).

Findings from this study indicate that educators are aware that policy makers are keen to continue to pursue internationalisation of HEIs. One recurrent theme arising from the interviews was the requirement to meet targets, goals, key performance indicators specifically in terms of internationalisation. Educators recommended better, improved practice in relation to internationalisation on a faculty and institution level.

One of the interviewees from the Scottish HEI spoke of future development through institutional learning:

“We need to do some institutional learning as to what works and what doesn’t work and why it doesn’t work. We need to work together to build cultural competence at the macro level and also at the meso level rather than just at the micro level. That to me is what we are missing at this point. We’re missing an academic framing of what are we doing to internationalise, what’s the purpose, and how are we going to get there”
(S1)

This interviewee also spoke of the necessity to ‘*divorce internationalisation from the cash cow mentality*’ (S1) and to approach internationalisation more holistically:

“Let everybody benefit from it so it’s more holistic rather than just “You are the assistant dean of internationalisation, you better go and get international students or else.” Do you know what I mean”? (S1)

Another interviewee from the same HEI made a similar point:

“I think we need to do a review of how we conceptualize internationalisation, how we came up with our policies and how we implement our policies for the good of the students, and this review needs to be holistic” (S3).

This interviewee also highlighted the importance of looking at the bigger picture and taking stock:

“We need to recognize where we are in the ecosystem, the professional ecosystem of internationalisation in Scotland, because actually, the ecology of internationalisation is quite well developed and diverse within Scotland but nobody [from this HEI] has actually stopped to look at it and say, well, where's our niche? Why don't we do that? What could we get better at? It's almost as if there's been no recognition that actually we don't need to do it all [...] It's about recognizing that we need to evolve and adapt to the environment, the niche where we find ourselves at present” (S3).

These findings support research by Alsharari (2018) who suggests that embedding internationalisation by changing the institutional language, culture, and attitudes into standard university practice is more likely to achieve success than when it is merely upheld as a goal (p. 360).

Vision and Values: Improve Understanding (allow the educator to be involved)

This research found that one way to improve internationalisation in HEIs for educators in the future may be by allowing educators to share experiences and best practice regarding internationalisation vision and values. By allowing educators to share how they internationalise effectively in their current role, and learn from best practice, it may improve all staff members' understanding of internationalisation and increase collaboration to support its successful implementation within the HEI.

Vision and Values: Ensuring Staff Agency

Research shows that successful implementation of policy requires participation of the stakeholders involved (Coburn and Stein, 2006). Participation and involvement of the educator is essential and is welcomed by most educators in this present study. The findings demonstrate good congruence with Alashoo et al. (2005), which acknowledge the importance of the educator understanding strategy and having connection with the vision, and in this case, the strategy and vision regarding internationalisation. Furthermore, findings from this research demonstrate that successful implementation of internationalisation relies upon faculty members, in this case, the educator, similar to the findings of Sanderson (2011).

The findings from this research suggest that internationalisation policy is important. Educators in this study who identified themselves as not having a clear understanding of internationalisation in their HEI context suggested that in order for

internationalisation to be successfully implemented and understood, the policy could be disseminated to them in a more systematic, fair and achievable way. The educators who participated in this study recommended that systems and resources are required for them to improve internationalisation in their HEI context.

3. Systems and Resources

When considering the future prospects of internationalisation in their HEI, the participating educators spoke of the need to improve the systems required to support internationalisation and to allocate more resources to it. Improved structures and systems requested by the educators include direct, supportive leadership and ensuring the responsibility of decision making or implementation is not the responsibility of the educator. Previous research by Ninomiya (2010) similarly recommends that internationalisation can be achieved in a HEI when leadership is present and the responsibility of decision making or implementation is not the responsibility of the educator.

A number of educators in this present study shared that they would prefer their HEI to be more systematic and organised in their approach to internationalisation. Suggestions made included guidelines, clarification on internationalisation as a policy, process, practice, system or resource, opportunities to feedback, someone allocated and committed to a role involving internationalisation are recommendations made by the participants in this present study. Examples include

“Our exchange coordinator does a great job, but she's an academic with a full-time job as well and she's running around, she's trying to do her best while she's also under pressure. That should be a full-time position for someone. If we're serious about internationalisation, that should be someone's job, their function, their role. It seems

to be delegated to people who are academics, who have full teaching commitments but also have an interest in that area, but that's not feasible. For example, when I was in Sweden the School of Education that I was engaging with had fulltime exchange officer so it's almost as if we're not thinking at the same level as colleagues elsewhere” (S1).

‘There are international projects with Taiwan and Singapore, but they are organized by individual teachers. More support from the University is required.’ (Japanese questionnaire respondent 5)

More sustainability and strategy around allocation of resources was also highlighted as something that should be part of future internationalisation plans

“I do think that what we’ve got to do is we’ve got to start thinking about cutting our cloths to fit the budgets that we’ve got because we are well into austerity. [...] we need to ask some questions about a sustainable internationalisation policy and initiatives. How do we sustain growth, but build track record?” (S1).

Another participant shared

‘Misplaced resource allocation to a select few to travel for partnership deals and no measureable outcomes are provided. No tangible outcomes meaning there is no way of colleagues to see the benefit of the allocation of resources for these trips. Very little planning with any agenda, purpose, remit or aim to these trips’ (Scottish questionnaire respondent 16).

And another commented

‘Getting to conferences etc. overseas is difficult as there is little to no support - yet this is something that is required of me to know the trends and developments within my field.’ (Australian questionnaire respondent 13)

In relation to the suggestions, a recurring theme in the responses for improving the future of internationalisation in HEIs from the educators in this study is the need and want for more time. Overwhelmingly, time is a valued and sought after resource. This finding echoes that of Green and Whitsed (2013) who claim that academics being at the “coalface of teaching and learning often feel under-informed, under-supported, underprepared, and under-confident when it comes to internationalisation” (p. 149) and that of Bedenlier and Zawacki-Richter (2015) who suggest that internationalisation has a major impact on faculty members on an individual level.

Systems and Resources: Intercultural Awareness and Global Citizenship

One aspect of future improvement regarding systems and resources required for internationalisation suggested by educators in this study was personal development and inclusion, in order to “increase one’s level of international and intercultural competencies” (Bedenlier and Zawacki-Richter, 2015, p.191). This may be due to the fact that all stakeholders within HEIs could benefit from development of cultural awareness and intercultural engagement (Mak and Kennedy, 2012). The professional development provided by the HEI may be specific to the HEI, just as internationalisation definitions, practices and policies are unique to a HEI (Yang, 2002) and the rationales which drive the process of internationalisation vary from region to region, country to country or even between institutions (Knight, 2007; 2014).

Schuerholz-Lehr et al. (2007) identified that faculty members who engaged in the professional development within their faculty relating to the process of internationalisation, reported changes in their perspectives and demonstrated the willingness to change their understandings particularly in the area of intercultural

awareness as part of internationalisation of the curriculum. The educators in this present study had similar ideas.

Systems and Resources: Collaboration as way to Improve Systems and Resources

Collaboration between educators in different HEIs was suggested by participants in this present study as a strategy to improve the understanding of internationalisation for the educator. By improving opportunities for collaboration, educators in this study believed that they could learn best practice and share resources. Findings from this study also suggested that improved collaboration of research on a global scale is necessary and would be welcomed by the educators. Such as

“I think we need to have a more international research network, but we should be more strategic in the conferences, the networks that people are going to, in order to contribute to a particular direction” (S4).

This recommendation is confirmed by a study comprehensive internationalisation of Dutch HEIs in which it was highlighted that “collaboration on an international scale, improves both research and education and offers the university a better situation in order to secure national and international research funding while also recruiting some of the best students and researchers some institutions have to offer. Some of the world leading universities recruit from one another and collaborate in-between on a global scale” (Popescu and Marjon, 2017, p.1514).

Common examples of collaboration between this study and the present study include “faculty exchange, joint workshops and research collaboration [...] prioritizing partnerships and facilitate better cooperation within the research, scholarships and institutional strategies.” (Popescu and Marjon 2017, p.1516).

4. Context

Findings from this study revealed that, at times, aspects of internationalisation experienced by an educator, may be particularly unique to a certain country and to a certain HEI. The context may also be influential to the educators understanding and experience of internationalisation in HE.

Commonalities and differences in terms of future recommendations for internationalisation in the future may occur depending on cultural and global context (between educators in similar and different HEIs). Particular aspects of internationalisation are unique to a certain country and, or a certain HEI (Schartner and Cho, 2017). In terms of this study, examples of unique aspects include access to resources, government legislation and guidelines and migration laws. A HEI's future approach to internationalisation could rely heavily on government policy and geographical position according to some educators in this study.

Context: Geography

According to the findings of this research, internationalisation can be unique to a HEI because of the country or geographical context which echoes the findings of Knight (2013) and Teichler (2010).

As Teichler (2017s) has suggested, internationalisation is regional and at times, global. Tange and Jenson (2012) acknowledge that a difference in perception of internationalisation can be because of the location of an HEI in an English speaking nation or not. Similarly, Galloway and Rose (2015) posit that movements due to internationalisation are increasingly linked to the role of English in the university setting.

Context: Government

There are several ways in which internationalisation is unique to a country including factors such as government influence and geographical position. Government influence could include how internationalisation is defined in higher education, where internationalisation is in terms to government priorities, the government budget allocation for internationalisation in education, how international students are processed and recruited, visa allocations and support for students with English as a Second Language (Teichler, 2004; 2017).

The governments of Australia, Japan and Scotland each have future goals and ambitions for internationalisation in higher education. Their aims and recommendations for improvement are somewhat similar to the suggestions of the educators in this study as explained in the following section.

Australia

The Australian Government is committed to advancing international education as they build upon their current opportunities and markets (Australian Government, 2016, p.5). The National Strategy for International Education 2025 is based upon three pillars: Strengthening the Fundamentals, Making Transformative Partnerships and Competing Globally (Australian Government, 2016). The National Strategy notes that there is a “clear role for government in facilitating growth of Australian international education” (Australian Government, 2016, p.5). Demonstrating the clear importance of government involvement in internationalisation of HEIs.

It has also been suggested “Australia will embrace opportunities to grow international education by being more innovative, inclusive and responsive to the needs of students and employers” (Australian Government, 2016, p.30), however, in accordance with

the findings of this research support for the educator is somewhat lacking. Furthermore, an aspect of the improvement process proposed by the National Strategy for International Education 2025 is to listen to international students and make sure their needs are met. Strategies adopted to do so include building student capacity and increased encouragement, however the educator is not specifically mentioned or referred to as a way in which to improve the student experience.

However, Australia is committed to improving education and research. As the findings of this study suggest supporting international mobility of students and staff is one way in which the Australian Government aims to do so (Australian Government, 2016) whilst promoting itself as a world-class international education provider, continuing to be a desirable destination and provider of international education.

Japan

According to Ota (2014) the internationalisation of HEIs in Japan, is a “government led endeavour” (Ota, 2014, p.227). The findings of this study and recent results from Times Higher Education (THE, 2019) show that it continues to be so, and that national initiatives have improved Japan’s global outlook and performance in areas including share of international students, international staff and exchange programmes.

Yonezawa (2017) notes that Japan’s prestigious and influential HEIs have “ambitious internationalisation strategies” (Yonezawa, 2017, p.377) which have been endorsed by the Japanese government via internationalisation projects. However, specific details regarding how the strategies are implemented or adopted are vague and congruent with the findings of this study. Ota (2014) noted that in the past “the individual-level activities have inadvertently come to play a major part in the ad hoc

internationalisation of Japanese universities” (Ota, 2014, p.228). Unfortunately, despite the efforts of the Top Global University Japan project (MEXT, 2019), the ad hoc approach could still be the case and significant work is still required to achieve internationalisation in Japanese HEIs beyond preparing for the 2020 Olympics games (Bothwell, 2019).

Scotland

The OECD states that “international activities of tertiary educational institutions have not only expanded in volume and scope, but also in complexity” (OECD, 2018, p.221). In Scotland, internationalisation in higher education continues to include international research collaborations and efforts to internationalise the curriculum (Weedon and Kong, 2015). HEIs continue to be supported by the Scottish Funding Council who support student and staff mobility as well as helping universities strengthen UK and overseas educational, research and investment activities (Scottish Funding Council, 2019).

Summary of Research Question Three

The future of internationalisation in HEIs has been considered and commented upon by educators in HE. Educators from this study note that internationalisation will continue to have consequences and implications for them in their role within the HEI. They have provided recommendations in an effort to improve internationalisation for educators in HE.

The main areas for future recommendations to improve the understanding and experience of educators in terms of the phenomenon that is internationalisation include: student experience, vision and values, support and resources within the HEI which at times can be contextual and hence the findings of this study highlight that

there would be benefits for the educator from collaborating with local, national and international colleagues in regards to improving the understanding and experience of internationalisation in HE.

Chapter Summary

Chapter Five has provided a critical discussion of the research findings in relation the existing literature presented in Chapter Two. This chapter identified how the findings of this present research build upon the research of others and why this research has been necessary.

Throughout the chapter the varying experiences that exist amongst educators in HEIs in Australia, Japan and Scotland predominantly within the School of Education were identified and discussed. As the everyday experience of the educator in HEI was the major focus of this research, the participant voice was provided throughout the chapter in the form of verbatim quotes that allowed the educators who participated in this study to be present. The participant voice highlighted and identified their significant and integral role within the HEI in terms of internationalisation, specifically their understanding, experiences and recommendations.

In the next chapter, the implications of the findings will be discussed as well as recommendations. The limitations of this study will also be presented.

CHAPTER SIX Conclusion

Introduction

This chapter presents a review of the research findings that are discussed in association with the research title and the three research questions. This chapter also includes the limitations and weaknesses of the research and how they were addressed followed by an autobiographical reflection. Finally, the potential impact of the research and recommendations for future research based on the findings and outcomes of this study are provided.

Synthesis of Findings

The aim of this study was to understand the lived experience of educators in regards to internationalisation in Higher Education (HE). The analysis of the experiences of these educators led to the study's findings that suggest educators experience and understand internationalisation in HE in a variety of ways. The findings showed the variety of experience of educators in terms of internationalisation in HE. The experiences ranged from positive to negative and involved several barriers and challenges regardless of the geographical location in Australia, Japan or Scotland. Additionally, the findings provide insights and recommendations from the educators in HEIs to improve the process, understanding and outcomes of internationalisation within their own context.

The majority of research on internationalisation in higher education has been focused on internationalisation as a process and as a rationale (de Wit, 2015; Knight, 2013)

including internationalisation of the curriculum (Dunne, 2011; Leask 2009), and international students (Teichler, 2017; Sawir, 2013).

The experiences of educators and recommendations to improve the process of internationalisation are rarely considered and required further examination (Wihlborg, 2009; Daniels, 2013). Therefore, the findings of the present study are significant because they build upon a limited field of literature (Bedenlier and Zawacki-Richter, 2015; Daniels, 2013; Pherali, 2012) to provide a better understanding of the importance of the educator and their contributions to internationalisation in higher education.

The purpose of the research was to explore the experiences and understandings of the educators in three different HEIs located in Australia, Japan and Scotland. The research intended to compare the lived experience of an educator in HE in terms of internationalisation.

Review of the Major Findings

Overall, the findings from this present study indicate that educators in HE, based upon their own perceptions and experiences in their own context, have varied understandings of the phenomenon that is internationalisation. On the whole, commonalities and differences arose between educators in regards to internationalisation whether they are in the same School of Education, HEI or in other HEIs based in Australia, Japan and Scotland. Several key themes were determined and include: the evolving definition of internationalisation in HE and HEIs, the impacts on the educator throughout the process of internationalisation, the barriers and challenges the educators face in their role and how professional development and other

recommendations can be utilised to improve the educator's overall understanding and practice of internationalisation as a phenomenon in HEIs.

Evolving Definition of Internationalisation

There were many definitions and experiences of internationalisation provided by the educators in this study. The responses differed from educators within the same School and HEI, as well as from educators in each of the HEIs included in the study. This finding is similar to the results of the empirical study of Wihlborg (2009) who investigated teachers' and students' experiences of internationalisation in relation to their own educational contexts from a pedagogical perspective and discovered that participants did not share a mutual understanding of the phenomenon of internationalisation. A conclusion that can be drawn from this is that internationalisation in HE continues to be a nebulous concept, ambiguous and unclear, and means different things to different people (Knight, 1994; Knight, 2007).

Impacts of Internationalisation on Educators (Barriers and Challenges)

The present study determined that internationalisation can have an impact on the educator in their role within their HEI context. The impacts experienced have included barriers and challenges for the educator. There have been several studies using qualitative approaches to understand personal perception and experience of internationalisation of faculty members. The studies identified the impacts of internationalisation on faculty members (Bedenlier and Zawacki-Richter, 2015) and the challenges faced by faculty members in their experiences of internationalisation. (Pherali, 2012).

Professional Development

The findings of this present study also highlighted that educators require professional development in order to have a common understanding of internationalisation within their HEI and in order to practice it more effectively. By having professional development educators would benefit from clear guidelines and expectations in regards to what is expected of them in terms of internationalisation in their HEI. Moreover, a common finding from educators in Higher Education Institutions in this study was that they could benefit from having more clarity, direction and support in their role when it comes to internationalisation processes. Specific examples include training and education for internationalisation of the curriculum and improved research collaboration. This could be the specific goal of the professional development provided in the HEI.

Geographical Location

The findings of this study hint that geographical location of an HEI may have some impact on how educators understand and experience internationalisation in their context. Factors relating to geographical location and context of the HEI include government (migration laws in terms of student and staff mobility, government stance and input in terms of internationalisation of the curriculum), and cultural norms and traditions (societal expectations).

Future Recommendations

The findings of this study presented several recommendations from educators to improve their experience of internationalisation in their HEI context and for its future success. Specifically, recommendations provided included aspects relating to Student Experience; Vision and Values; Systems and Resources.

Limitations of the Research

Participants and Sample

It was the intention of this study to achieve an understanding of an educator's lived experience of internationalisation in their own HEI context. It should be noted that this study has been concerned only with educators in HEIs and their experiences and understanding of internationalisation. The findings account for the experience of the educator rather than the policy maker, therefore, in some sense, opinions and views may be considered one-sided, or limited. However, including policy makers or other stakeholders within the HEI in the study was deemed unnecessary, unspecific and could have detracted from the main focus of the research undertaken. Remaining close to the inclusion criteria was essential despite its limitations.

With this limitation in mind, it is important to note the generalisation of findings of this study. This study is of a small sample size and it may not be a true representation of other educators' perceptions and experience. The findings of this study are limited to educators' in specific HEIs who agreed to participate in a questionnaire, and also, in some cases, a semi-structured interview. The study was also restricted to educators in only one institution in Australia, Japan and Scotland. The findings cannot be a generalisation of the many educators who experience internationalisation in their HEI. With 94 questionnaire respondents and 11 interviewees many converging and diverging ideas were provided which is a positive aspect of this research sample.

Researcher

A limitation of the research process can be attributed to the researcher effect faced by educational researchers investigating the places where they work (Mercer, 2007). Due to the fact that the staff were known to the researcher to some extent in the Scottish HEI, this may have had an effect on their response, perhaps demonstrating ‘informant bias’ (Mercer, 2007, p. 7), when a participant’s response may be influenced by how an interviewer is perceived by the participant. Additionally, there may be a link to the fact that the researcher is a student in the HEI and educators may have found it difficult to share their true opinions and experiences of internationalisation in their context.

It was important for the researcher to be aware of bias and objectivity. Positionality and objectivity throughout the research could have been considered a problem if not addressed. Having had experiences as an educator and student in Australia, Japan and Scotland, the researcher had to be aware of their unconscious bias and their own lived experience could be deemed a challenge. However, in order to overcome this challenge, a reflective journal was utilised by the researcher. The reflective journal allowed the researcher to take notes during and after data collection and analysis as part of the bracketing method associated with phenomenological inquiry.

Another point for consideration in terms of researcher limitations is perspective specificity (Rosenthal and Rosnow, 1975). Perspective specificity is worthy of consideration in terms of the fact that responses and findings may have varied if the participant had been different, creating a different reality. Being aware of this matter and how it may affect perception is important to this study and a further reason why the findings cannot be generalised.

Autobiographical Reflection

Reflexivity is necessary for the researcher throughout the research process and it allows the researcher to appreciate the nature of the research (Shaw, 2010). In order for the researcher to demonstrate what has been ‘going on’ during the research a reflective journal noting aspects of the research journey was utilised. The notes were recorded in first person and therefore this section will be presented in this way.

“‘Experience’ is a complex concept [it] usually occurs when something important has happened in our lives” (Smith et al., 2009, p.1). My experiences as an international teacher, leader and educator have motivated me to try and understand the complexities of being an educator in a HEI that is or striving to be internationalised.

As an educator I have experienced the challenges that come with implementing policy, institutional change, processes, goals, etc. all of which are not unique to internationalisation. I have also had first-hand experience of being an international student and understand the importance of requiring support, intercultural awareness and socio-cultural sensitivities. My experiences as an educator have included teaching and supervising international students as well as creating curriculum that is internationalised and inclusive.

These experiences have prompted me to study the literature around internationalisation in higher education more closely. Whilst reading about this topic I was interested in the rising expectations placed on the educator in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). I was interested in the fact that internationalisation has been, and continues to be, an area of great focus for HEIs and I was keen to discover how the educator is supported when following internationalisation processes in their daily role.

The sequential mixed method approach to this research allowed me to gain a snap shot of the perspectives of educators via questionnaire and afterwards, an insight into individual educator's lived experience obtained through the idiographic attributes of interpretative phenomenological analysis (IPA).

The application of an interpretative phenomenological approach is more than a description and interpretation of the participants' experiences because the researcher becomes immersed in the process and data (Gadamer, 1975). It is popular in studies that "investigate various reactions to, or perceptions of, a particular phenomenon [to help the researcher] gain some insight into the world of his or her participants and to describe their perceptions and reactions" (Fraenkel and Wallen, 2006, p.436). This approach provided me with an opportunity to enter into the individual educators' experience and try to interpret them through questions and answers, listening to them share their thoughts and feelings.

Interviewing the participant face to face was an effective way to also aid me in creating a picture of each educator. Meeting eight of the eleven participants in person was a great pleasure and highly rewarding. Placing myself in their context, literally, I gained a greater understanding of the HEI and their place within it. Meeting educators who are passionate about their work was inspiring. I continue to be in awe of their work and their achievements.

The research process, I have learned, is a tasking yet rewarding one. It is somewhat of a rollercoaster ride. Throughout the journey I have had the opportunity to reflect on my own practices as an educator and as a student.

Through my research I have attempted to answer how educators understand internationalisation in HE by focusing on their lived experience. I have some level of

insider knowledge of being an educator in secondary schools and HEIs in Australia, Japan and Scotland. Although it could be argued that my previous experience as an educator may influence my interpretations, I believe my own lived experience as an educator was beneficial and helpful throughout the research process. I ensured impartiality by paying close attention to the data and ‘bracketing out’ my own opinions and experiences about the phenomenon under study (Moustakas, 1994; Smith et al., 2009).

Although the findings from this research cannot be generalised, I do hope that the insights gained and the recommendations made from this research have provided an opportunity for educators to express themselves, and for their ongoing efforts and challenges relating to internationalisation in their HEI context, to be recognised and acknowledged.

Problems Arising During the Research

Location

Three locations (Australia, Japan and Scotland) where research was to be undertaken could have been considered a problem during the research as the geographical distance prohibited some face to face semi-structured interviews. However, Skype was successful and proved to be efficient and effective despite time differences. The location of questionnaire respondents did not pose any problems.

Recruitment of Sample Participants

Problems may arise relating to recruitment of participants and non-response during research (Bryman, 2016). In terms of this present study, some educators were reluctant to partake in research associated with their current job and employer due the sensitivities around sharing personal and work related experiences. Furthermore, recruiting for semi-structured interviews was a challenge as commitments of participants changed, cancelled and at times, rescheduled.

Specifically, the non-response and lack of willing participants to take part in semi-structured interviews from the Japanese HEI was disappointing and proved to be somewhat challenging. Language and cultural differences may have been the major contributing factors for the high non response rate.

Language

Language is significant for social researchers. In terms of this present social research it was considered important to understanding language, to know how words and specific terms are viewed in terms of the social world being studied (Bryman, 2016) In terms of this study, conducting research in a foreign language (Japanese) had its

limitations as there may have been a slight language barrier between the researcher and participants during the semi-structured interviews or during the translation of open ended questionnaire responses.

Although most correspondence was in English or translated by the researcher (and another confidant/colleague for checking for errors from Japanese to English and vice versa) there has to be some room allowed for human error and/or interpretation of responses. In a similar respect, Australian data collection may have at times been misinterpreted with use of colloquialisms, however procedures including re-reading of transcripts and repeated listening of audio recordings were in place to limit this as much as possible.

Recommendations

The aim of this study was to understand the lived experience of internationalisation in HEI by the educator.

The following recommendations are drawn from the findings of this research which is limited to a sample of educators in Australia, Japan and Scotland therefore they cannot be assumed to be applied generally. However, the recommendations from this study may be applied to universities and HEIs that have a vision and focus linked to, or based on, internationalisation. In particular, the recommendations may further support the educator in their role within a 21st Century higher education teaching and learning environment.

The findings from this research have contributed to the broader domain of Higher Education. By understanding the experiences of educators in terms of internationalisation in their HEI context a number of recommendations for educators, policy makers and further research arose and are now presented.

Recommendations to the HEI and policy makers for improving the experience of educators in terms of internationalisation in HEIs include:

- Recommendation One: Work Towards a Common Understanding

A recommendation is to try and ensure that within a HEI all stakeholders have a common understanding and input towards internationalisation. In order to do this each HEI needs to have a definition of internationalisation that is common to all staff within it. The definition could be one that already exists. Nevertheless, it is required to remove the challenge of the nebulous understanding of this phenomenon.

- Recommendation Two: Improve Communication

Ultimately, what is at stake here is that if the concept, definition, or goal relating to internationalisation within a HEI is unclear, it is likely that disconnect, dissatisfaction, misunderstandings, working in silos, inconsistency amongst staff and student experience and ultimately lack of progress in terms of internationalisation will continue within the HEI context. Therefore, establishing and clearly communicating goals that are consistent between and amongst departments/faculties within the HEI is recommended. Furthermore, openly sharing the rationale(s) for internationalisation and drivers for internationalisation via a transparent process is recommended.

- Recommendation Three: Ask and Listen to the Educator

In order to successfully internationalise a HEI it could be recommended that more needs to be done to understand the educator's perspective and experience of internationalisation. The findings from this research show that educators are on the whole eager to support internationalisation in their HEI for the benefit of themselves and their students. Their eagerness to support internationalisation could be used advantageously in the HEI context and should be of interest to policy makers who aim to succeed in internationalisation.

- Recommendation Four: Ensure Collaboration

Most educators, despite their varied yet somewhat converging understandings of internationalisation, already internationalise to an extent within their HEI. If their efforts were combined, recognized and valued a successful outcome could be a consequence as many of them have excellent ideas and strategies for future professional development to support improved and concise approaches to internationalisation in their HEI context.

- Recommendation Five: Reduce Disconnect

De Haan (2014) discovered a need to help universities reduce the ‘implementation gap’ between internationalisation plans and actual outcomes achieved in terms of internationalisation. The findings of this research show that disconnect occurs between the policy maker and the educator in regards to how internationalisation policy in HEIs is understood and how internationalisation in HEIs is implemented. The disconnect may be because their understanding, perception and interpretation of the international policy can be so different from one another. The educators and policy makers are likely to have different priorities and goals, therefore, it is understandable that there is a difference in understanding and implementing internationalization. Therefore, a reduction in the ‘implementation gap’ is recommended.

- Recommendation Six: Involve Stakeholders in Planning and Process of Internationalisation

In response to reducing the implementation gap or disconnect, Bartell (2003) suggests that a strategic planning process is necessary when internationalising a HEI and suggests the need for educators to be involved in the planning processes. The findings from this research has highlighted the need for more accountability, measurement and monitoring of internationalisation within HEIs. Specifically, in terms how the educator’s contributions towards internationalisation are recognised within the HEI.

- Recommendation Seven: Authentic Accessible Professional Development

Improved access to professional development in terms of internationalisation for educators is a recommendation from the findings of this study Professional development including training and collaboration. In addition, the promotion of professional development that is led by educators, professional services and policy

makers is recommended. Furthermore, preparing staff adequately for the arrival of international students would be beneficial.

Recommendations for Future Research

The findings from the present study open the door to further research and research studies that could:

- Further explore the commonalities and difference that occur between educators within HEIs in regards to internationalisation. In order to improve their overall experience and improve the outcomes for the HEI.
- Determine how the policy makers in HEIs view internationalisation with the aim of reducing the ‘disconnect’ between them and the educator in terms of this phenomenon.
- Compare how internationalisation as an outcome is measured or monitored differently between HEIs or compare patterns of success amongst and within HEIs (or faculty comparisons).
- Identify specific ways in which to support educators to successfully implement internationalisation support educators in their endeavours to internationalise, further understand their intrinsic motivations that drive their efforts to internationalise in their role as an educator.
- Investigate the other stakeholders within the HEI context by examining their opinions and lived experience including stakeholders in positions such as of those Head of Internationalisation/Director of Internationalisation.
- Lead to future policy creation or future targets for an HEI in terms of internationalisation.

Contribution to Research

This study contributes to current literature and research in the area of internationalisation in HE in the following ways:

- In an environment where the internationalisation of HE is constantly changing (Marmolejo, 2010) this study emphasises the need to accept and continue to adapt and encourage the learning and improved understanding of internationalisation in HEIs.
- The findings from the present study that internationalisation has several of impacts on educators are broadly in line with (Bedenlier and Zawacki-Richter, 2015) who note that “the impacts on academic faculty members resulting from internationalization are thus found on the macro-level of national higher education systems, the meso-level of the institution, and the micro-level of individual faculty members” (p.189).
- This research provided examples of how internationalisation is evidenced in the everyday role of the educator in HE and how they acknowledge that internationalisation will be a phenomenon that will continue to exist in HE into the future and a goal for their HEI. This is consistent with previous research of Galloway and Rose (2015) who posit that internationalisation remains to be a priority for HEIs and will continue to be.
- The methodology developed in this study may be useful for other researchers in the field of education who may decide to use IPA. The findings are a step toward using a method/methodology most commonly used in psychology can more commonly become a methodology for educational research when attempting to understand a research participant’s lived experience.

- The findings of this research suggest incompatibility between the goals of educators and the goals of the institutions in terms of internationalisation. This research identifies how HEIs can learn from educators about how to successfully achieve goals relating to internationalisation.

Chapter Summary

This thesis explored internationalisation with the aim of discovering how internationalisation as a phenomenon was understood and experienced by educators in HEIs in Australia, Japan and Scotland, predominately in Schools of Education. Through a sequential, mixed method approach of questionnaires and semi-structured interviews, the participants' experiences and perceptions were identified and analysed.

A finding from the study was that internationalisation processes, practices and definitions in HE, are continuously changing, they are understood differently and applied uniquely depending on the specific HEI and depending on the educator's individual, unique experience. Therefore, as internationalisation in HEIs continues to be complex for the HEI (Knight, 2004; de Wit 2002), more care and consideration should be given to the people who are somewhat responsible for the successful implementation of internationalisation in HE, the educator.

APPENDIX

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TITLE: INTERNATIONALISATION OF HIGHER EDUCATION: A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF EDUCATORS' EXPERIENCES			
RESEARCH QUESTION	LINKS TO QUESTIONNAIRE DATA	LINKS TO SEMI STRUCTURED INTERVIEW DATA	LINK TO THEME and LITERATURE
How do educators in HEIs understand and define internationalisation?	Questions 1 and 12	Questions G1 and S1	DEFINITION AND UNDERSTANDING
What are the experiences of the educator in regards to internationalisation?	Experiences: Questions 2, 3, 6 and 7 (11) Contribution: 4, 5, 5b	Questions G2, S2, S3, S4, S6	BENEFITS AND CHALLENGES/ WITHIN THEIR CONTEXT
What is the future of internationalisation for the educator in HEI and their recommendations for improvement?	Question 9 and 10	Questions S4, S5, S6	FUTURE/AGENCY/ ASPIRATIONS

Appendix. 1 Alignment of Research Questions, Semi-Structured Interview Schedule Questions and Questionnaire Questions

Appendix. 2 Sample of Questionnaire

Internationalisation of Higher Education from the perspective of the educator

Research Aim: To understand what educators say about Internationalisation of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs)?

Using the following 1-5 scale, please indicate, by filling the most correct response, the degree to which you agree with the statements listed below. Place additional comments in spaces provided.

Completion of this questionnaire will provide consent for your responses to be used as data. All responses will remain confidential. If you would prefer not to use your own email address, please enter anonymous@ac.uk/au/jp in the field below. You may be invited to participate in further research.

1. Email address *

2. Which School do you belong to?

Mark only one oval.

- Education
- Business and Enterprise
- Media, Culture and Society
- Science and Sport
- Engineering and Computing
- Health, Nursing and Midwifery
- Other: _____

3. What is your role in your HEI?

Mark only one oval.

- Educator
- Other: _____

1. I have a clear understanding of Internationalisation within my current HEI context

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

2. I encounter Internationalisation often in my current role

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

3. I am satisfied with the investment my organization makes in training and education specifically for Internationalisation

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

4. It is essential for me to follow policy and procedure in regards to Internationalisation

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

5. I believe my HEI provides me with sufficient resources to support the process of Internationalisation

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

Please provide further comment regarding your response

6. I receive support and professional development from my HEI in order to further understand Internationalisation

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

7. I was involved in the creation of Internationalisation policies and procedures at my HEI

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

8. I have significant input in the review of Internationalisation policies and procedures

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

9. I would appreciate the opportunity to have future involvement in the Internationalisation process of my HEI

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

Please provide examples of how you wish to be involved

10. Compared to other HEIs, my HEI is successfully Internationalised

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

11. To have intercultural competence is important in my current role

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

12. Please define internationalisation in your own words?

Appendix. 3 Sample of Japanese Questionnaire

大学の国際化に関する調査

*下記の質問について、5段階（1. 全くそう思わない、2. あまりそう思わない、3. どちらでもない、4. 少しはそう思う、5. 強くそう思う）で、ご回答下さい。（番号をマルで囲む）

また5、9、12の質問には、ご意見をお書き下さい。

*本質問紙調査の回答は、西スコットランド大学の厳格な倫理規定に則って処理され、個人情報
情報は守秘されますので、下記にお名前とメール・アドレスをご記入下さい。

お名前：

先生ご自身に就いてお伺いします。（該当するものにマルをつけて下さい。）

① 本学での所属部門

教育 / 人文・社会科学 / 自然科学・スポーツ / 工学・情報科学 / 健康科学 / その他

② 先生の本学での職責

教育職(Educator) / 管理運営職(Policy maker) / その他

③ 本学での勤務年数

1-3年未満 / 3-5年未満 / 5年以上 / その他

1. 本学の現況下における「国際化(Internationalisation)」状況を明確に理解している。

否定 (1. 2. 3. 4. 5.) 肯定

2. 本学における現在の職務において、「国際化」問題に出会うことがよくある。

否定 (1. 2. 3. 4. 5.) 肯定

3. 自身の所属組織における「国際化」に向けた教育活動への予算増額(investment)に満足している。

否定 (1. 2. 3. 4. 5.) 肯定

4. 私にとって、「国際化」に関する方針(policy)や手続き(procedure)に従うことは重要である。

否定 (1. 2. 3. 4. 5.) 肯定

5. 私は本学が「国際化」を進める過程を支援するのに十分なリソースを私に用意してくれているものと信じている。

否定 (1. 2. 3. 4. 5.) 肯定

*あなたの上の回答につきまして、ご意見(further comment)をお書き下さい。

People are talking about change now, which is good, but change happens very slowly in Japan.

6. 私は、「国際化」をより理解するために、本学から支援や専門的な講義(professional development)を受けている。

否定 (1. 2. 3. 4. 5.) 肯定

7. 私は、本学で「国際化」の方針(policies)や手続き(procedures)を決定することに関わってきた。

否定 (1. 2. 3. 4. 5.) 肯定

8. 私は、「国際化」の方針(policies)や手続き(procedures)の評価(review)について、重要な考え(input)を持っている。

否定 (1. 2. 3. 4. 5.) 肯定

9. 私は、今後の本学の「国際化」過程にもっと関わることを望む

否定 (1. 2. 3. 4. 5.) 肯定

*あなたの上の回答につきまして、どのように関わるのかをお書き下さい。

I think implementing different ideas or ways of doing things by the foreign staff would be good. I am foreign staff but I am also new, so maybe in a few years I can help.

10. 他大学(教員養成大学)と比べて、本学は「国際化」に成功している。

否定 (1. 2. 3. 4. 5.) 肯定

11. 「異文化対応能力(Intercultural competence)」を持つことは、今の自分の職務に重要である。

否定 (1. 2. 3. 4. 5.) 肯定

12. ご自分の言葉で「国際化」を「定義」して下さい。

The peaceful mixing of people from different cultures, coming together and exchanging ideas and ways of doing things to improve society.

本調査へのご回答、ご協力、有難うございました。

Appendix. 4 Examples of Thematic Analysis of Qualitative Questionnaire Data

Questionnaire respondent	Response	Code	Category
Scottish questionnaire respondent 1	N/A		
Scottish questionnaire respondent 2 SSI SAW	N/A		
Scottish questionnaire respondent 3	making the curriculum and content that the students learn more international, recruiting and supporting international students to increase the numbers, encouraging international collaborations, research trips and student experiences abroad to take place.	IS PM	FG
Scottish questionnaire respondent 4	N/A		
Scottish questionnaire respondent 5	Increasing the number and breadth of the student body which travels to study in the UK or who are taught by a UK university in their own country. The net effect of which should be a student		

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Questionnaire respondent	Response	Code	Category
Japanese questionnaire respondent 1	(in our case) it's the process, as Japanese educators, to review the present Japanese education by exchanging ideas with educators from abroad.	MOB	MOB
Japanese questionnaire respondent 2	Internationalisation is to improve and to change the function of universities through exchanges of students and teachers with those abroad, so that we can make our education and researchers better.	IS	
Japanese questionnaire respondent 3	People live with regulations understanding diverse cultures and environments. People with different ways of thinking interact each other across the border. The process to understand each	CUL IMP	IC & GC Not sure

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Appendix. 5 Participant Sheet and Consent Form

Participant Sheet

Name of department:

School of Education

UWS UNIVERSITY OF THE
WEST of SCOTLAND

Title of the study:

**Internationalisation of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs):
Understanding the who, what and why from the perspective
of the educator.**

*What do educators say about Internationalisation of Higher
Education?*

Introduction

My name is Laura Wilson and I am a PhD student at the University of the West of Scotland in the UK.

What is the purpose of this investigation?

Internationalisation is currently a priority for most Higher Education Institutions (HEI) around the world. How it is successfully achieved and measured is subject to interpretation. I want to understand the impacts of and for educators within the HEI when there is an inconsistent definition and understanding of internationalisation.

I am interested in finding out how you understand internationalisation within your context and the input you have towards its success. Furthermore, I am interested in your opinion as an educator/important stakeholder within a HEI that is internationalised and how you influence and contribute towards it.

As part of this study, I am seeking to questionnaire, interview and conduct a focus group with educators and certain gatekeepers who work within an Internationalised University.

Why have you been invited to take part?

You have been *invited to take part* in this study because you are an educator/member of leadership team within an Internationalised HEI and/or have been nominated by your HEI.

Do you have to take part?

You do not have to take part in the study, and even if you do agree to take part, you may withdraw at any time. If you do decide to withdraw, with your permission, only the data collected up to the point of withdrawal will be used.

Participating or not participating in the study will not affect your relationship/position within the HEI or with colleagues in any way.

What will you do in the project?

During the study you will be invited to complete a questionnaire, take part in a semi structured interview and take part in a focus group of which I will be the group leader. We will cover information such as:

- your views and understanding of internationalisation within your HEI.
- how you are involved in the process of internationalisation
- your experiences of internationalisation including your influence and input.

If any question makes you feel uncomfortable, you do not need to answer. You can be assured that information collected during each stage of research will remain confidential.

What happens to the information in the project?

The findings from this study will be published in my final PhD Thesis and consequent journal publications. However, your name will never be mentioned and all participants who take part will remain anonymous. The information that you provide us with will be kept for six months before being destroyed.

Thank you for reading this information – please ask any questions if you are unsure about what is written here.

What happens next?

If you are happy to be involved in the project, you should sign your name on the attached consent form. If you do not want to be involved in the project, then I would like to thank you for your attention.

This investigation was granted ethical approval by the School of Education: University of the West of Scotland ethics committee.

Researcher Contact Details:

Ms Laura Wilson
University of the West of Scotland
Paisley Campus
High Street, Paisley PA1 2BE
Scotland

Should you wish to discuss any aspect of this research with someone other than Ms L Wilson, please contact:

Dr Lisa McAuliffe
School of Education
University of the West of Scotland
Ayr Campus
Scotland

Consent Form

There are two copies of this consent form – one will be retained by the participant and, one will be retained by the researcher.

Name of department:

School of Education

Title of the study:

Internationalisation of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs): Understanding the who, what and why from the perspective of the educator

- I confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet for the above project and the researcher has answered any queries to my satisfaction.
- I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw from the project at any time, without having to give a reason and without any consequences.
- I understand that I can withdraw my data from the study at any time up to the point of data analysis.
- I understand that any information recorded in the investigation will remain confidential and no information that identifies me will be made publicly available.
- I consent to being a participant in the project.
- I consent to being audio recorded as part of the project Yes/No

I (PRINT NAME)	Hereby agree to take part in the above project
Signature of Participant:	Date

Dear Colleague,

My name is Laura Wilson and I am a PhD student at the University of the West of Scotland in the UK.

I am currently researching Internationalisation of Higher Education, specifically, Understanding Internationalisation of Higher Education from the perspective of the educator.

I would greatly appreciate your involvement and that of selected staff members in the collection of my primary data – specifically a Semi Structure Interview between 30-40 minutes.

Please find attached my research questions and intended research methods and letter of participation.

Many thanks for your consideration and I look forward to hearing from you in the near future.

Yours sincerely,

Researcher Contact Details:

Ms Laura Wilson

University of the West of Scotland

Paisley Campus

High Street, Paisley PA1 2BE

Scotland

Appendix. 6 Sample of Semi Structured Interview (SSI) Questions

Guiding questions used during SSI:

G1. In your opinion, what is Internationalisation at ___?

G2. How do you experience Internationalisation at ___?

It could be suggested that Internationalisation is a phenomenon in Higher Education.

What are your experiences of Internationalisation in the HE context of ___?

Sub questions:

S1. As an educator, how are/were you informed about internationalisation within your HEI?

S2. In what ways are you supported in ensuring that internationalisation takes place within your role?

S3. How is internationalisation monitored within your role?

S4. In what ways have you been/would prefer to be professionally developed in regards to internationalisation?

S5. How do you think your HEI compares with other Internationalised HEIs?

S6. What input do you have in the creation and review of policies and agendas in regards to internationalisation?

S7. What do you envisage for the future direction of internationalisation for your HEI and your role within it? What are your recommendations?

Appendix. 7 Interviewee Responses to Questionnaires and Interview Information

Participant	Qu1	Qu2	Qu3	Qu4	Qu5	Qu6	Qu7	Qu8	Qu9	Qu10	Qu11
A1	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	4	4	4
A2	1	4	1	5	2	1	4	4	4	1	5
A3	5	4	4	4	4	2	3	1	3	4	5
A4	5	5	4	4	4	2	2	1	3	4	4
J1	3	2	4	5	3	4	2	1	5	3	5
J2	3	4	2	5	3	2	2	4	5	3	5
J3	4	5	4	4	3	3	1	2	3	4	5
S1	3	4	1	2	2	2	1	1	3	1	4
S2	5	3	4	1	3	4	1	1	1	3	1
S3	2	5	1	3	2	1	1	2	5	2	5
S4	5	2	1	5	3	3	2	1	3	3	5

Candidate	Question 5	Question 9	Question 12
J1	People are talking about change now, which is good, but change happens very slowly in Japan.	I think implementing different ideas or ways of doing things by the foreign staff would be good. I am foreign staff but I am also new, so maybe in a few years I can help.	The peaceful mixing of people from different cultures, coming together and exchanging ideas and ways of doing things to improve society.
J2	I have hardly ever been informed of what's going on as far as 'internationalisation' events are concerned.	I don't think I am expected.	To get closer to global standard.
J3	I belong to the course to promote global education, but I rarely get information because I am specially appointed only for three years.	It's difficult because of my present position (educator).	It's a term to be used for closed countries like Japan when they want to be westernised.
S1	N/A	N/A	Internationalisation for me comes through in the way we design and construct the

			curriculum. It also requires us to be culturally sensitive to our students prior educational experience and to their learning needs. We also need to account for differences in communication between different people from different cultural contexts and help to support them to communicate across the language boundaries. I also believe that internationalisation ought to provide Scottish students the opportunity to study part of their programme in another country.
S2	N/A	N/A	N/A
S3	I think that Internationalisation needs to be (re)defined within this organisation, and that this process should involve all staff (*and students).	I would like to discuss the meaning of the word; the nature of Internationalisation with regard to this university, and to be involved in an iterative process of defining, reflection and evaluation.	Internationalisation refers to the layers of support of all university staff and students in preparing for, and developing the university experience, of ALL students; it requires the development of shared goals; of awareness among staff and students to enable us to become, and behave like, global citizens; and an understanding of the ways that we will all benefit from being a (truly) international university at this time, and in this global community. It is more than International students bringing money to the university.
S4	N/A	N/A	providing learning and teaching opportunities that extend beyond the UK and activities that broaden one's horizons and outlook.
A1	I don't really understand the HEI's agenda in this regard nor what is expected of me in order to support it	conceptually about directions we might like to take and possibly brainstorming on	As applied to higher education, internationalisation seems to be mostly about profit-making through tapping into markets outside Australia to run programs badged by our

		what we could/should do.	university. It is partly about our branding internationally, but also involves bringing students into our uni from other parts of the world.
A2	No time nor workload but expectation to take part.	N/A	In my words... to develop the intercultural understanding of students who may well spend their whole lives thinking that Internationalism is eating spicy food and watch foreign movies
A3	If directly involved in international, HE programs support is strong. Otherwise on local issues especially HDR students support is limited.	N/A	Universities have a responsibility to discover new knowledge and to disseminate that knowledge widely. Knowledge and values are culturally related and interpreted. To fulfil its social responsibilities institutions need to understand the multiple cultures that it is exposed to and to accommodate their values and beliefs in the processes of dissemination of new knowledge. In doing so, universities have an obligation to treat all cultures with dignity and respect. Internationalisation is the process through which Universities assume a global role in knowledge building.
A4	N/A	N/A	Knowledge, understanding and a cultural awareness of international issues, education systems and needs and customs of the diverse range of students in our Institutions

Interview dates

AUS: 04/10/17 (A1), 6/10/17 (A2), (10am), 6/10/17 (A3) (11am), 09/10/17 (A4)

SCOT: 12/09/17 (S1), 14/09/17 (S2), 13/11/17 (S3), 05/12/17 (S4)

JAP: 10/12/17 (J1), 10/12/17 (J2), 10/12/17 (J3)

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